

TRANSFORMING OPEN RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION THROUGH CHARM
TORCH

DELIVERABLE D11.1 – TORCH: ANNUAL OPEN FORUM 2 REPORT

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY: ANNUAL OPEN FORUM 2 REPORT

The second TORCH Open Forum, under the title **'Sharing Common R&I Policies and Strategies: Strengthening Collaboration Towards a Transformational Approach'**, was held on March 8, 2023, hosted by Trinity College Dublin.

The meeting was addressed to multiple relevant collectives: university Rectors and Vice Rectors, academic and technical staff, as well as any actors engaged in R&I activities and universities' collaboration. It was also relevant for policymakers, as the European Commission's perspective was included. More than 120 participants attended the different sessions (online and/or in person), in which 61 chairs, speakers and rapporteurs took part representing several European and national organizations as well as 15 European University Alliances.

The event encouraged reflection on the Alliance's shared common R&I policies and strategies, discussed pioneering initiatives of universities regarding transdisciplinary and challenge-driven research, and provided the possibility to share results and achievements related to five key R&I areas:

1. Working towards reforming research assessment.
2. Fostering equality, diversity and inclusivity.
3. Championing Open Science.
4. Promoting inter/transdisciplinary research driven by societal challenges.
5. Intensifying R&I Cooperation Between Universities.

The Plenary Session on the **'ERA's Policy Agenda 2022-2024 and R&I Cooperation Between European Universities'** brought together a diverse panel of speakers who discussed the role of the Alliances as innovative living labs within the ERA's framework. Representatives of different entities shared their views on the Policy Agenda, such as the Coimbra Group, the European University Association, and Science Europe. Links and intersections between the different actions included in the Agenda were highlighted and the (potential) activities of Alliances were also discussed.

The Panel Session on **'The European perspective on the reform of research assessment'** presented the latest approaches and progress on the revision of the evaluation systems for research institutions, researchers, and funding agencies. All the participants agreed on the need to reform research assessment, such process being a priority for the new European Research Area. The roadmap established by the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) was discussed, including the European Commission's (DG RTD) perspective.

The **TORCH Cluster Sessions ('Progress on joint R&I strategies in European University Alliances')** served the purpose of exchanging experiences and practices among several Alliances:

- Cluster 1: **'New approaches for diverse academic careers'**. Six Alliances (CHARM-EU, ARQUS, FORTHEM, YUFE, CIVIS, and EPICUR) shared their progress and plans to promote Open Science and Equality, Diversity and Inclusivity, as well as presented some specific actions and strategies on reforming research assessment.
- Cluster 2: **'Intensifying R&I cooperation between universities'**. Eight examples of initiatives to build collaborative frameworks for joint and shared R&I-related activities were shared by FORTHEM, EELISA, SEA-EU, UNIC, ECIU, CIVIS, and CHARM-EU.
- Cluster 3: **'Promoting inter/transdisciplinary research driven by societal challenges'**. Good practices and strategies on exploring joint transdisciplinary, challenge-driven research were discussed by representatives of CHARM-EU, EC2U, FilmEU, Circle U, CIVICA, Una Europa, and FORTHEM.

The Panel Session **'University with and for Society: promoting Citizen Science within Open Science'** brought together representatives of different universities to discuss their institutional plans and support systems to foster Citizen Science.

This report constitutes TORCH's deliverable D11.1, and contains the Forum Agenda, followed by a debriefing of the meeting sessions, as well as the main outcomes and conclusions. All presentations used during the meeting are collected in Annex II.

1. INTRODUCTION & FORUM OBJECTIVES

CHARM-EU represents a Challenge-Driven, Accessible, Research-based and Mobile model for the co-creation of a European University aligned with the European Values and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It is an initiative founded by five research-based universities (University of Barcelona –UB, Trinity College Dublin –TCD, Utrecht University –UU, Eötvös Loránd University Budapest –ELTE, and University of Montpellier –UM), which has recently grown with four new partners (Åbo Akademi University –ÅAU, Julius-Maximilian-Universität Würzburg, –JMU, Hochschule Ruhr West –HRW, and University of Bergen –UiB).

The TORCH Project enhances CHARM-EU's academic and research networks, as it builds up the R&I dimension of CHARM-EU, promoting a challenge-driven transformative agenda with a transdisciplinary and intercultural vision, laying its foundation in three Cross Cutting Principles of RRI: Interdisciplinarity, Gendered Innovation, Ethics and Integrity; and four Transformational Modules: Common R&I Agenda, Cooperation with Non-Academic Actors, Open Science Practices, Citizen Science and Public Engagement.

Concept Note

The second TORCH Annual Forum was entitled “Sharing Common R&I Policies and Strategies: Strengthening Collaborations Towards a Transformational Approach”. The hybrid event (hosted by Trinity College Dublin) was open to stakeholders engaged in research and innovation as well as university-industry-citizen collaboration.

Within its Research & Innovation dimension (TORCH), the CHARM-EU Alliance is developing its challenge-driven transformative R&I agenda based on a transdisciplinary and intercultural vision to solve complex societal challenges. The TORCH Forum provided the possibility to share results and achievements related to the project and discuss them together with stakeholders, other European University Alliances and Research Performing Organizations. The meeting focused on five key R&I areas:

1. Working towards reforming research assessment.
2. Fostering equality, diversity and inclusivity.
3. Championing Open Science.
4. Promoting inter/transdisciplinary research driven by societal challenges.
5. Intensifying R&I Cooperation Between Universities.

The event encouraged reflection on the Alliance’s shared common R&I policies and strategies, discussed pioneering initiatives of universities regarding responsible research and innovation (RRI), and uncovered legal, financial and regulatory barriers to Alliances’ collaborative endeavors. It also

included the outlook of the European Commission and stakeholders interested in research and innovation and university-industry-citizen collaboration.

Exploring synergies and sharing best practices with other European University Alliances that are addressing the same challenges facilitates all HEIs to support innovative solutions and progress in their respective common science agendas. Such sharing of knowledge also supports the values of the ERA policy agenda¹, which lays out a number of priority actions for that period, some of which provide a framework to strengthen future cooperation among Alliances, namely: Action 13 (“Empower Higher Education Institutions to develop in line with the ERA, and in synergy with the European Education Area”), and Action 17 (“Enhance the strategic capacity of Europe’s public research performing organizations”).

Intensifying R&I cooperation between universities involves not only developing aligned policies and transformative actions on strategic areas (research assessment; equality, diversity and inclusivity; Open Science; inter- and transdisciplinary challenge-driven research), but also establishing mutually beneficial partnerships to efficiently share knowledge and competences, exploring efficient governance models that facilitate the sharing of resources and capacities, the streamlining of administrative processes to support research activities, the creation of joint structures, and the establishment of mutual recognition agreements. The European Council and Commission encourage deeper cooperation and the pooling of knowledge and resources to deepen cooperation between HEIs, and invite the Member States to remove obstacles to more compatible higher education systems². This provides a framework for a more effective transnational cooperation structure, by which interconnected HEIs are better ready to fulfil all their missions and tackle the great societal challenges. Furthermore, it opens up an “opportunity for HEIs to explore the necessity, benefits, risks and feasibility of setting up institutionalized cooperation instruments, such as a possible legal status for Alliances”³.

Promotion & Dissemination

The 2nd TORCH Annual Forum was open and publicized through different means and communication channels in order to reach the relevant target audience and maximize the number of participants.

In terms of internal dissemination within the CHARM-EU and TORCH communities, the event was shared via email with the whole community (≈500 people) involved in the CHARM-EU Alliance and

¹ European Commission (2021). European Research Policy Agenda: Overview of the actions for the period 2022-2024. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Available at https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-11/ec_rtd_era-policy-agenda-2021.pdf

² European Council (2022). Council conclusions on a European strategy empowering higher education institutions for the future of Europe. Luxembourg: Official Journal of the European Union, 21-4-2022 (2022/C 167/03). Available at [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52022XG0421\(02\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52022XG0421(02))

³ European Commission (2022b). Proposal for a Council Recommendation on building bridges for effective European higher education cooperation. Strasbourg, 18/1/2022 COM(2022). Available at <https://education.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2022-01/proposal-council-recommendation-bridges-european-higher-education-cooperation.pdf>

its educational and/or research projects (scientific and technical staff, teachers and researchers participating in diverse related activities). The event was included in the highlights section of the of the 2023 February edition of [CHARM-EU Newsletter](#) (sent out to ≈1000 subscribers). In addition, all CHARM-EU partner universities distributed the invitation internally among their respective communities.

A [specific webpage](#) was created for the event within the official CHARM-EU website including information on the context, programme, registration and practical matters. Specific promotional material was designed to announce the Forum (see posters in Annex I). Registration was managed through the CHARM-EU website.

Following the CHARM-EU and TORCH communication and dissemination strategies and in order to maximize participation and impact, the event was also promoted on social media via different official channels of the Alliance (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and Instagram) as well as its partner institutions⁴.

The event was also featured in the 2023 February edition of the [Coimbra Newsletter](#) and was shared on the social media accounts of other European University Alliances and organizations with relevant audience such as the European University Association or Campus engage⁵.

Participation

The TORCH Forum was addressed to universities leadership, researchers and innovators, European University Alliances staff, and any actors engaged in R&I activities and management. It was also relevant for policymakers, as the European Commission's perspective was included. The number of participants is shown in Table 1⁶.

Table 1. TORCH Open Forum number of participants (see agenda).

No.	Participants	No.	Participants
221	Individual registrations prior to the event	34	Participants in Cluster 1
68	Individual in-person registrations	33	Participants in Cluster 2
28	Female Chairs/Speakers/Rapporteurs	17	Participants in Cluster 3
32	Male Chairs/Speakers/Rapporteurs		

⁴ For the detailed social media campaign on the CHARM-EU channels (with data about the number of impressions/people reached until March 14, 2023), see Section 4. Outcome & Conclusions.

⁵ See examples in Annex I.

⁶ See footnote 4 for details on online/in-person engagement.

Organizing Committee

The Forum was organized by TORCH staff in close collaboration with the TORCH WPs Leaders. The Forum Organizing Committee is as follows (in alphabetical order):

- Doris Alexander (Associate Director of European Engagement, TCD).
- Brian Broderick (Associate Dean of Research, TCD).
- Siobhán Callaghan (Research Fellow, TCD).
- Meritxell Chaves (Secretary General, CHARM-EU).
- Daniel Griffin (CHARM-EU Teaching Fellow, TCD).
- Kirsten Hollaender (Project Manager, UU).
- Jenny Kirkwood (Administrative Officer, TCD).
- Pia Le Grand (Head of International Cooperation, ÅAU).
- Jaime Llorca (Project Manager, UB).
- Gemma Marfany (Rector's Delegate for Scientific Dissemination, UB).
- Veronika Peciarova (Project Manager, UM).
- Conor Spillane (Project Manager, TCD).
- Mária Szulovszky (Communications Coordinator, ELTE).

This Report

This report constitutes TORCH's deliverable D11.1, and contains the Forum Agenda, followed by a debrief of all sessions and presentations, as well as the main conclusions drawn from the discussion. All presentations (ppt) showed during the event are collected in Annex II. The report is to be published in the Project's website and distributed among the fellow University Alliances and any other interested stakeholders.

2. FORUM PROGRAMME

Sharing Common R&I Policies and Strategies: Strengthening Collaborations Towards a Transformational Approach.

2nd TORCH Annual Open Forum. March 8, 2023. Trinity College Dublin.

Venue: Regent House, Trinity College Dublin, College Green, Dublin 2.

Format: In-person (+ hybrid).

9:00 – 9:30 | Registration

9:30 – 10:00 | Opening Ceremony

Presenter: JENNIFER DALY, Office of the Dean of Research, Trinity College Dublin.

Speakers:

- LINDA DOYLE. Provost and President, Trinity College Dublin.
- JORDI GARCIA. Vice Rector for Research, University of Barcelona.
- KATE MORRIS. Head of Campus Engage, Irish Universities Association.

10:00 – 11:15 | Plenary Session | ERA's Policy Agenda 2022-2024 and R&I Cooperation Between European Universities

Chair: MERITXELL CHAVES. Secretary General, CHARM-EU.

Speakers:

- ADRIEN BRAEM. Senior Policy Officer, Science Europe. *Science Europe's perspective on the new European Research Area.*
- GARETH O'NEILL. Principal Consultant on Open Science, Technopolis Group. *European Universities and Areas of Institutional Change.*
- EMMANUELLE GARDAN. Director of Coimbra Group. *Coimbra Group's perspective on the new European Research Area.*
- STEPHANE BERGHMANS. Director of Research & Innovation, European University Association. *EUA's perspective on the new European Research Area.*

Rapporteur: MÁRIA SZULOVSKY. Communications Coordinator, Eötvös Loránd University.

11:15 – 11:30 | Coffee Break

11:30 – 12:30 | Panel Session | The European Perspective on the Reform of Research Assessment

Chair: REKO LEINO. Vice Rector for Research, Åbo Akademi University.

Speakers:

- JEAN-EMMANUEL FAURE. Team leader of Research assessment, DG Research & Innovation, European Commission. *Reforming research assessment.*
- STEPHANE BERGHMANS. Director of Research & Innovation, European University Association. *A Reform of Research Assessment. The Agreement & CoARA Coalition - A University Perspective.*
- TERESA MAGUIRE. Director of Research Strategy & Funding, Irish Health Research Board. *Reform of Research Assessment - Research funder perspective.*
- PAUL BOSELIE. Chair Recognition & Rewards in Open Science, Utrecht University. *The European perspective on the reform of research assessment.*

Rapporteur: PIA LE GRAND. Head of International Cooperation, Åbo Akademi University.

12:30 – 13:30 | Lunch Break

13:30 – 15:00 | TORCH Clusters | Progress on Joint R&I Strategies in European University Alliances

· Cluster 1 | New Approaches for Diverse Academic Careers

Chair: CATHERINE COMISKEY. Professor in Healthcare Modelling and Statistics & Academic Director of CHARM-EU, School of Nursing and Midwifery, Trinity College Dublin.

Speakers:

- NINA SHIEL, Trinity College Dublin (CHARM-EU/TORCH). *CHARM-EU Inclusivity Plan: An Intersectional Approach to Attain Equality in R&I.*
- PIA VOIGT, Universität Leipzig. DANIELA PICHLER, Universität Graz (ARQUS R&I). *How to foster Open Science - Results from an ARQUS-wide Survey among Researchers and derived Recommendations.*
- KATARZYNA MOLEK-KOZAKOWSKA, University of Opole (FIT FORTHEM). *Modelling Citizen Science for Education (MSCEDU): Insights from introducing Citizen Science to schools by FORTHEM Alliance universities.*
- MARIA PIETILÄ, JOUNI KEKÄLE, University of Eastern Finland (YUFERING). *YUFERING portfolio in researcher assessment.*
- MIHNEA DOBRE, University of Bucharest. RAFAELLA LENOIR, Autonomous University of Madrid. FABIEN BORGET, Aix-Marseille Université (RIS4CIVIS). *Exploring a Path to Research Assessment Reform in a European University Alliance: RIS4CIVIS.*

- ANDREAS RAGGAUTZ, Universität Graz (ARQUS R&I). *Pilot: activity framework and research assessment reform.*
- THRASYVOULOS TSIATSOS, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (EPICUR). *The deployment of a model researcher assessment framework (EPIQAssess) in the EPICommunity platform.*
- MARIJANNEKE VIJGE, Utrecht University (CHARM-EU / TORCH). *CHARM-EU: Towards Reforming Research Assessment.*

Rapporteur: JENNY KIRKWOOD. Administrative Officer CHARM-EU, Trinity College Dublin.

· Cluster 2 | Intensifying R&I Cooperation Between Universities

Chair: FERENC TAKÓ. Head of CHARM-EU Office, Eötvös Loránd University.

Speakers:

- NICOLE BIRKLE, Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz (FORTHEM / FIT-FORTHEM). *The FORTHEM Joint Research Services and Policy Office.*
- ISABEL SALGUEIRO, Polytechnic University of Madrid. DAVID SCHKADE, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität (EELISA InnoCORE). *EELISA InnoCORE and EELISA Unfolds: opening up our innovation ecosystems, building joint initiatives for innovators and entrepreneurs.*
- GWENDOLINE TRAINSEL, Université de Bretagne Occidentale (SEA-EU / ReSEArch-EU). *Building a common strategy in a multidisciplinary alliance: identifying and matching the research forces with societal challenges.*
- JOHN BARIMO, University College Cork. BANU LIMAN, Koç University. ROBERTO SAN SALVADOR, University of Deusto (UNIC). *Towards a strategy for 'engaged' research and a collaborative roadmap with cities and city stakeholders.*
- PÁDRAIG MURPHY, Dublin City University (ECIU SMART-ER). *Organising alliance institutions to pilot bottom-up challenge-based research.*
- CIRO FRANCO, Sapienza University of Rome (RIS4CIVIS). *Sharing of Research Infrastructures, for the benefit of CIVIS Alliance community.*
- MARTIN GALVIN, University College Cork. SARI HIRVONEN-KANTOLA, University of Oulu. SARA BJARSTORP, Malmö Universitet (UNIC). *Infrastructure for Research - UNIC Centre for City Futures.*
- ARNAUD FABRE, University of Montpellier (CHARM-EU / TORCH). *TORCH TTOs virtual network.*

Rapporteur: KIRSTEN HOLLAENDER. Project Manager, Utrecht University.

· Cluster 3 | Promoting Inter/Transdisciplinary Research Driven by Societal Challenges

Chair: RAUL RAMOS. Vice Rector for Internationalization Policy, University of Barcelona.

Speakers:

- ALBERT DIAZ, VICENTE ROYUELA, University of Barcelona (CHARM-EU / TORCH). *TORCH Common Science Agenda: A Multidisciplinary Approach to Develop SDG-driven Research Challenges.*
- LUDOVIC THILLY, Université de Poitiers. (EC2U / RI4C2). *Inter-disciplinary research promoted by the EC2U Virtual Institutes.*
- DAITHÍ MAC SÍTHIGH, Institute of Art, Design + Technology (FilmEU). *Dynamic research clusters in film and media arts.*
- DAVID SITBON, Université Paris Cité (Circle U). *When Circle U. meets interdisciplinarity.*
- SÉBASTIEN HUBER, European University Institute (CIVICA). *Promoting interdisciplinary research centred around CIVICA's four thematic priorities.*
- AINE MOORE, University College Dublin (Una Europa). *Una Europa's vision towards interdisciplinary hubs for research.*
- NICOLE BIRKLE, Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz (FORTHEM / FIT-FORTHEM). *The New FORTHEM Research, Innovation and Transfer Mission – background and content.*

Rapporteur: VERONIKA PECIAROVA. Project Manager, University of Montpellier.

15:00 – 15:30 | Short Break

15:30 – 16:30 | Panel Session | University with and for Society: Promoting Citizen Science within Open Science

Chair: GEMMA MARFANY. Rector's Delegate for Scientific Dissemination, University of Barcelona.

Speakers:

- MARKO JOAS, Vice Rector for Collaboration. MATS LINDFELT, Director of Research Services, Åbo Akademi University. *Piloting Citizen Science Support through Small Scale Projects – The Case of Åbo Akademi University.*
- LUKAS WORSCHKECH. Head of Division Research and Technology Transfer, Julius-Maximilian-Universität Würzburg. *Citizen science as part of knowledge transfer actions with SMEs.*
- ELLEN ROEMER. Hochschule Ruhr West. *Opportunities for Citizen Science Projects - Experiences at Ruhr West University of Applied Science.*
- JOSEP PERELLÓ. Director of OpenSystemsUB, University of Barcelona. *Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action: The experience of the CoAct EU project.*

Rapporteur: JAIME LLORCA. TORCH Project Manager, University of Barcelona.

16:30 – 16:45 | Closure

Speaker: BRIAN BRODERICK. Associate Dean of Research, Trinity College Dublin.

3. FORUM DEBRIEF

The section below shows a brief summary of the meeting development, with the minutes of all sessions and presentations.

3.1 Opening Ceremony⁷

Universities leadership open the event.

Opening Ceremony

Presenter: JENNIFER DALY, Office of the Dean of Research, Trinity College Dublin.

Speakers:

- LINDA DOYLE. Provost and President, Trinity College Dublin.
- JORDI GARCIA. Vice Rector for Research, University of Barcelona.
- KATE MORRIS. Head of Campus Engage, Irish Universities Association.

Rapporteur: JAIME LLORCA. TORCH Project Manager, University of Barcelona.

The inaugural ceremony is presented by **Dr. Jennifer Daly** (Office of the Dean of Research, Trinity College Dublin), and is opened by **Prof. Linda Doyle** (Provost and President, Trinity College Dublin), who welcomes all participants to the 2nd TORCH Annual Forum and emphasizes the importance of organizing such meetings in the European R&I context. It is essential for universities to work together, as the UN Sustainable Development Goals can only be addressed in a cooperative manner. Collaboration is vital for universities, especially when it comes to research. The University Alliances are now seen as an important stakeholder in delivering a European Research Area, a European Education Area, and in developing the new European Innovation Agenda. TORCH is also distinctive for the emphasis it places on interdisciplinarity. Prof. Doyle wishes all participants a fruitful meeting, and thanks the TCD staff involved in the Project.

University of Barcelona's Vice Rector for Research, **Prof. Jordi Garcia**, greets all attendees, thanks the Trinity College Dublin and its Provost for hosting the event, and stresses importance of collaboration among universities regarding their education and research missions. Prof. Garcia highlights the participation in the TORCH Forum, which welcomes representatives of the Coimbra Group, the European University Association and CoARA, the Irish Universities Association, Science Europe, the Irish Health Research Board, and the DG Research & Innovation (EC), as well as members of 14 fellow Alliances. In addition, around 230 participants registered for the Forum.

⁷ Session recording available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ka8oO7n4Nck>.

TORCH completed its first stage, and we are now in its second, focused on developing common policies/strategies for the CHARM-EU Alliance and implementing a series of pilot actions within five key R&I areas: 1) Working towards reforming research assessment; 2) Fostering equality, diversity and inclusivity; 3) Championing Open Science; 4) Promoting inter/transdisciplinary research driven by societal challenges, 5) Intensifying R&I Cooperation Between Universities. The great global challenges must be addressed through interdisciplinary research, or even, “undisciplinary” research. Alliances should act as a bridge between universities and society. Exploring synergies, sharing knowledge, facilitating the exchange of best practices among Alliances are key aspects of what we do. All this provides an invaluable input for HEIs to support innovative solutions and progress their respective R&I agendas, besides promoting deeper transnational cooperation between universities.

Figure 1. Opening Ceremony. Speakers: Prof. Linda Doyle (TCD); Prof. Jordi Garcia (UB); Kate Morris (IUA).

Dr. Kate Morris (Head of Campus Engage, Irish Universities Association) closes the session with a presentation entitled 'Addressing societal challenges through engaged Research & Innovation'. First, Dr. Morris presents the IUA and its mission, as well as the Irish R&I landscape. Then, reflects on the global challenges the society currently faces (e.g. housing, climate crisis, health, energy, etc.), and points out that Engaged Research & Innovation can help tackle these challenges. The concept of Engaged R&I comprises: 1) bringing beneficiaries into the research and innovation process; 2) a collective transdisciplinary approach; 3) measure societal impact next to industry engagement. An engaged multidisciplinary approach is more effective in solving these problems, as people are on board, it saves time and money, and accelerates impact.

There is political momentum to get these changes embedded within the ERA, which also can be noticed in the R&I funding requirements, both at a European and national levels. Regarding Ireland's R&I ecosystem, it is a highly connected network, which contributes to make it very competitive. A new national strategy is under implementation in the country, as well, in which the public has involved in defining the major societal challenges. Hence, research is acting as a gateway between society and evidence informed policy making. However, we are far from delivering on this, so Dr. Morris takes the opportunity to call for action: 1) to change attitudes from top down, in order the change the culture; 2) change infrastructures and roles in universities; 3) build capacity (train staff to have the skills to achieve these changes).

3.2 Plenary Session. ERA's Policy Agenda 2022-2024 and R&I Cooperation Between European Universities⁸

The introductory plenary session serves to frame the meeting's general topic: The ERA's Policy Agenda 2022-2024 and the cooperation on R&I among the European Universities. The development to date of the R&I cooperative support structures of the European Universities have both provided valuable insights into, as well as being influenced by, the development of many aspects of the ERA Policy Agenda. The ambition of the European Universities is to be innovative live labs for the agenda, piloting actions, pushing boundaries and promoting positive change for Europe and beyond. Through this session, information on the implementation of the policy agenda 2022-2024 is provided, with a particular focus on action 13 and action 17 as well as asking what happens after 2024.

Plenary Session: ERA's Policy Agenda 2022-2024 and R&I Cooperation Between European universities

Chair: MERITXELL CHAVES. Secretary General, CHARM-EU.

Speakers:

- LIDIA BORRELL. Secretary General, Science Europe.

⁸ Session recording available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ka8oO7n4Nck>. See Annex II for the participants' presentations.

- GARETH O'NEILL. Principal Consultant on Open Science, Technopolis Group.
- EMMANUELLE GARDAN. Director of Coimbra Group.
- STEPHANE BERGHMANS. Director of Research & Innovation, European University Association.

Rapporteur: MÁRIA SZULOVSKY. Communications Coordinator, Eötvös Loránd University.

The plenary session, entitled 'ERA's Policy Agenda 2022-2024 and R&I Cooperation Between European Universities', is chaired by **Meritxell Chaves** (Secretary General, CHARM-EU Alliance). She highlights the contribution of European University Alliances as innovative live labs trying to test transformative activities and the effects of the ERA policy agenda on their work. Referring to the cluster sessions, she also highlights one of the general aims of the event as a mapping of experiences of the 15 Alliances participating in the Forum. She then presents the goal of the session and introduces the speakers.

Dr. Adrian Braem (Senior Policy Officer, Science Europe) presents the work of Science Europe by summarizing its core values and mission to define a long-term perspective for European research and to work towards best practice approaches. Regarding Science Europe's contribution to the ERA policy agenda, he emphasizes that research funding and performing organizations should be at the table when discussing the implementation of the ERA. He highlights the main priorities of Science Europe:

- Contributing to research development and influencing research culture.
- Strengthen science's role in tackling societal challenges.
- Supporting members to play a role and build strong ecosystems in their national research systems.

Dr. Braem emphasizes that Science Europe is committed to work on several of the ERA Policy Actions (such as Open Science, research assessment and careers, EDI, green transition and research infrastructure). In connection with research assessment, he highlights the association's contribution to CoARA, as Science Europe was part of the drafting committee and is now involved of the steering board. He emphasizes that they try to ensure that CoARA is as collaborative and bottom-up as possible.

Regarding the development of the new policy agenda, Dr. Braem states that Science Europe is currently developing its strategic vision on ERA and is reflecting on the actions to focus on based on the successes and challenges of the first year. Among the successes and as a result of the growing involvement of stakeholders, he highlights the improving governance and the impetus ERA has gained with the better involvement of Member States. He also emphasizes the good progression of the sub-group on Global Action. On the other side, he considers the uneven progress of the different ERA Action among the challenges together with the insufficient exploitation of interconnections

between them. Science Europe considers that some of the key issues such as ethics and integrity or the research element of green transition should receive more attention.

The discussions have already started on the development of the new ERA Policy Agenda for 2025-27, and Dr. Braem considers that the mid-term review of the ERA Actions provides an opportunity to improve and bring them closer to the bottom-up research priorities of universities, researchers and funders. Defining the new policy agenda also allows a reflection on the role of the ERA Forum and its stakeholders.

Regarding the question of how the ERA Forum can be improved, Science Europe would like to see more focus on overseeing the implementation of the Actions and ensuring the proper exploitation of synergies. Finally, in terms of the potential improvement of the ERA Policy Agenda for 2025-27, Science Europe would prefer a shorter list of priorities and a more holistic approach on finding solutions to common European issues.

Key Points:

- RPOs and RFOs should be at the table when discussing the implementation of the ERA.
- Science Europe is an important contributor to CoARA that tries to ensure that it is as collaborative and bottom-up as possible.
- Science Europe considers that synergies between the ERA Actions should be better exploited and key issues like ethics and integrity should be incorporated in the Agenda.
- The mid-term review of the ERA Actions provides an opportunity to improve and bring them closer to the bottom-up research priorities of universities.
- Science Europe would prefer a shorter list of priorities that affect the whole research ecosystem and a more holistic approach on finding solutions to common European issues.

Gareth O'Neill (Principal Consultant on Open Science, Technopolis Group) focuses on the ERA Policy Agenda and its connections to University Alliances and the transformational modules. He briefly summarizes the 20 Actions of the current policy agenda considering that Action 13 on Empowering higher education institutions and Action 17 on Strategic capacity of public RPOs are the most relevant Actions for Alliances in general. Concerning TORCH and the CHARM-EU Alliance, he also emphasizes Action 1 on Open sharing of knowledge, Action 3 on the Reform of Research Assessment and Action 4 on Strengthening research careers as important areas.

O'Neill then summarizes the history and the objective of University Alliances and presents the “two sides” of cooperation within them: the educational focus (connected to the Erasmus+ pilot support) and the research and innovation focus (connected to the Horizon 2020 support). Within their R&I dimensions, Alliances are working on the implementation of transformational modules now called Areas of Institutional Change based on their specific choice of strategic focus.

O'Neill presents the seven areas/transformational modules:

1. Regarding the area on Developing a common R&I agenda and action plan the focus is on the commonalities within a particular alliance in terms of strategic objectives. This includes the identification of challenges and convergence, the preparation of action plans, the identification of resources and the scaling of excellence.
2. Sharing resources & infrastructures such as human resources or digital infrastructures is a complex area focusing on bringing together different systems and working out how to achieve interoperability and manage access.
3. The area of Strengthening human capital focuses on supporting researchers and staff by building common framework conditions, finding a balance in the assessment of academics, dealing with brain drain, pooling knowledge and promoting skills and competences.
4. Reinforcing cooperation with non-academic sector is a broad area focusing on collaboration with both the public and the private sectors but with a particular focus on engaging industries and businesses. This can include the development of an innovation strategy, strengthening capacities, promoting an entrepreneurial mindset and cooperation as well as developing an innovation pipeline.
5. Very relevant for TORCH is the area on Mainstreaming Open Science practices such as Open Access and research data managements, promoting Open Science skills, and providing incentives and rewards to encourage Open Science practices by revising assessment systems.
6. The area on Engaging citizens & society contains options to focus on science communication and science's role in society, citizen science, knowledge creating teams with a team-focused mindset rather than individual research, the outreach to schools and connection with the Sustainable Development Goals.
7. The area of Exploring joint structures was added later and focuses on the setup of common technical activities and infrastructure facilitating collaboration within an Alliance with the aim of finding solutions together on common obstacles and sharing best practices.

O'Neill concludes by highlighting the report on the Progress of Pilot 1 University Alliance Projects under the 2020 SwafS support call to be published in March/April 2023. The report is focusing on the challenges, progress and good practices of the Pilot 1 Alliances. He highlights that while some of them face specific challenges (because of their specific disciplinary focus) there are several common challenges with various solutions put forward. He considers that there is a huge progress across alliances in general (sometimes on specific transformational modules, sometimes across them). Key point: While some alliances face specific challenges, they have several common challenges. The solutions put forward by Alliances to overcome these challenges are not always the same.

Emmanuelle Gardan (Director of the Coimbra Group) starts by introducing the Coimbra Group as a significant stakeholder and highlights that CG Members are officially involved in several European University Alliances including CHARM-EU. Coimbra is also an associated partner of CHARM-EU and its TORCH project.

Regarding the engagement with the ERA policy agenda, she highlights that Coimbra Group's strategic priorities for 2022-23 include actively engaging in the implementation of the European Research Area, more specifically in terms of Actions 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 11, 13 and 14. This follows CG's active involvement in shaping the policy framework behind the Actions which includes:

- Active engagement with the EU institutions in shaping the Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe.
- Intense advocacy for promoting stakeholder representation in the new ERA governance (specifically from the university sector).
- Active engagement with the EU institutions in shaping the ERA Policy Agenda for 2022-2024 and soon for the next period.

Regarding Coimbra Group's involvement in the implementation phase, the association consulted its members on the 20 ERA actions to identify collective priorities and those actions where they can bring added value. This resulted in formal commitment to implement the following eight Actions:

- Action 3. Reform of research assessment.
- Action 4. Attractive & sustainable research careers, balanced talent circulation & international, transdisciplinary & intersectoral mobility across the ERA.
- Action 5. Promote gender equality & foster inclusiveness.
- Action 6. Protecting academic freedom in Europe.
- Action 8. Sustainability, accessibility and resilience of research infrastructures.
- Action 11. An ERA for Green Transformation.
- Action 13. Empowering HEIs to develop in line with the ERA/EEA.
- Action 14. Bring science closer to citizens.

In connection with the most relevant Actions for the Alliances, Director Gardan emphasizes that key thoughts from the Council Conclusion on the European Universities are closely connected to many ERA policy objectives. According to her, this means that all ERA Actions are potentially relevant for the alliances. She highlights two Actions where CG have taken a more proactive role: 4 and 13.

Regarding Action 4 on Strengthening Research Careers, she presents three action strands: 1) the development of a comprehensive European Framework for Research Careers, 2) the exchange of

best practices on skills and mutual learning, and 3) support measures to improve the attractiveness of research careers. This Action received huge support via the formal commitment of 26 Member states, 3 Associated Countries and 12 stakeholder organizations. As a sponsor of the Action, Coimbra Group is ensuring shared responsibility, brings in relevant initiatives, pilots initiatives and supports the implementation of the Action.

Regarding Action 13 on Empowering higher education institutions the two main objectives are the strengthening of the European dimension in R&I and the improvement of the excellence and global competitiveness of European HEIs. CG is involved in the subgroup as co-chair from the stakeholder side. The subgroup has recently adopted the Terms of Reference and discussed the needs of Member States and stakeholders. Within this Action, they will work on facilitating the exchange and sharing of practices, supporting coordination between countries and departments, analyzing the results of studies and providing recommendations on support mechanisms. Finally, she identifies some of the challenges:

- A diversity in the scope and stakeholders of the ERA Policy Actions as well as their state of advancement.
- Silo-approaches, duplications and a plethora of EU initiatives targeting universities.
- Challenges of public communication & outreach, the risk of “Brussels-bubble jargon”.
- Funding issues – no political commitment on defining a percentage of the GDP on R&I from Member States.

Key points:

- Key aspects of the Council Conclusion on the European Universities are closely connected to ERA policy objectives: all ERA Actions are potentially relevant for the alliances.
- Synergies between the different Policy Actions should be better explored and ensured.
- ERA must create tangible impact for final users (researchers & research institutions, in particular universities).
- Funding both on the European and Member States’ level is key for the effective implementation of ERA Actions.

The session is closed by **Dr. Stephane Berghmans** (Director of Research & Innovation, European University Association), who presents EUA’s perspective on the New European Research Area. He starts with describing the work of the association as providing services and a forum for exchange of practices for their membership while also representing the voice of European universities.

Regarding EUA’s contribution to ERA, he mentions that the association was always very active on ERA. He highlights the establishment of the ERA Forum for Transition without the involvement of other stakeholders than Member States, Associated Countries and the Commission and EUA’s

subsequent work on lobbying to ensure the involvement of Stakeholders in the governance of the ERA. This resulted in the 2021 Council Conclusion and the representative involvement of Stakeholders at the ERA Forum. He highlights that one of the seven types of stakeholders identified are universities and higher education institutions.

In terms of the work carried out during 2022, he talks about the intensive collaboration with regular ERA Forum Meetings, and ERA University Sector Group meetings with participants sharing information and coordinating their input to provide a common message. He also highlights EUA's active involvement in the ERA Subgroup on Action 9 – Global Approach. Overall, EUA contributed to the sectorial coordination and representation of what Dr. Berghmans considers the most active stakeholder group with specific commitments to ERA Actions from the participating organizations. They are also ready to get involved in the implementation of those Actions.

EUA (and stakeholders in general) are very positive on the overall process (some consider it the “Bologna of research”) but they are awaiting the concrete outcomes. In terms of challenges, he does not see yet the financial commitment of Member States either. (This also reflects in the only Action not reaching the threshold: Action 20 R&I investment and reform.) Another challenge he sees is the disconnection between ERA and the EAA, an issue particularly important for universities and alliances. Regarding their commitment, EUA has committed to all 20 Actions but with 11 considered as high priority. He also showcases how the 11 university associations collaborate and share the coordination of the specific Actions between themselves. In terms of the next policy agenda, he emphasizes that stakeholders will be able to take part in the co-creation process and present their suggestions. He considers that the new framework is also an opportunity to create links between the ERA framework and the EEA.

He considers that alliances could be involved in Action 13 (Reform of research Assessment), Action 17 (Strategic capacity of public RPOs), Action 4 (Strengthen research careers) and Action 3 (Reform of research assessment). Besides, he recommends for consideration Action 6 (Protecting academic freedom), Action 5 (Gender equality and inclusiveness), Action 7 (Better knowledge valorization) and Action 16 (EU-wide access to excellence) depending on the focus of the alliance.

Key points:

- No point trying to establish a European Research Area without those who will be implementing and who are actively involved in it.
- EUA are very positive on the overall process but they are awaiting the concrete outcomes.
- The lack of financial commitment from Member States and the disconnection between ERA and EEA are challenges.

Figure 2. Plenary Session. ERA's Policy Agenda 2022-2024 and R&I cooperation between European universities. Speakers: Meritxell Chaves (CHARM-EU), Adrien Braem (Science Europe), Gareth O'Neill (Technopolis Group), Emmanuelle Gardan (Coimbra Group), Stephane Berghmans (EUA).

Once completed all presentations, participants are invited to respond the following question from the audience: How would you summarize post ERA and its impact on society in terms of beneficiaries of research and societal partners like industry, community, government and citizens?

Dr. Berghmans answers that he does not know exactly as the process is at its starting and not yet there where beneficiaries can feel its impact. There are different kinds of actions currently taken such as the Commission launching a CSA to bring stakeholders to the national level starting in 2024. The start of the implementation process will probably also raise the issue that Member States are the ones that have to make sure that national stakeholders are consulted. He mentioned the good example of Norway as a very active country in this regard.

Gareth O'Neill slightly disagrees with Dr. Berghmans as some Actions are progressing relatively well, such as Actions 1, 4 and 3. Regarding Action 1 on Open Science for example, he was working on a monitoring framework with EOSC Future for national contributions to EOSC and Open Science. This has already an effect on the MS level in terms of tracking investments and policies and pushing them towards their collective path. This can trickle down over the years to institutions and ultimately to researchers. Concrete projects have started in connection with Actions 3 and 4 as well.

Emmanuelle Gardan complements on what Dr. Berghmans said on the involvement of national level stakeholders: countries like Austria, Germany and Norway are developing national ERA action plans. They are hoping for more Member States to start developing these actions, which can potentially result in legislative changes and new funding instruments. It's crucial that stakeholders are sitting at the table regarding implementation as well.

Final question from the audience: Last week the European Commission and the government of UK announced the Windsor framework. Will this change anything?

Stephane Berghmans answers that as soon as it is ratified, it means that the association is wide open. Having UK in the ERA is fundamentally beneficial not just for the UK but for the Union as well. Gareth O'Neill adds that, in principle, the University Alliances are open as well and already accepting new members.

3.3 Panel Session. The European Perspective on the Reform of Research Assessment⁹

A reform of the research assessment system for research, researchers and institutions to improve their quality, performance and impact was called out as a priority area for joint action in the ERA policy agenda 2022-2024 which was approved as part of the Council conclusions on the future government of the ERA on 26th November 2021. This session presents the current European

⁹ Session recording available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ka8oO7n4Nck>. See Annex II for the participants' presentations.

initiative towards reforming research assessment and fosters reflection on its relevance and impact on both national authorities/agencies and HEIs.

Panel Session: The European Perspective on the Reform of Research Assessment

Chair: REKO LEINO. Vice Rector for Research, Åbo Akademi University.

Speakers:

- JEAN-EMMANUEL FAURE. Team leader of Research assessment, DG Research & Innovation, European Commission. *Reforming research assessment*
- STEPHANE BERGHMANS. Director of Research & Innovation, European University Association. *A Reform of Research Assessment. The Agreement & CoARA Coalition - A University Perspective*
- TERESA MAGUIRE. Director of Research Strategy & Funding, Irish Health Research Board. *Reform of Research Assessment - Research funder perspective*
- PAUL BOSELIE. Chair Recognition & Rewards in Open Science, Utrecht University. *The European perspective on the reform of research assessment*

Rapporteur: PIA LE GRAND. Head of International Cooperation, Åbo Akademi University.

Prof. Reko Leino (Vice Rector for Research, Åbo Akademi University) introduces the panel session on the ‘European Perspective on the Reform of Research Assessment’, briefly reviewing the recent developments in the European higher education framework with regards to researchers and institutions evaluation systems.

Dr. Jean-Emmanuel Faure (Team leader of Research assessment, DG Research & Innovation, European Commission) opens the session with a presentation entitled ‘Reforming Research Assessment’. The speaker reflects on the need to reform research assessment as a priority area of the new European Research Area (ERA). The overarching aim is to maximize the quality and impact of research and support the attractiveness of research environments. CoARA (the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment) has 487 signatories from 41 countries as of 3rd March 2023. Based on 10 commitments, the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment sets a shared direction for changes in assessment practices for research, researchers and research performing organizations. It includes the principles, commitments and timeframe for reforms and lays out the principles for a Coalition of organizations willing to work together in implementing the changes.

The European Commission supports CoARA by:

- Being an active member of the Coalition, mainly in its quality as a research funder, and participating in relevant working groups and activities.
- Providing operational support to the CoARA Secretariat, ad interim.
- Providing financial support to the CoARA activities through Horizon Europe.

- Providing policy support in liaising the Coalition with Member States and Associated Countries in the framework of the ERA Forum.
- Fostering global alignment and cooperation with other regions worldwide & synergies with other European initiatives.

Figure 3. Panel Session. The European perspective on the reform of research assessment. Speakers: Reko Leino (ÅAU), Jean-Emmanuel Faure (DG R&I, EC), Stephane Berghmans (EUA), Teresa Maguire (HRB), Paul Boselie (UU).

Dr. Stephane Berghmans (Director of Research & Innovation, European University Association) proceeds to present the CoAra Coalition and agreement in detail. Universities are needed to bring change and should be actively involved in the reform of research assessment. Many universities in some countries have signed the CoARA, but many countries are still missing. The CoARA agreement

is not legally binding (it is more of a morally binding signature towards peer organizations), but it is an agreement with clear commitments. The member organizations keep full autonomy of the steps towards the implementation of the Agreement and the pace of the reform at their organization. There is no membership fee, but resources should be allocated as is needed for each organization.

The European University Association's role is:

- Supporting EUA members through webinars, seminars, guidelines, etc.
- Platform for exchange and collaboration.
- Engagement in CoARA: e.g. manage/lead a Working Group linked to the core activities of universities and ensure complementarities/synergies between CoARA activities and EUA's activities.
- Policy Advocacy in the new ERA.
- Global outreach through sister organisations.
- Supporting the Steering Board.

The third speaker, **Dr. Teresa Maguire** (Director of Research Strategy & Funding, Irish Health Research Board) presents the research funder perspective on research assessment. The HRB is a health research funder. Its mission is to support research that improves people's health, promotes evidence-informed care and creates solutions to societal challenges. The economic constraints on public funding have multiplied, leading to increased political demands to measure impact and demonstrate the value of investing in research. There is a huge need for reform of research assessment. Assessment is one of the most significant processes in the global research arena, encompassing everything from policy goals and programme budgets to project selection, awards and career development.

To conclude, **Prof. Paul Boselie** (Chair of Recognition & Rewards in Open Science, Utrecht University) outlines the state of the art in the Netherlands regarding research assessment, as well as UU's strategy. In the Netherlands the reform of research assessment started with a position paper published in 2019 with the title 'Room for everyone's talent'¹⁰. During 2021-2027 the Strategy Evaluation Protocol (SEP) is being implemented.

At Utrecht University, there is the Open Science programme including the subtheme of Recognition & Rewards. It consists of: Public engagement; Recognition & Rewards; Open Access; FAIR Data & software; and Open education. Some of the goals are:

- Co-operation instead of competition.

¹⁰ Room for everyone's talent: Towards a new balance in the recognition and rewards of academics. Available at https://www.nwo.nl/sites/nwo/files/media-files/2019-Recognition-Rewards-Position-Paper_EN.pdf

- New evaluation criteria.
- Impact.
- Teamwork.
- Leadership.
- Distinction between academic and support staff reduced.

3.4 TORCH Clusters. Progress on joint R&I Strategies in European University Alliances

These sessions, carried out via MS Teams for online participants, focus on the European Universities' advances and specific initiatives concerning a number of R&I topics, presenting the main progress of the TORCH Project and the fellow Alliances' SwafS projects. It is divided into three parallel thematic clusters. Each group is led by a chair (to guide the session and discussion, providing questions and moderating the audience's participation), and has a rapporteur (which takes notes, describing the content of the session, including results and challenges coming out of the debate).

· Cluster 1: New approaches for Diverse Academic Careers¹¹

This session goes over specific examples and/or pilots and action plans towards promoting Open Science and intersectional initiatives regarding equal opportunities, non-discrimination and inclusivity within the new research assessment frameworks.

Each speaker has a 10 minutes presentation followed by the possibility of discussing and exchanging ideas with all participants.

Cluster 1: New Approaches for Diverse Academic Careers

Chair: CATHERINE COMISKEY. Professor in Healthcare Modelling and Statistics & Academic Director of CHARM-EU, School of Nursing and Midwifery, Trinity College Dublin.

Speakers:

- NINA SHIEL, Trinity College Dublin (CHARM-EU/TORCH). *CHARM-EU Inclusivity Plan: An Intersectional Approach to Attain Equality in R&I.*
- PIA VOIGT, Universität Leipzig. DANIELA PICHLER, Universität Graz (ARQUS R&I). *How to foster Open Science - Results from an ARQUS-wide Survey among Researchers and derived Recommendations.*
- KATARZYNA MOLEK-KOZAKOWSKA, University of Opole (FIT FORTHEM). *Modelling Citizen Science for Education (MSCEDU): Insights from introducing Citizen Science to schools by FORTHEM Alliance universities.*

¹¹ See Annex II for the participants' presentations.

- MARIA PIETILÄ, JOUNI KEKÄLE, University of Eastern Finland (YUFERING). *YUFERING portfolio in researcher assessment.*
- MIHNEA DOBRE, University of Bucharest. RAFAELLA LENOIR, Autonomous University of Madrid. FABIEN BORGET, Aix-Marseille Université (RIS4CIVIS). *Exploring a Path to Research Assessment Reform in a European University Alliance: RIS4CIVIS.*
- ANDREAS RAGGAUTZ, Universität Graz (ARQUS R&I). *Pilot: activity framework and research assessment reform.*
- THRASYVOULOS TSIATSOS, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (EPICUR). *The deployment of a model researcher assessment framework (EPIQAssess) in the EPICommunity platform.*
- MARJANNEKE VIJGE, Utrecht University (CHARM-EU / TORCH). *CHARM-EU: Towards Reforming Research Assessment.*

Rapporteur: JENNY KIRKWOOD. Administrative Officer CHARM-EU, Trinity College Dublin.

The session, chaired by **Prof. Catherine Comiskey** (Academic Director of CHARM-EU, Trinity College Dublin), comprises presentations on initiatives to promote diverse academic careers from six Alliances (CHARM-EU, ARQUS, FORTHEM, YUFE, CIVIS, and EPICUR), in the framework of their SwafS projects. Prof. Comiskey introduces the topic and welcomes all participants.

Dr. Nina Shiel (Trinity College Dublin, CHARM-EU/TORCH) opens the cluster session with a presentation entitled 'Towards a CHARM-EU Inclusivity Plan: An Intersectional Approach to Attain Equality in R&I'. The main topics presented are:

- Equality is a cross-cutting principle of TORCH & CHARM.
- TORCH has recommendations on the gap analysis.
- Dr. Shiel outlined the steps towards a CHARM-EU inclusivity plan.
- She also detailed the benefits of an Alliance level inclusivity plan.
- The Commission will look at all proposals for their gender balance policy when deciding which to fund.
- Dr. Shiel is not aware of any other alliance working on this, but would welcome other Alliances to contact her about this matter.

Regarding data gathering, TORCH is looking to find out whether and to what extent each university is gathering diversity data at all. There will certainly be significant differences.

Dr. Pia Voigt (Universität Leipzig) and **Dr. Daniela Pichler** (Universität Graz), on behalf of ARQUS Alliance, present 'How to Foster Open Science – Results from an ARQUS-wine Survey among Researchers and derived Recommendations'. Main topics discussed:

- Recommendations based on an Open Science Survey. Sent to all July/August last year.
- Develop training, support & share policies among ARQUS researchers.
- Introduce rewards & incentives.
- Provide resources, infrastructure & funding.
- Communicate research results.

Particular emphasis on Open Science not being recognized enough in career progression was made.

Dr. Katarzyna Molek-Kozakowska (University of Opole, FIT FORTHEM) presents 'Modelling Citizen Science for Education: Insights from introducing Citizen Science to schools by FORTHEM Alliance Universities'. Main topics:

- FORTHEM Alliance have labs that answer societal challenges.
- FIT FORTHEM brings citizen science to schools through the FORTHEM Alliance universities.
- Universities work with schools to task students with developing their own citizen science projects that are relevant to the local community, e. g. Ukrainian refugees, teenage relationship breakdown, mental health, sex education.
- Young people learn how to conduct research and surveys and collate data with the support of their teachers and the FORTHEM academics.
- Short questionnaire at end of each cycle to see how students felt about research in social science.
- Videos and promotional material made.

Dr. Molek-Kozakowska is asked how far this initiative has gone in co-creation of the citizen science project. Schools with profiles more in humanities and social sciences were chosen, who came up with the interesting ideas that the project could support.

The fourth presentation, by **Dr. Maria Pietilä** and **Dr. Jouni Kekäle** (University of Eastern Finland, YUFE), is entitled 'YUFERING Portfolio in Researcher Assessment'. Main topics:

- Calling for reform of research assessment. But important to build on good things that already exist.
- Flexible approach that allows recruiters to emphasize their own priorities.
- YUFE-wide piloting taking place in selection of post-doctoral researchers in 2023.
- Implications of the portfolio depend on the academic gatekeeper's use of the information.
- Reporting in Autumn 2023.

The speakers stress that countries/institutions involved are very different so need a flexible approach to allow for their priorities. It is very important that the portfolio is piloted.

Dr. Mihnea Dobre (University of Bucharest), **Dr. Raffaella Lenoir** (Autonomous University of Madrid) and **Dr. Fabien Borget** (Aix-Marseille University), CIVIS Alliance, present 'Exploring a Path to Research Assessment Reform in a European University Alliance: RIS4CIVIS'. Main topics:

- Promote collaborative inter-institutional research.
- Strengthen interactions between academics/civil society and private enterprise & cultural sectors.
- Develop innovative infrastructure/tools.
- Strengthen mobility of researchers.
- Promote collaboration between research support units.
- With a specific focus on strengthening human capital, mainstreaming Open Science and embedding citizens and society.

The sixth presentation, by **Dr. Andreas Raggautz** (Universität Graz, ARQUS), is entitled 'Activity Framework and Research Assessment Reform - University of Graz Pilot'. Main topics covered:

- Exploring a Path to Research Assessment Reform in a European University Alliance.
- Need transparency of achievements expected at respective career levels & research culture.
- Work on format for research units (innovation, scientific community, international visibility).
- Create strategy document for next ten years – bottom up, flexible approach.
- Case studies to finish mid-summer 2023.

Prof. Comiskey praises the sensible, broad approach, as it is practical and achievable. With regard to peer assessment, the presenter is asked about their recruitment procedure. Peers are suggested by the department, with rector and vice rector deciding (must declare no conflict of interest). Almost all peers are external.

Dr. Thrasylvoulos Tsiatsos (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, EPICUR) presents 'The Deployment of a Model Researcher Assessment Framework (EPIQAssess) in the EPICommunity platform'. Main topics:

- Aim to use digitalization & international collaboration as enablers in the delivery of research & innovation formats.
- Creating Platform EPICommunity following EC guidelines.

- EPICommunity is a solid platform implementing EPIQAssess.
- EPICommunity is open for every researcher and every Alliance.

The speaker is inquired on the number of users the platform has, and how successful have the promotion campaigns been. Part of the EPICommunity is using this resource, but an increase of use is needed, along with the deployment in more universities.

As for the final presentation in the cluster session, **Dr. Marjanneke Vijge** (Utrecht University, CHARM-EU/TORCH) introduces 'CHARM-EU: Towards Reforming Research Assessment'. Main topics:

- Focus on reforming research assessments for CHARM EU - towards Open Science.
- Looking at the career track of UU geoscience academic staff.
- Education and societal impact not sufficiently recognized, focus is still on research.
- But how do we measure public engagement? This is the challenge.
- Solutions possible through CHARM-EU, CHARM-8, and TORCH.

Figure 4. TORCH Cluster 1: New Approaches for Diverse Academic Careers.

· Cluster 2: Intensifying R&I Cooperation Between Universities¹²

The objective of the session is to share the Alliances' best practices and initiatives towards building collaborative frameworks for joint and shared R&I-related activities. It focuses on the creation of common science agendas and collective/pooled structures seeking long-term sustainable and effective cooperation.

Each speaker has a 10 minutes presentation followed by the possibility of discussing and exchanging ideas with all participants.

Cluster 2: Intensifying R&I Cooperation Between Universities

Chair: FERENC TAKÓ. Head of CHARM-EU Office, Eötvös Loránd University.

Speakers:

- NICOLE BIRKLE, Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz (FORTHEM / FIT-FORTHEM). *The FORTHEM Joint Research Services and Policy Office.*
- ISABEL SALGUEIRO, Polytechnic University of Madrid. DAVID SCHKADE, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität (EELISA InnoCORE). *EELISA InnoCORE and EELISA Unfolds: opening up our innovation ecosystems, building joint initiatives for innovators and entrepreneurs.*
- GWENDOLINE TRAISNEL, Université de Bretagne Occidentale (SEA-EU / ReSEArch-EU). *Building a common strategy in a multidisciplinary alliance: identifying and matching the research forces with societal challenges.*
- JOHN BARIMO, University College Cork. BANU LIMAN, Koç University. ROBERTO SAN SALVADOR, University of Deusto (UNIC). *Towards a strategy for 'engaged' research and a collaborative roadmap with cities and city stakeholders.*
- PÁDRAIG MURPHY, Dublin City University (ECIU SMART-ER). *Organising alliance institutions to pilot bottom-up challenge-based research.*
- CIRO FRANCO, Sapienza University of Rome (RIS4CIVIS). *Sharing of Research Infrastructures, for the benefit of CIVIS Alliance community.*
- MARTIN GALVIN, University College Cork. SARI HIRVONEN-KANTOLA, University of Oulu. SARA BJARSTORP, Malmö Universitet (UNIC). *Infrastructure for Research - UNIC Centre for City Futures.*
- ARNAUD FABRE, University of Montpellier (CHARM-EU / TORCH). *TORCH TTOs virtual network.*

Rapporteur: KIRSTEN HOLLAENDER. Project Manager, Utrecht University.

The cluster session on 'Intensifying R&I Cooperation Between Universities' is chaired by **Dr. Ferenc Takó** (Head of CHARM-EU Office, Eötvös Loránd University), and includes representatives from seven Alliances: FORTHEM, EELISA, SEA-EU, UNIC, ECIU, CIVIS, and CHARM-EU.

¹² See Annex II for the participants' presentations.

The first presentation, by **Dr. Nicole Birkle** (Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz, FORTHEM), is entitled 'The FORTHEM Joint Research Services and Policy Office'. Dr. Birkle presents the idea for a joint research support service and policy office as a central place to collect, connect, share as well as for strategy development. FORTHEM made connections in Brussels with regional representatives, plans for joint events and collected commitment letters. Besides, it is also meant to address the needs of new researchers. Next steps are to offer services, support transfer, offer trainings, join forces and support network building and write a book of good practices.

Isabel Salgueiro (Polytechnic University of Madrid) and **Dr. David Schkade** (Friedrich-Alexander-Universität), in representation of EELISA, present 'EELISA InnoCORE and EELISA Unfolds: opening up our innovation ecosystems, building joint initiatives for innovators and entrepreneurs'. This initiative expanded now from nine to ten partners. The EELISA Unfolds project is financed by EIT Digital and addresses courses, a repository, a hackathon, mentoring, and a demo-day event. The Innocore project supports the bundling of activities and organizes some, such as a prototype contest. It brings together good practices, e.g. contests, opening offers to EELISA partners, interlinkages offers, pilots for learning, startup contests in connection with mentoring. Challenges lie in the promotion of activities, the EU vs. National level and in the long-term perspective.

Dr. Gwendoline Traisnel (Université de Bretagne Occidentale, SEA-EU) presents the ReSEArch-EU project advances on 'Building a common strategy in a multidisciplinary alliance: identifying and matching the research forces with societal challenges'. The Alliance expanded from six to nine members. It wants to contribute to transparency on research strengths, matching and agenda setting. The approach is by a bibliometric analysis based on national and Web of Science Databases, Conference Papers and PhD Theses and also S3 (Smart Specialization Strategies). This resulted in a database of 58000 documents also including H2020 projects, as basis for a performance analysis and a science mapping. They extracted the keywords for the top 100 authors with help of the software Bibliometrix and VOS viewer. This is a combination of methods and now currently working on matching strengths and challenges.

Dr. John Barimo (University College Cork), **Banu Liman** (Koç University) and **Dr. Roberto San Salvador** (University of Deusto), representing UNIC, present 'Towards a strategy for 'engaged' research and a collaborative roadmap with cities and city stakeholders'. Focussed on post-industrial transition cities, the Alliance is forming tight bonds with city partners and has signed a MOU with them. Their core concept is engaged research. The MOU is titled: European Declaration on Engaged Research. UNIC are also working on a framework development and showcasing good practices. Also, a roadmap is being developed with the cities and a seed fund call was launched, currently the award recipients are being selected.

The fifth presentation, by **Dr. Pádraig Murphy** (Dublin City University, ECIU/SMART-ER), is entitled: 'Organizing alliance institutions to pilot bottom-up challenge-based research'. The Alliance has a Mexican partner as associated member. It is building a Virtual Research Institute for Smart European Regions. The core concept is challenge based research for SDG11 - Sustainable Cities and Communities, and work with testbeds and pilots. So far, the project has identified 4500 researchers

on this topic with areas such as transport, energy, circular economy, resilient communities, and Citizen Science. Seed funding is used as instrument next to cotutelles, networking, community-based research, and webinars on Citizen Science. The ECIU position paper addresses their teething problems plus the needs for the virtual institute (governance, etc.).

Dr. Ciro Franco (Sapienza University of Rome, CIVIS) shares a presentation on ‘Sharing of Research Infrastructures, for the benefit of CIVIS Alliance community’. CIVIS presents their R&I strategy and institutional transformation model within the RIS4CIVIS project. Currently working on a charter for research infrastructure access and use, with rules and guidelines. To achieve this, a soft approach is chosen. In addition, a database of infrastructures has been developed, with 172 on the list to date.

Dr. Martin Galvin (University College Cork), **Dr. Sari Hirvonen-Kantola** (University of Oulu) and **Dr. Sara Bjarstorp** (Malmö Universitet), members of UNIC, present ‘Infrastructure for Research - UNIC Centre for City Futures’, an initiative to be kick-off in September 2023.

To close the cluster session, **Arnaud Fabre** (University of Montpellier, CHARM-EU/TORCH) presents the ‘TORCH TTOs virtual network’. The speaker explains the background and aim of the Virtual TTOs network for CHARM. Next to local and national networks, the next step is a European network.

Given the time constraints, a brief discussion is held by the end of the session. The main question asked is what happens after the SwafS funding ends. How to maintain the momentum that has been created? For now, first generation Alliances are focused on preparing proposals for European competitive calls. In any case, the Alliances are pushing for a feasible pathway from 2027 onwards.

Figure 5. TORCH Cluster 2: Intensifying R&I Cooperation Between Universities.

· Cluster 3: Promoting Inter/Transdisciplinary Research Driven by Societal Challenges¹³

This session's goal is to present diverse joint approaches the Alliances are taking to foster transdisciplinary and challenge-driven research.

Each speaker has a 10 minutes presentation followed by the possibility of discussing and exchanging ideas with all participants.

Cluster 3: Promoting Inter/Transdisciplinary Research Driven by Societal Challenges

Chair: RAUL RAMOS. Vice Rector for Internationalization Policy, University of Barcelona.

Speakers:

- ALBERT DIAZ, VICENTE ROYUELA, University of Barcelona (CHARM-EU / TORCH). *TORCH Common Science Agenda: A Multidisciplinary Approach to Develop SDG-driven Research Challenges.*
- LUDOVIC THILLY, Université de Poitiers. (EC2U / RI4C2). *Inter-disciplinary research promoted by the EC2U Virtual Institutes.*
- DAITHÍ MAC SÍTHIGH, Institute of Art, Design + Technology (FilmEU). *Dynamic research clusters in film and media arts.*
- DAVID SITBON, Université Paris Cité (Circle U). *When Circle U. meets interdisciplinarity.*
- SÉBASTIEN HUBER, European University Institute (CIVICA). *Promoting interdisciplinary research centred around CIVICA's four thematic priorities.*
- AINE MOORE, University College Dublin (Una Europa). *Una Europa's vision towards interdisciplinary hubs for research.*
- NICOLE BIRKLE, Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz (FORTHEM / FIT-FORTHEM). *The New FORTHEM Research, Innovation and Transfer Mission – background and content.*

Rapporteur: VERONIKA PECIAROVA. Project Manager, University of Montpellier.

The session on 'Promoting Inter/Transdisciplinary Research Driven by Societal Challenges' is chaired by **Prof. Raul Ramos** (Vice Rector for Internationalization Policy, University of Barcelona), and hosts representatives from seven Alliances: CHARM-EU, EC2U, FilmEU, Circle U, CIVICA, Una Europa, and FORTHEM. Prof. Ramos welcomes all speakers and attendees, and introduces the topic, stressing the importance for the Alliances to take on joint transdisciplinary actions.

Prof. Albert Diaz and **Prof. Vicente Royuela** (University of Barcelona, CHARM-EU/TORCH) open the session, with a presentation entitled 'TORCH Common Science Agenda: A Multidisciplinary Approach to Develop SDG-driven Research Challenges'. The idea of this initiative is to create

¹³ See Annex II for the participants' presentations.

multidisciplinary teams composed by TORCH partners to conceive a number of Research Challenges, via a bottom-up three-step method:

- Step 1: Data collection on researchers expertise and interests (questionnaire submitted by each university).
- Step 2: Institutional analysis (results of the questionnaire).
- Step 3: Challenge formulation by teams of researchers after focus groups.

Six challenges are presented, focused on three SDGs: SDG3 (Good Health & Well-Being), SDG10 (Reduced Inequalities), SDG13 (Climate Action). The next steps are to support these research groups for the proposals to be further developed and submitted to EU funding calls. Partners benefit from their institutional support: Administrative; financial, proposal preparation, etc.

The speakers also present an interactive user-friendly tool to support the TORCH challenges that visualizes collaborative researcher's networks among TORCH universities, and identifies key research topics.

The second presentation, by **Prof. Ludovic Thilly** (Université de Poitiers, EC2U), is 'Inter-disciplinary research promoted by the EC2U Virtual Institutes'. Prof. Thilly presents the Alliance and the European campus of City-Universities. He explains that research is a major component of their Alliance, each university having its own research profile. A common digital platform for teaching was used to identify research needs of the universities. They cross cut their institutional research domains and four of them were sorted out: Social Sciences and Humanities, Health and Biology, Energy and Environmental Sciences, and Physics and Engineering. In addition, some SDGs have been identified: SDG3 (Good Health and Well-Being), SDG4 (Quality Education), SDG11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities). An Erasmus project was used to create 3 virtual institutes, being the first outcome from the educational component the creation of three joint master programmes, opened in September 2022. Other ongoing initiatives:

- Summer schools and joint PhD trainings.
- Mobility programmes for researchers.
- Joint PhD thesis.
- Joint research programmes: mobility possibilities.

Dr. Daithí Mac Síthigh (Institute of Art, Design + Technology, FilmEU) presents 'Dynamic research clusters in film and media arts'. First, presents the FilmEU Alliance for film and media arts: four institutions to collaborate around the common objective of jointly promoting high-level education, innovation and research in multidisciplinary field of film and media arts. The FilmEU RIT project designs strategies and action plans around research and innovation in film and media arts. Several research clusters were developed:

- Cultural heritage (Pilot 1): European archive of short animation (lack of reliable data in this field).
- Stereoscopic visions (Pilot 2): decolonizing the panorama of Congo: a virtual heritage artistic research.
- Volumetric cinema & future visions (Pilot 3): expanded memories; artistic experiments into hybrid analogue – digital film production.
- Volumetric cinema & future visions: machine acts (Pilot 4): collaborative screenplay writing with GTP-3. Teaching methods combined with computer methods.
- Experimental sound & vision (Pilot 5): artistic research and cognitive film studies; towards a transdisciplinary understanding of cinema.

The key messages of this presentation are: 1) Testing the collaboration of the systems is really interesting; 2) bringing new partners to the alliance is important.

David Sitbon (Université Paris Cité, Circle U) presents 'When Circle U. meets interdisciplinarity'. Circle U is an Alliance formed by nine partner universities, with two ongoing projects: Erasmus+ and ERIA project (H2020). Examples of Circle U interdisciplinary activities:

- ERIA project: To strengthen R&I collaborations in Circle U. Fostering interdisciplinarity to co-construct solutions with other sectors, involving citizens and society in research and innovation, strengthening human capital, structured collaboration at the European level, among pilot Alliances.
- INTER Circle U. Prize (ICUP): To showcase the best examples of inter- and transdisciplinary research at Circle U.
- SANDPITS (or sandboxes): Innovative workshop facilitated by a specialist in interdisciplinary research to bring together the researchers from the alliance and to kick start new projects.
- ITRN event: Supporting interdisciplinary projects involving at least three universities, four ITRN projects selected in 2022.
- An academic directory tool: to connect the researchers based on common research interests and to allow smooth inter-university collaboration.

Future initiatives:

- Interdisciplinarity is at the core of the Alliance to promote research collaboration.
- Several activities to occur every year and link to other interdisciplinary events.
- R&I integrated into the next roll-out phase.

Dr. Sébastien Huber (European University Institute, CIVICA) shares a presentation on 'Promoting interdisciplinary research centered around CIVICA's four thematic priorities'. CIVICA is composed of ten universities, all with the aim to influence the policy making, focused on 4 main areas:

- Societies in transition and crises of Earth.
- Challenges to democracy in the 21st century.
- Europe Revisited.
- Data driven technologies for societal challenges.

One specific thing in CIVICA is the connection to EU as political subject. Its research dimension identified several milestones already, with a focus on Open Science. First call for research proposals has been launched: 11 winning projects out of 27 applications. Second call for research projects: 28 research projects are to be funded by CIVICA. Synergies within and outside CIVICA are centered in:

- R&I management.
- Doctoral training.
- Doctoral community.
- Roadmap for interdisciplinary laboratory.
- Partnerships with other alliances & beyond.

The main barriers found so far are related to the lack of time to address all the challenges and lack of financing.

The sixth presentation, by **Dr. Nicole Birkle** (Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz, FORTHEM), is entitled 'The New FORTHEM Research, Innovation and Transfer Mission – background and content'. FORTHEM is formed by nine universities (two new partners joined in 2022). The R&I project, FIT FORTHEM, focuses on some thematic areas (FORTHEM labs):

- Diversity and migration.
- Multilingualism in school and higher education.
- Food science.
- Digital transformation.
- Climate and resources.
- Experiencing Europe.
- Resilience, Life Quality and Demographic Challenge.

The main lessons learned during the process are:

- Workshops, boot-camps, and surveys identified Early-Stage Researchers as the most vulnerable group FORTHEM needs to address.
- Agendas, policies, action plans, and recommendations will only show their impact after the lifetime of the project.
- Strongholds are identified but need more incentives to be matched, especially in case of experienced researchers.
- Common understanding of co-creation needs to be further developed.
- Open Science as a core topic to be further developed and trained.
- Office needs to be implemented permanently to guarantee results are exploited.

Setting-up the FORTHEM Research, Innovation and Transfer Mission is a direct result of the FIT FORTHEM project and will also drive the alliance forward in the area of research and innovation. Results from FIT FORTHEM are not lost after the end of the project, but are retained and further evaluated and exploited. However, there is still a need for better incentives for researchers to participate in the activities of the alliance, implementing structural measures alone is not in the core of their intrinsic motivation. It needs attractive funding programmes for joint research, even in small formats, CSA and funding schemes especially in the WIDERA program are most appreciated, but it needs more attractive funding lines and better synergies between existing programmes.

Dr. Aine Moore (University College Dublin, Una Europa) presents 'Una Europa's vision towards interdisciplinary hubs for research', which lays out Una Europa's 2030 Strategy, with three pillars:

- Powering the research for the future.
- Pioneering the education of the future.
- Shaping the society of the future.

Enhancing collaboration in research and innovation:

- Promotion of high-quality and long-term research collaborations to drive the excellence dimension of European research and contribute to the objectives of the ERA.
- Advancing knowledge circulation and connecting complementary research strengths in key interdisciplinary research areas to tackle global and societal challenges.
- Creation of a trans-sectoral Una Europa ecosystem for research & innovation through collaborations with other sectors and society.

- Focus on added-value, going beyond what a single institution can achieve alone and pooling resources to prepare the future leading researchers of Europe and the globe.

Una Europa focus areas are: Cultural heritage; Data sciences & AI; Europe and the World; One Health; Sustainability; Future materials. The Alliance is now establishing a roadmap for R&I, which sets out their path towards a common research and innovation ecosystem that supports the entire spectrum of multi-, inter-, and transdisciplinary research.

Figure 6. TORCH Cluster 3: Promoting Inter/Transdisciplinary Research Driven by Societal Challenges.

3.5 Panel Session. University with and for Society: Promoting Citizen Science within Open Science¹⁴

In this panel session, the CHARM-EU new partners (Åbo Akademi University, Julius-Maximilian-Universität Würzburg, Hochschule Ruhr West), along with the University of Barcelona, showcase hands-on experiences from Citizen Science initiatives within universities (research processes that involve citizens, local communities, non-academic stakeholders and the wider society, with the focus on active and participatory research). This session aims to put forward some useful take-home

¹⁴ Session recording available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sIECPWRU40k>. See Annex II for the participants' presentations.

messages for HEIs about contributing to the reinforcement of societal trust in science, shaping public opinion and increasing citizens' scientific knowledge and awareness.

Panel Session: University with and for Society: Promoting Citizen Science within Open Science

Chair: GEMMA MARFANY. Rector's Delegate for Scientific Dissemination, University of Barcelona.

Speakers:

- MARKO JOAS, Vice Rector for Collaboration. MATS LINDFELT, Director of Research Services, Åbo Akademi University. *Piloting Citizen Science Support through Small Scale Projects – The Case of Åbo Akademi University.*
- LUKAS WORSCHKECH. Head of Division Research and Technology Transfer, Julius-Maximilian-Universität Würzburg. *Citizen science as part of knowledge transfer actions with SMEs.*
- ELLEN ROEMER. Hochschule Ruhr West. *Opportunities for Citizen Science Projects - Experiences at Ruhr West University of Applied Science.*
- JOSEP PERELLÓ. Director of OpenSystemsUB, University of Barcelona. *Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action: The experience of the CoAct EU project.*

Rapporteur: JAIME LLORCA. TORCH Project Manager, University of Barcelona.

Prof. Gemma Marfany (Rector's Delegate for Scientific Dissemination, University of Barcelona) introduces the topic, reflecting on the importance of Open Science, as society must have access, free access, to innovation and research outputs generated by universities. Citizen Science (CS) goes even further than Open Science, because it is not only about producing and sharing knowledge, but also about empowering society, making citizens an active part of the scientific process, and involving them in the co-creation of knowledge. It is not an easy task, which encompasses diverse angles, and hence the relevance of this session, focused on how different universities are approaching specific pilot programs and initiatives regarding CS.

Prof. Marko Joas and **Dr. Mats Lindfelt** (Åbo Akademi University) open the session with a presentation entitled 'Piloting Citizen Science Support through Small Scale Projects – The Case of Åbo Akademi University'. Prof. Joas starts by introducing their university, and the institutional approach on citizen support systems for CS. ÅAU is committed to the Declaration of Open Science and Research 2020-2025 and associated national policies¹⁵. The university introduced a CS pilot, with purpose to develop and test forms of support for CS by: creating information materials for researchers; planning the process; supporting at least three research projects with CS elements.

There are different traditions to work with and for society in different disciplines, but it is a two-way collaboration with society, and a key element and goal for universities. The definition elements (which vary a lot depending on disciplinary background) are:

¹⁵ Declaration for Open Science and Research 2020-2025. Available at <https://edition.fi/tsv/catalog/book/79>

- Scientific research conducted with participation from the public (in different phases of the research process).
- Co-creation with the public in the research process.
- Two-way communication and education, both scientists and the public.

The pilot project, in which the ÅAU Library, the Centre for Lifelong Learning, the Communications Department and representatives from the Rectorate are involved, focuses on how to engage researchers to include CS elements in their research practice. It aims to reply some main questions: What kind of support might researchers need when using CS in their research projects? How to select projects that gain most from different kind of support? What kind of service do we need to develop for researchers and citizens respectively? Which collaborations and services within ÅAU do we need to develop to support CS? Its main goals are:

- Raising awareness amongst our researchers about CS and the general public by using a method for producing new knowledge and science impact – collaborative research.
- Developing support structures for the researchers.
- Developing and training researchers in science communication.
- Leading to citizens being active participators rather than objects of science.

The implementation of the pilot involves:

- Arranging information sessions, workshops and webinars for researchers.
- Selecting relevant research projects for the pilot: different faculties and disciplines; previous experience and the need for support; different forms and levels of citizen engagement.
- Developing information material on how to carry out CS together with the researchers in the pilot.
- Offering researchers support with project coordination and communication to increase the possibilities of cooperation with citizens
- Evaluating the results of the pilot to further develop the support.

The second presentation, by **Prof. Lukas Worschech** (Julius-Maximilian-Universität Würzburg), deals with the topic of 'Citizen Science as part of knowledge transfer actions with SMEs'. The goal of knowledge transfer is to transfer knowledge generated at the university to the economy and public sectors with a high degree of efficiency and for social and entrepreneurial benefit. JMU, with its Service Centre Research and Technology Transfer, aims to:

- Provide important impulses for the local economy, society and the environment through research areas with high future potential.

- Build innovative transfer structures and dynamic innovation networks.
- Support the acquisition of collaborative projects between science and industry.
- Promote start-ups and ensure the evaluation and exploitation of inventions.

In addition, the university supports networks with regional SMEs via diverse projects. The ESF-BuDanu: Using Business Data project focuses on transferring knowledge for SMEs employees in Bavaria, as well as providing training in digital skills and exploiting the potential of corporate data. The EFRE BigData@Geo project represents a good example on the application of taking big data to application. It includes an interactive climate atlas that conveys knowledge about climate change in Lower Franconia (Bavaria) in a low threshold and user-friendly way. Citizens are particularly aware of extreme events and are thus primed for the climate change problem, at least in the short term. The needs of decision-makers from society (here the agricultural sector) shape the scientific knowledge process and lead to products/information that science would not have produced without citizen participation.

Dr. Ellen Roemer (Hochschule Ruhr West) presents 'Opportunities for Citizen Science Projects - Experiences at Ruhr West University of Applied Science'. Dr. Roemer first introduces the university, located in the western part of the Ruhr in a diverse community. Then, shows the taxonomy of Citizen Social Science projects at HRW, by differentiating three forms:

- Contributory projects.
- Collaborative projects.
- Co-created/autonomous projects.

Contributory projects, in which citizens participate as research objects and discussants, usually entail scientific talks and discussions and surveys, and imply mainly a passive contribution from their side (although more active participation is foreseen in the near future). Co-created projects, where institutions are co-creators in research, are carried out with the city council, local companies and NGOs, that provide research questions, secondary data, give feedback to measurement instruments, participate in pre-tests, provide access to the local community for data collection, and provide platforms for discussions and help with interpretation of data.

The key experiences, and the important ingredients for successful CS projects, are:

- Engagement with and integration of researchers and their institutions into the activities of the local community.
- Networking with key stakeholders and actors (citizens, politicians, NGOs, etc.) - digital (e.g., via social media) and non-digital (meetings, events).
- Non-scientific knowledge communication between academics and key stakeholders/actors.

Figure 7. Panel Session. University with and for Society: Promoting Citizen Science within Open Science. Speakers: Gemma Marfany (UB); Marko Joas and Mats Lindfelt (ÅAU); Lukas Worschech (JMU); Ellen Roemer (HRW); Josep Perelló (UB).

The last contribution, by **Prof. Josep Perelló** (University of Barcelona), presents the OpenSystems-UB experience on 'Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action: The experience of the CoAct EU project'. Prof. Perelló first highlights the active environment regarding CS initiatives currently taking place in the city of Barcelona. Then, introduces the CoAct project based on co-creation and collective action, with the aim of delivering policy briefs for policy-makers.

CS is about participation, but there are diverse schools, with different notions and approaches for this process. The starting point for the project is the idea that CS is a "form of science developed and enacted by citizens themselves" (Irwin, 1995)¹⁶. CoAct understands CS as a participatory research process co-designed and directly driven by citizen groups that share a social concern. The main actors in this project are considered co-researchers, that is, persons having a lived experience in relation to the social concerns and thus recognized as experts-in-the-field. As such, they are co-owners of the research data and results. The idea is to produce an action plan to tackle the common issue, from a collective perspective. Four topics are selected: mental health care; youth employment; environmental justice; and gender equality.

With regards to the mental health side of the initiative, the project decided to focus on social support networks, in order to understand how they work and propose actions to strengthen them. A Telegram Chatbot was developed, through co-creation with citizens, to collect data to end up producing a set of recommendations for policy-makers.

Before closing the session, Prof. Marfany asks all the speakers to provide a brief take-home message for the audience. Dr. Roemer stresses that non-scientific communication is key to promote CS and Open Science, so that real involvement of citizens is achieved, to democratize science. Researchers, as well as administrations, need to make an effort to engage with citizenship. Prof. Worschech highlights the importance of involving young researchers and fostering engagement with SMEs to guide results and innovation towards society. Dr. Lindfelt, from the research support side, emphasizes the need to provide training on CS and communication skills to all practitioners that are part of these processes. Prof. Joas states points out the importance for universities to systematically support CS, not only regarding external stakeholders, but also their own researchers. Prof. Perelló, to conclude, puts emphasis on not doing CS alone (from the researchers' point of view), but to necessarily include citizenship throughout the whole process.

¹⁶ Irwin, A. (1995). Citizen science: A study of people, expertise and sustainable development. Routledge Press.

3.6 Closure¹⁷

Meeting closing remarks.

Speaker: BRIAN BRODERICK. Associate Dean of Research, Trinity College Dublin.

Prof. Brian Broderick (Associate Dean of Research, Trinity College Dublin) brings the meeting to a close, by thanking all participants and attendants (online and in-person), and hoping the exchange of experiences and knowledge among the Alliances is useful for further progress their respective projects. Prof. Broderick thanks the organizing committee of the event and highlights the relevance of the programme and speakers. The European Research Area is changing, and it is clear that the way researchers work is changing, and who researchers work with as well. The Alliances are going to play a strong role in that change and thus, in shaping the future European research. That is the main message from today, we can help that transformation by collaborating together.

Figure 8. Closure. Speaker: Brian Broderick (Trinity College Dublin)

¹⁷ Session recording available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sIECPWRU40k>.

4. OUTCOME & CONCLUSIONS

The second TORCH Open Forum, under the title ‘**Sharing Common R&I Policies and Strategies: Strengthening Collaboration Towards a Transformational Approach**’, was held on March 8, 2023, hosted by the Trinity College Dublin.

The meeting was addressed to diverse relevant collectives: university leadership, academic and technical staff, as well as any actors engaged in R&I activities and universities collaboration. It was also relevant for policymakers, as the European Commission’s perspective was included. The event was conceived as a dissemination activity not only to share and discuss the TORCH Project progresses, but also as a forum in which fellow University Alliances could showcase their SwafS projects initiatives. As such, all FOREU1 and FOREU2 Alliances were invited to participate, since the main topics covered were relevant to their development:

- Working towards reforming research assessment.
- Fostering equality, diversity and inclusivity.
- Championing Open Science.
- Promoting inter/transdisciplinary research driven by societal challenges.
- Intensifying R&I Cooperation Between Universities.

More than 120 participants attended the different sessions (online plus in person), in which 61 chairs, speakers or rapporteurs took part. Plenary and panel sessions were recorded and are available in the CHARM-EU YouTube channel. Updates on the event were also live-tweeted. For more details on participation and engagement see Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2. TORCH 2nd Open Forum participation (online and in-person).

Online participation during streamed sessions (registrations: 153)			
Morning Sessions https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ka8oO7n4Nck		Afternoon Sessions https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sIECPWRU40k	
Opening ceremony	53	Cluster Sessions	84
Plenary Session	63	Panel Session	29
Panel Session	52	Closure	14
Peak number	63	Peak number	29
Total views*	444	Total views*	1000
In person participation during sessions (registration: 68)			
Morning Sessions	≈60	Afternoon Sessions	≈50

*Total views (as of March 27, 2023) since the videos were published (source: YouTube Analytics).

Table 3. TORCH 2nd Open Forum social media engagement. Data retrieved on March 14, 2023 (except the post-communication posts, on March 27, 2023).

Date / Channel	Twitter	LinkedIn	Facebook	Instagram
2023.02.07-08	Twitter post n.1 (2082)	LinkedIn post n.1 (664)	Facebook post n.1 (124)	Instagram post n.1 (377)
2023.02.16	Twitter post n.2 (1968)	LinkedIn post n.2 (916)	Facebook post n.2 (102)	Instagram post n.2 (261)
2023.02.21	Twitter post n.3 (592)	LinkedIn post n.3 (937)	Facebook post n.3 (998)	Instagram post n.3 (417)
2023.02.24	Twitter post n.4 (529)	LinkedIn post n.4 (831)	Facebook post n.4 (53)	
2023.03.01	Twitter post n.5 (2525)	LinkedIn post n.5 (563)	Facebook post n.5 (415)	
2023.03.06	Twitter post n.6 (1399)			
2023.03.08-09	Live thread (3971) & tweet (1290)	LinkedIn post communication 1 (1196)	Facebook post communication 1 (154)	Instagram post communication 1 (323)
Post-comm posts	Twitter post (2056)	LinkedIn post (605)	Facebook post (101)	Instagram post (272)

The Plenary Session on the **‘ERA’s Policy Agenda 2022-2024 and R&I Cooperation Between European Universities’** put together a diverse panel of speakers who discussed the role of the Alliances as innovative living labs within the ERA’s framework. Representatives of different entities shared their views on the Policy Agenda, such as the Coimbra Group and the European University Association (as universities organizations) or Science Europe (with the research funding organizations perspective), all of them involved in co-creating the general strategy. Linkages between the different actions included in the Agenda were highlighted and the (potential) activities of Alliances were also discussed, with a focus on those of them which are more relevant and could have greater impact on their development.

The Panel Session on **‘The European perspective on the reform of research assessment’** presented the latest approaches and progress on the revision of the evaluation systems for research-performing institutions, researchers, and funding agencies. All the participants agreed on the need to reform research assessment, such process being a priority for the new European Research Area. The roadmap established by the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) was discussed, including the perspective of the European Commission (DG RTD) as well as the Irish Health Research Board (as a national funding agency), the European University Association and Utrecht University.

The **TORCH Cluster Sessions (‘Progress on joint R&I strategies in European University Alliances’)** served the purpose of exchanging experiences and practices among several Alliances with regards to some R&I key areas:

- Cluster 1: **'New approaches for diverse academic careers'**. Six Alliances (CHARM-EU, ARQUS, FORTHEM, YUFE, CIVIS, and EPICUR) shared their progress and plans to promote Open Science and intersectional initiatives regarding equal opportunities, non-discrimination and inclusivity, as well as presented some specific actions and strategies on reforming research assessment.
- Cluster 2: **'Intensifying R&I cooperation between universities'**. Eight examples of initiatives to build collaborative frameworks for joint and shared R&I-related activities were shared. FORTHEM, EELISA, SEA-EU, UNIC, ECIU, CIVIS, and CHARM-EU presented diverse cases, from the creation of joint research support offices to sharing research infrastructures or setting up networks of TTOs. Speakers agreed on the need to keep developing collaborative frameworks across HEIs.
- Cluster 3: **'Promoting inter/transdisciplinary research driven by societal challenges'**. Good practices and strategies on exploring joint transdisciplinary, challenge-driven research were discussed. Representatives of CHARM-EU, EC2U, FilmEU, Circle U, CIVICA, Una Europa, and FORTHEM put forward their Alliances' respective plans to support inter/transdisciplinarity.

The Panel Session **'University with and for Society: promoting Citizen Science within Open Science'** brought together representatives of different universities (Åbo Akademi University, Julius-Maximilian-Universität Würzburg, Hochschule Ruhr West, and the University of Barcelona) to discuss their institutional plans and support systems to foster Citizen Science, presented some hands-on experiences and participatory projects involving citizens, local communities and the wider society as co-creators, finally sharing some take-home messages as helpful ideas and advice, and pointing out some strengths and caveats when implementing CS research.

ANNEX I: PUBLIC PROGRAMME AND PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL

Public Programme

The full programme, along with the concept note and practical information to attend the event, were published at <https://www.charm-eu.eu/torch-2nd-annual-forum-march-2023>

Banner

Twitter & Instagram

Social Media Promotion and Live Tweets (examples)

CHARM-EU
1.385 seguidores
2 semanas

Our 2nd TORCH Annual Forum organized by Trinity College Dublin is approaching: researchers, university leaders, innovators and policymakers will discuss common R&I strategies and pioneering responsible research and innovation initiatives.

The event will focus on five key areas:

- Working towards reforming research assessment
- Fostering equality, diversity and inclusivity
- Championing Open Science
- Intensifying R&I Cooperation Between Universities
- Promoting inter/transdisciplinary research driven by societal challenges

Watch our video to learn more about the purpose & agenda of TORCH and register now! <https://lnkd.in/gqTUKSBd>

#TORCHForum2023 #research #innovation #OpenScience #CitizenScience #equality #inclusion #transdisciplinarity #cooperation #ERA

Tú y 19 personas más 4 veces compartido

CHARM-EU
1.385 seguidores
1 semana

One week to go until our 2nd TORCH Annual Forum focusing on responsible research & innovation and common R&I strategies.

The event will bring together researchers, innovators, university leaders, policymakers, higher education advisors and representatives of European University Alliances to discuss together the key areas related to R&I cooperation and reform.

Learn more about the main topics of the event as well as our diverse group of contributors and register now! <https://bit.ly/3KyknCb>

#TORCHForum2023 #research #innovation #OpenScience #equality #transdisciplinarity #cooperation

Tú y 17 personas más 5 veces compartido

CHARM-EU
1.385 seguidores
5 días · Editado

We would like to say thank you to all the speakers, chairs, contributors, organizers and attendees for joining our #TORCHForum2023 yesterday and taking part in the discussions on common research & innovation strategies! It was an honour to have You with us! 🙌

We were thrilled to have representatives of 14 fellow Alliances sharing their achievements and perspectives, as well as to have colleagues representing diverse national and international actors within the European R&I landscape. 🌟

Huge thank you Trinity College Dublin for hosting us! ❤️

con Tú y 28 personas más
63 2 comentarios · 6 veces compartido

CHARM-EU
@charm_eu

One week to go until our #TORCHForum2023 in @tcddublin focusing on responsible research and innovation strategies, cooperation and reform.

Learn more about the key topics of the event as well as our diverse group of contributors and register now! bit.ly/3KyknCb

Universitat de Barcelona y 6 más
11:53 · 01 mar 23 · 2.250 Visualizaciones

CHARM-EU
@charm_eu

Our #TORCHForum2023 is under way in Dublin with Provost @LindaDoyle from @tcddublin, Vice-rector @jordigarciafdez from @UniBarcelona and Head of @campus_engage Kate Morris from @IUOfficial opening the event

Follow the TORCH Forum live bit.ly/3mpNrlY

#HappeningNow

TORCH 2nd Annual Forum 2023 | Morning Sessions

CHARM-EU
@charm_eu

Happy to have representatives of 14 Alliances sharing their work on R&I! Thank you @ArqusAlliance @FORTHAlliance @AllianceYufe @civis_eu @EpicurAlliance @eelisa_eu @SeaEuAlliance @UNIC_EU @ECIUUniversities @EC2U Alliance @filmeualliance @CircleU_eu @CIVICA_EU & @Una_Europa! 🇪🇺

Gareth O'Neill @gtonell

Join our session on the #ERAPolicyAgenda and #UniversityAlliances with @LidiaBorrellDam @StefEurope and @Emma_Gardan on 08 March 2023 at #TORCHForum2023 at 11.00-12.15 CET. Agenda → bit.ly/3yggcUA. Morning → bit.ly/3myMall. Afternoon → bit.ly/3yelcbz

CHARM-EU y 9 más
15:49 · 06 mar 23 · 2.094 Visualizaciones
7 Retweets · 6 Citas · 19 Me gusta

OPUS.eu - Open and Universal Scie... @OpusEu

Today, 11.00-12.15 CET: Our colleague @gtonell in the #ERAPolicyAgenda and R&I Cooperation Between European Universities session with @LidiaBorrellDam @StefEurope and @Emma_Gardan at #TORCHForum2023. Agenda bit.ly/3yggcUA. Morning bit.ly/3myMall #OpenScience

Traducir Tweet

CHARM-EU @charm_eu

During the first plenary session @ScienceEurope Senior Policy Officer Adrian Braem, @TechnopolisGrip Consultant @gtonell, @CoimbraGroup Director @Emma_Gardan and R&I Director @StefEurope from @euatweets focus on the ERA policy agenda and R&I cooperation between universities 🤝👍

Trinity College Dublin y 5 más
11:09 · 08 mar 23 · 1.284 Visualizaciones

Campus Engage @campus_engage

Busy morning celebrating and debating potential of EU University Alliance #societalimpact #TORCHforum2023 with colleagues from @TUAofficial Brian Broderick @tcdublin Padraig Murphy @DCU Martin Galvin @JohnBarimo @UCC with Stephane Berghmans @euatweets @UniBarcelona @charm_eu

John O'Halloran y 3 más
13:42 · 08 mar 23 · 2.822 Visualizaciones

Aine Moore @AineMoore1 · 5d

Delighted to speak on behalf of @Una_Europa about the alliances interdisciplinary approach to address societal challenges. Thank you @charm_eu and Torch for the invite to such an interesting forum #TORCHForum2023 #SocietalImpact

CHARM-EU @charm_eu · 5d

Happy to have representatives of 14 Alliances sharing their work on R&I! Thank you @ArqusAlliance @FORTHEMAlliance @AllianceYufe @civis_eu @EpicurAlliance @eelisa_eu ...
Mostrar este hilo

1 · 24 · 1.184

RRING Project @RRING_PROJECT

The #ERAPolicyAgenda and #UniversityAlliances session with @gtonell, @LidiaBorrellDam @StefEurope and @Emma_Gardan on 08 March 2023 at #TORCHForum2023 at 11.00-12.15 CET. Agenda → bit.ly/3yggcUA. Morning → bit.ly/3myMall. Afternoon → bit.ly/3yelcbz

Traducir Tweet

ANNEX II: PRESENTATIONS

Opening Ceremony

KATE MORRIS. Head of Campus Engage, Irish Universities Association.

It is a **requirement for funding**

- ✓ Horizon Europe
- ✓ SFI Challenge based funding calls

A competitive **edge for Ireland**

A competitive **edge for Ireland**

Research as a **gateway** between society and **evidence informed policy making**

- 1 Change **attitudes & culture**
- 2 Change **infrastructure & roles**
- 3 Build **Capacity**

TAKE ACTION

BUILDING CAPACITY
RELAUNCH - 6 WEEK "TRAIN THE TRAINER" COURSE
ENGAGED RESEARCH & INNOVATION FOR SOCIETAL IMPACT

@CAMPUS_ENGAGE

30 NEW CAMPUS ENGAGE TRAINERS

2022 OUTCOMES

- Number of **new Trainers** 2022: **32**
- Number of **respondents** to survey: **22**
- Number of **training workshops** delivered by Trainers May 2022 - February 2023: **37**
- Number of **people trained** at workshops: **1,520**
- Number of **pending workshops** March - May 2023: **10**
- Number of **other events** including conference presentations, webinars, seminars: **15**
- Number of **people in attendance** at other events: **3,931**

Global reach:

Plenary Session: ERA's Policy Agenda 2022-2024 and R&I Cooperation Between European Universities

ADRIEN BRAEM. Senior Policy Officer, Science Europe.

TORCH ANNUAL FORUM

8 MARCH 2023

ADRIEN BRAEM

ABOUT SCIENCE EUROPE

WHAT IS SCIENCE EUROPE?

Science Europe is the association representing major public organisations that fund or perform excellent, ground-breaking research in Europe.

<p>30 countries</p> <p>With members from 30 EU and non-EU countries and beyond parts of Europe, we speak with a truly European voice.</p>	<p>40 member organisations</p> <p>Bringing together research-funding and research performing organisations.</p>	<p>22.4 bn €</p> <p>Spent on research per year by our members</p> <p>Our members make a significant contribution to European scientific research and excellence opportunities in European science and research performing.</p>
--	--	---

3

SCIENCE EUROPE'S MISSION

SCIENCE EUROPE MISSION

Define long-term perspectives for European research and champion best practice approaches, ensuring high-quality science for the benefit of humanity and the planet.

4

VALUE SYSTEM FOR THE ORGANISATION OF RESEARCH

Values lie at the centre of the research system and therefore underlie rigorous research processes and activities, outputs and outcomes, research management, and governance.

Values Framework (Science Europe, June 2022)

5

HOW IS SCIENCE EUROPE'S CONTRIBUTING TO THE ERA?

6

ROLE OF SCIENCE EUROPE AND ITS MEMBERS IN IMPLEMENTING THE ERA

- Both research funding and performing organisations need to be at the table when discussing the implementation of the ERA.
- Funders can design their instruments and policies in different ways to achieve goals put forward in the ERA Actions. Performers implement the changes needed to achieve the ERA and face its impacts on the ground.
- Science Europe and its research funding and performing members collaborate and act together following three strategic priorities:
 - Shaping European research policy developments
 - Contributing to the evolution of research culture
 - Strengthening the role and contribution of science in tackling societal challenges
- Science Europe and its members support the advancement of national European research systems and build the strongest possible research ecosystem for the benefit of science, researchers, institutions, and society.
- In addition, we contribute to global developments through participation in worldwide initiatives, such as the Global Research Council.

7

OVERVIEW OF PRIORITIES

Process of commitment took place in late 2021/early 2022. Member States, Associated Countries, and stakeholders were invited to send commitments. Science Europe provided a series of commitments aligned with its Strategic Plan.

- | | |
|--|---|
| • ERA Action 1 on Open Science. | • ERA Action 9 on CBC. |
| • ERA Action 3 on Research Assessment. | • ERA Action 12 and 13 on Green Transition. |
| • ERA Action 4 on Research Careers. | • ERA Action on Research Infrastructures. |
| • ERA Action 5 on Inclusive Gender Equality. | • ERA Action 16 on Access to Excellence. |
| • ERA Action 6 on Academic Freedom. | |

8

CASE STUDY - COARA

- ERA Action 3 mostly revolves around the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment – which brings together signatories of the Agreement to work towards its implementation.
- Science Europe (together with the European Universities Association and Karen Stroobants) was part of the drafting committee of the Agreement. It is now part of the CoARA steering board.
- 481 organisations have signed the Agreement, as 24 February 2023
 - Of those, 423 CoARA are members, from 35 countries
 - 32 of 40 Science Europe Member Organisations committed
- Large diversity of organisation types, but still very European - 63% Universities / 11% other RPOs / 9% RFOs / 9% Academies & Research community associations / 6% non-profit orgs / 2% national agencies.
- Science Europe is also supporting the setting up of the CoARA Working Groups and will manage one of the Working Groups that will be established.

9

SCIENCE EUROPE'S PLANNED CONTRIBUTION IN 2023

- Develop an overall strategic vision for the ERA and a narrative for the ERA Policy Agenda.
- Propose a list of essential ERA Actions to be included in the ERA Policy Agenda 2025-2027 in the form of thematic papers on each of these priorities.
- This position will form the basis of Science Europe's advocacy and contributions towards the development of the next ERA Policy Agenda.
- Actively contribute to the discussions in the ERA Forum.

10

NEW ERA – ONE YEAR ON

11

NEW ERA – SUCCESSES AND CHALLENGES

Successes

- **Involvement of stakeholders** has seen a substantial improvement compared to the previous policy cycles.
- Stronger **impetus to the ERA**, including through a better involvement of Member States and increased commitments.
- **Sub-group on the Global Approach** works well.

Challenges

- **Progress** towards implementing the different ERA Actions has been **uneven**.
- **Interconnections and synergies** between the different ERA Actions and activities have **not been exploited** as much as they could have.
- ERA Policy Agenda is close to the Commission's priorities and **certain key issues are missing**.

12

WHAT IS NEXT – ERA POLICY AGENDA 2025-2027

13

NEW POLICY AGENDA AND HOW IT COULD IMPROVE THE ERA

What is going to happen?

- Discussions are already starting to develop the ERA Policy Agenda 2025-2027.
- It will take place first in the ERA Forum and in ERAC throughout 2023.
- Definition of a list of ERA Actions followed by a new commitments process.

What are the opportunities for change?

- Mid-term cycle allows to review the **ERA Actions** and bring them closer to research priorities.
- New policy agenda leads to a **reflection on the role of the Forum** (and stakeholders)

14

OPEN QUESTIONS AND CHALLENGES

- What changes and improvements could be made to the role of the ERA Forum?
 - It could focus more on overseeing the implementation of the ERA Actions and ensuring that the synergies are properly exploited.
- How could the ERA Policy Agenda be improved?
 - Focus could be directed towards a shorter list of essential issues and priorities that affect the research ecosystem – and less on activities undertaken by other fora.
 - Could take a more holistic approach: will centre around finding solutions for issues that are shared across Europe and ensures that all ERA Actions work towards the same objectives.

15

Plenary Session: ERA's Policy Agenda 2022-2024 and R&I Cooperation Between European Universities

GARETH O'NEILL. Principal Consultant on Open Science, Technopolis Group.

European Universities and Areas of Institutional Change

Gareth O'Neill
TORCH Annual Forum 2023
08 March 2023 in Dublin

bit.ly/3Jmd9QQ

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gareth.oneill@technopolis-group.com

01

ERA Policy Agenda: 20 actions

- DEEPENING A TRULY FUNCTIONING INTERNAL MARKET FOR KNOWLEDGE**
 1. Open sharing of knowledge, incl. EOSC
 2. Data legislation fit for research
 3. Reform of research assessment
 4. Strengthen research careers
 5. Gender equality and inclusiveness
 6. Protect academic freedom
 7. Better knowledge valorisation
 8. Research infrastructures
 9. International cooperation, reciprocity
- TOGETHER FOR TWIN GREEN AND DIGITAL TRANSITION, AND INCREASING SOCIETY'S PARTICIPATION IN THE ERA**
 10. R&I Missions and Partnerships for ERA
 11. Green energy transformation
 12. Transition of industrial ecosystems
 13. Empower higher education institutions
 14. Bring science closer to society
- AMPLIFYING ACCESS TO RESEARCH AND INNOVATION EXCELLENCE ACROSS THE UNION**
 15. Regional and national R&I ecosystems
 16. EU-wide access to excellence
 17. Strategic capacity of public RPOs
- ADVANCING CONCERTED R&I INVESTMENTS AND REFORMS**
 18. Coordination national support for ERA
 19. ERA monitoring mechanism
 20. Prioritisation and coordination of R&I investments and reforms

University Alliances

Council invited EC in 2018 to:

- Strengthen strategic partnerships between HEIs across EU
- Encourage emergence by 2024 of 'European University' alliances
- Enable students to obtain a degree by combining studies across several EU countries

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03

University Alliances

Erasmus+ pilot support:	Horizon 2020 support:
2019: 17 new alliances	2020: €2 M to 17 alliances for R&I transformations
2020: 24 new alliances	2020: €2 M to 24 alliances for R&I transformations
2022: 16 extra support	
2022: 4 new alliances	

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04

Areas of Institutional Change

- (1) Developing a common R&I agenda and action plan
- (2) Sharing resources & infrastructures
- (3) Strengthening human capital
- (4) Reinforcing cooperation with non-academic sector
- (5) Mainstreaming Open Science practices
- (6) Engaging citizens & society
- (7) Exploring joint structures

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05

Areas of Institutional Change

- (1) Developing a common R&I agenda and action plan
 - o Identification of challenges and convergence
 - o Preparation of action plans
 - o Identification of resources
 - o Scaling excellence

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06

Areas of Institutional Change

- (2) Sharing resources & infrastructures
 - o Needs
 - o Cooperation
 - o Infrastructures for Open Science

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07

Areas of Institutional Change

- (3) Strengthening human capital
 - o Framework conditions
 - o New balance in the assessment of academics
 - o Dealing with brain drain
 - o Cloud of knowledge
 - o Promoting talent (skills and competences)

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08

<p style="text-align: center;">Areas of Institutional Change </p> <p>(4) Reinforcing cooperation with non-academic sector</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Developing an innovation strategy ○ Strengthening innovation capacity ○ Mainstreaming entrepreneurial mind-set ○ Inducing cooperation ○ Innovation pipeline development <p>@gtoneill gareth.oneill@technopolis-group.com</p> <p style="text-align: right;">09</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Areas of Institutional Change </p> <p>(5) Mainstreaming Open Science practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Open Access and research data management ○ Open Science skills and education ○ Open Science incentives and rewards ○ Open Science ambassadors <p>@gtoneill gareth.oneill@technopolis-group.com</p> <p style="text-align: right;">10</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Areas of Institutional Change </p> <p>(6) Engaging citizens & society</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Science in society ○ Citizen science ○ Knowledge creating teams ○ Outreach to children and schools ○ Sustainable Development Goals ○ Policy feedback <p>@gtoneill gareth.oneill@technopolis-group.com</p> <p style="text-align: right;">11</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Areas of Institutional Change </p> <p>(7) Exploring joint structures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Common technical activities ○ Facilitating collaboration in activities ○ Common obstacles and solutions ○ Clustering activities to share best practices <p>@gtoneill gareth.oneill@technopolis-group.com</p> <p style="text-align: right;">12</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Progress of University Alliances </p> <p>Report to be published in March/April 2023 by REA</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Progress of Pilot I University Alliance Projects under IBA-SwafS-Support-1-2020 Call</p> <p>Looks at challenges, progress, and good practices of the Pilot I University Alliances</p> <p>@gtoneill gareth.oneill@technopolis-group.com</p> <p style="text-align: right;">13</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">European Universities and Areas of Institutional Change </p> <p style="text-align: center;">Thank you!</p> <p>@gtoneill gareth.oneill@technopolis-group.com</p> <p style="text-align: right;">14</p>

Plenary Session: ERA's Policy Agenda 2022-2024 and R&I Cooperation Between European Universities

EMMANUELLE GARDAN. Director of Coimbra Group.

FACTS AND FIGURES

- Founded in 1985
- 41 Universities from 23 European countries
- > 1,4M students / > 232 000 staff members (teaching, research, admin.)
- 14.4% of all signed grants in H2020:
 - 25% of all RIAs, IAs and CSA projects awarded under Pillar II
 - 12.5% of all ERC funded grants
 - 15.5% of all MSCA funded projects
- 21% of all signed grants in HEU:
 - 26% of all RIAs, IAs and CSA projects under Pillar II
 - 11,7% of all ERC funded grants
 - 20.85% of all MSCA funded projects

CG MEMBERS OFFICIALLY INVOLVED IN ALLIANCES OF EUROPEAN UNIVERSITIES

CHARM-EU Barcelona (ES) Bergen (NO) Budapest (HU) Dublin (IE) Montpellier (FR) Utrecht (NL) Würzburg (DE) Åbo Akademi (FI)	Una Europa Bologna (IT) Edinburgh (UK) Kraków (PL) Leiden (NL) KU Leuven (BE)	EC2U Coimbra (PT) Jagi (RO) Jena (DE) Pavia (IT) Poltters (FR) Salamanca (ES) Turku (FI)	ENLIGHT Galway (IE) Göttingen (DE) Groningen (NL) Tartu (EE) Uppsala (SE)
ARQUS Bergen (NO) Granada (ES) Graz (AT) Padova (IT) Vilnius (LT)	4EU+ Heidelberg (DE) Prague (CZ) Geneva (CH)	Circle U. Aarhus (DK) Louvain (BE)	EUniWell Cologne (DE)

With CG as Associated Partner

NEW ERA: A STRATEGIC PRIORITY FOR COIMBRA GROUP FOR 2022-2023

- Actively engage in the implementation of the **European Research Area**, more specifically for Actions 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 11, 13 and 14
- Reform of **research assessment** (CG is a founding member of the COARA)
- **European Universities Initiative**
- **European Strategy for Universities**
- Continue strengthening **Coimbra Group engagement with society**
- Continue developing policies, tools and guidelines to **limit the impact of BREXIT on Universities' core activities**

CG ENGAGEMENT WITH THE NEW ERA

- Active engagement with the EU institutions in shaping the **Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe (Nov 2021)**, which sets out **principles** for research and innovation for the first time ever.
- Intense advocacy for promoting stakeholder representation, and specifically **university sector representation in the new ERA governance**.
- Coimbra Group is **formally registered as an ERA stakeholder** since Nov 2021, and currently represented as such in the ERA Forum by the EUA (main) and YERUN (alternate).
- Active engagement with the EU institutions in **shaping the ERA Policy Agenda for 2022-2024** (set of 20 Policy Actions) and soon for the next period.

CG ENGAGEMENT IN THE IMPLEMENTATION PHASE

- Which role for CG? **Consultation of our members on the 20 ERA actions** to identify those that both are **priority** for us collectively – where we can bring **added-value**.
- **Formal commitment to implement 8 ERA Policy Actions:**
 - ☐ **Action 3, Reform of research assessment:**
 - ➔ CG member of core groups drafting the agreement & setting the governance - *Coimbra founding member*
 - ☐ **Action 4, Attractive & sustainable research careers, balanced talent circulation & international, transdisciplinary & inter-sectoral mobility across the ERA:**
 - ➔ CG co-sponsor of this action jointly with Partagsi (work plan and roll-out)
 - ☐ **Action 5, Promote gender equality & foster inclusiveness:**
 - ➔ CG member of the action's subgroup
 - ☐ **Action 6, Protecting academic freedom in Europe; not started yet**
 - ☐ **Action 8, Sustainability, accessibility and resilience of research infrastructures:**
 - ➔ CG actively involved
 - ☐ **Action 11, An ERA for Green Transformation:**
 - ➔ CG actively involved on the stand of activities related to the future of work
 - ☐ **Action 13, Empowering HEIs to develop in line with the ERA/EEA:**
 - ➔ CG co-chair of the action's subgroup together with France
 - ☐ **Action 14, Attracting science closer to citizens; not started yet**

MOST RELEVANT SPECIFIC ACTIONS FOR THE ALLIANCES; THE WHY?

- **May 2021 Council Conclusions on the European Universities:**
 - "European Universities will:
 - contribute decisively towards achieving the ambitious vision of an **innovative, globally competitive and attractive EEA and ERA**, in full synergy with the EHEA,
 - by helping to boost the **excellence dimension of HERI**,
 - while promoting **gender equality, inclusiveness, and equity**,
 - allowing for **seamless and ambitious transnational cooperation** between higher education institutions in Europe, and inspiring the transformation of higher education".
 - "European Universities are
 - strengthening the attractiveness of academic and research careers,
 - supporting institutional change, for example, through **inclusive gender equality plans**,
 - and reinforcing **cooperation with surrounding ecosystem actors**;
 - working towards **open science & open education, engaging with citizens** for solving societal challenges
 - and reinforcing **excellence** in education and research for global competitiveness"

MOST RELEVANT SPECIFIC ACTIONS FOR THE ALLIANCES; THE WHY?

- "European Universities will contribute to strengthen the research & innovation dimensions of HEIs in Europe by developing a **common agenda, shared infrastructures and resources**, fostering critical mass, strengthening human capital & involving non academic actors in teaching & research, connecting with surrounding innovation ecosystems, with citizens and society".
- "European Universities should be guided to serve as "testbeds":
 - for research, including **academic career assessment & rewarding systems** that take into account inter alia open science practices, quality of teaching, transfer of knowledge and outreach;
 - improved tenure track systems and **strengthened career management and diversification**;
 - and adoption of **open science principles and practices**, including the EOSC and the open access publishing infrastructures, knowledge & data sharing, as well as open collaboration".
- "European Universities should be guided to promote the endorsement of the "European Charter for Researchers" and the "Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers" & their implementation mechanisms, including the HRS4R and EURAXESS and the future ERA Talent Platform".
- **April 2022 Council Conclusions on the European Strategy for Universities:**
 - "These alliances should also be supported, where appropriate, in promoting the development of **attractive and sustainable careers**; in mutualising resources and structures, for instance laboratories and platforms".

MOST RELEVANT SPECIFIC ERA ACTIONS FOR THE ALLIANCES:

THE WHY?

=> MY ANSWER: ALL ERA ACTIONS ARE POTENTIALLY RELEVANT FOR THE ALLIANCES!

ERA ACTION 4: STRENGTHENING RESEARCH CAREERS

Deepening the ERA: Action 4 – Strengthen research careers

- DEEPENING A TRULY FUNCTIONING INTERNAL MARKET FOR KNOWLEDGE
- Action 4 – Promote attractive and sustainable research careers, balanced talent circulation and international, transdisciplinary and inter-sectoral mobility across the ERA**
- 3 levels of activity**
1. Development of a comprehensive **European Framework for Research Careers**
 2. **Exchange of best practices** on skills and mutual learning to support inter-sectoral mobility and more balanced talent circulation (e.g. ResearchComp, ERA4You)
 3. **Support measures** to improve attractiveness of research careers within and beyond academia (e.g. HRS4R, Research Careers Observatory, ERA Talent Platform)

ERA ACTION 4: STRENGTHENING RESEARCH CAREERS

- **Formal commitments received for this action:**
 - 26 Member States
 - 3 Associated Countries
 - 12 Stakeholder Organisations
- **Kick-off meeting on 1st February 2023, Brussels co-chaired by DG RTD, Portugal and Coimbra Group:** state of play of the action; follow-up on the commitments and activities planned by MS, AC and SHO for 2023; shaping the work plan until 2024; synergies with other ERA actions with evident dimensions related to research careers.
- **EU highlights:**
 - Technical document on a European Framework for Research Careers
 - Partnership for young researchers
 - ResearchComp, ERA Talent Platform and Research and Innovation Careers Observatory

ERA ACTION 4: STRENGTHENING RESEARCH CAREERS

Action 4 - Sponsors

- There were already several exchanges between the Commission and Portugal/Coimbra Group
- Sponsors can e.g.
 - Ensure shared responsibility and ownership
 - Bring in initiatives at national or stakeholders level that are relevant
 - Pilot initiatives
 - Support the management of the implementation of the action between ERA Forum meetings

ERA ACTION 4: STRENGTHENING RESEARCH CAREERS

ERA ACTION 4: STRENGTHENING RESEARCH CAREERS

ERA ACTION 4: STRENGTHENING RESEARCH CAREERS

- Relevant ongoing projects**
- **SECURE**, kick-off meeting January 2023: focus on inter-sectoral and interoperable research careers, and career development and progression (coordinator PLOCAN consortium, Spain)
 - **DocTalent4EU**, kick-off meeting January 2023: focus on transversal skills, including machine-learning model based on ESCO to identify most in-demand skills and foster employability (coordinator University Cote d'Azur, France)
 - 39 **European Universities alliances** pilot projects (Horizon 2020) + 8 other alliances of universities (Horizon Europe), collaborating to realise capacity in ERA priorities, including implementing strategies to strengthen human capital (assessment report of the first pilots expected in Q1-Q2 2023)
 - 9 **ERA Talents** projects for intersectoral mobility (selected January 2023)

ERA ACTION 13: EMPOWERING HEIs FOR ERA IN SYNERGY WITH EEA

- **Formal commitments received for this action:**
 - 16 Member States (+2)
 - 3 Associated Countries
 - 12 Stakeholder Organisations
- **Policy approach:** subgroup w/ 1-year mandate, reporting to ERA Forum
- **1st meeting on 8th March 2023, Brussels co-chaired by DG RTD, France and Coimbra Group:** subgroup scope and mandate adopted; needs identified by MS, AC and SHO for 2023; experts' presentations shaping the work plan until 2024.

ERA ACTION 13: EMPOWERING HEIS FOR ERA IN SYNERGY WITH EEA

ERA Action 13: Empower higher education institutions
Objectives (see explanatory document)

European dimension in R&I

- Achieve excellence and inclusion in science and value creation through integrated and institutional cooperation of higher education institutions
- Support implementation of ERA actions in higher education institutions

Excellence, competitiveness

- Align Member States' efforts to improve global visibility, excellence and competitiveness of Europe's HEIs

Tool

- Develop a European Excellence Initiative

ERA ACTION 13: WORK STREAMS

- **Facilitate exchange and sharing of practices**
 - Practices on national excellence initiatives and on cooperation of universities
 - Policy and programme development in R&I and in support of institutional change of universities
- **Support coordination between countries and departments**
- **Analyse results of studies**
 - First results of Horizon support to the European Universities pilot alliances
 - Mapping and modelling of national excellence initiatives
 - Definition of the perimeter of excellence at institutional and cooperative level
- **Work together with experts from university sector to**
 - Analyse digital needs, notably digital infrastructure
 - Analyse progress and exchange practice in implementing ERA actions by universities
- **Providing recommendations on future support mechanism**

MOST RELEVANT SPECIFIC ERA ACTIONS FOR THE ALLIANCES: THE CHALLENGES

- **Diversity of ERA Policy Actions**
 - Scope
 - State of advancement
 - Synergies between actions
- **Siloed-approaches (ERA, EEA, EHEA) and plethora of EU initiatives targeting universities recently** which can be counter-productive
- **Public communication / Outreach**
 - Risks of EU-*"Brussels-bubble jargon"* and distance
 - Success criteria: ERA must create tangible impact for final users (researchers & research institutions, in particular universities)
- **Funding (EU/MS) is key** for effective implementation of ERA actions

Plenary Session: ERA's Policy Agenda 2022-2024 and R&I Cooperation Between European Universities

STEPHANE BERGHMANS. Director of Research & Innovation, European University Association.

EUA's perspective on the new European Research Area

Stephane Berghmans
Director for Research & Innovation

2nd TORCH Annual Forum
8 March 2023

The New European Research Area 2020 - 2021

- 2020**: Commission Communication "A new ERA for Research and Innovation", September
- January 2021**: Establishment of the ERA Forum for Transition
 - 12 meetings
 - Three workshops and R&I Days side event with ERA stakeholder umbrella organisations
 - Some covered topics: ERA governance framework, ERA policy agenda, four ERA pilot actions - green hydrogen, plastic pipes, EOSC, and the talent platform
- 16 July 2021**: Council Conclusions on the new ERA, December
- 16 July 2021**: Commission adopts proposal for a "Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe"
 - Principles for R&I in Europe
 - Priority areas for ERA joint actions
 - Investments and reforms
 - Simplified policy coordination
- 26 November 2021**: Council Recommendation on a "Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe"
 - Council conclusions on the new ERA governance & the first ERA policy Agenda (2022-2024)

ERA Governance

To: Minister Simona Kuszec, Commissioner Mariya Gabriel
Brussels, 4 October 2021

Open letter on ERA governance

Honourable Minister Simona Kuszec and Commissioner Mariya Gabriel,

With this letter, the undersigned representatives of research and innovation (R&I) organisations

Support to the Slovenian Council Conclusions proposal

- appropriate representation at its meetings of the following sectors...
- open online voluntary stakeholder register

→ ERA Conference (25 Oct 21)
→ Council Conclusions (26 Nov 21)

Council Conclusions - ERA Governance

Representative involvement of Stakeholders at the ERA Forum meetings

- Stakeholders should be more systematically involved in the **delivery of the ERA at Union and national levels**; National stakeholder participation should be ensured at national level
- The Commission should foresee that the ERA Forum will ensure representative involvement at its relevant meetings of **EU-level umbrella organisations or other appropriate representative organisations** relevant at EU level of the following seven types of stakeholders:
 - universities and other higher education institutions
 - research and technology performing organisations
 - R&I-intensive businesses, including SMEs,
 - individual researchers and innovators, including at early and middle stages of their careers
 - research infrastructures
 - R&I-funding organisations
 - academies of sciences

The new European Research Area

ERA university sectorial coordination group

The new European Research Area

What happened in 2022?

- 10 ERA Forum Meetings 3-12
 - 1 per month: 7 online, 3 onsite
 - Discussed ERA actions and planning for implementation
- Fortnightly ERA University Sector Group meetings
 - Sharing of information and intelligence
 - Coordination of input, feedback and approach
 - Debrief of all meetings
- ERA Subgroup on Action 9 – Global Approach
- Informal meetings and workshops on various actions

→ Sectorial coordination
→ Sectorial representation
→ Most active and contributing stakeholder group
→ Commitments to ERA Actions
→ Involvement in implementation

EUA is positive overall on the process
Still awaiting concrete outcomes
Questioning MS financial commitment

But EU stakeholders are IN!

The new European Research Area

ERA Policy Agenda 2022-2024

Commitments by Member States, associated countries and stakeholders, 24.2.2023

Chart showing commitments by Member States, associated countries and stakeholders, 24.2.2023. The chart displays the number of commitments for various ERA actions (Action 1 to Action 20) across different stakeholder groups.

The new European Research Area

ERA Policy Agenda 2022-2024

Gantt chart showing commitments for ERA actions (Action 1 to Action 20) across different stakeholder groups (AURORA, CESAER, Coimbra, ECIU, EUI, EuroTech, SPI, The Guild, UAS4EU, UNICA, YERUN) from 2022 to 2024.

eua EUROPEAN UNION ADVISORY BOARD FOR RESEARCH

Thank you for your attention

More questions?
stephane.berghmans@eua.eu

[in](#) [t](#) [f](#) [yt](#)

Panel Session: The European perspective on the reform of research assessment

JEAN-EMMANUEL FAURE. Team leader of Research assessment, DG Research & Innovation, European Commission.

Need for reform of research assessment

- To reflect **evolving research processes**
 - ✓ Digital transition; Iterative and recursive; Collaborative and open
- To reflect **increasing demands on research**
 - ✓ Societal, environmental, economic challenges; Diversity of outputs
- To move away from **inappropriate uses** of journal- and publication-based metrics
 - ✓ Rewards quantity and publication venue rather than quality; does not reward sharing, collaboration and outputs other than publications
- To further support the **quality of research** and the **attractiveness of research environments**
 - ✓ Requires a system and cultural change, involving institutions, funders and researchers

Timeline of progress

<p>Commission Scoping Report November 2021</p>	<p>Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment 20 July 2022</p>	<p>Coalition governance documents 20 October 2022</p>	<p>Coalition Constitutive Assembly 1 December 2022</p>
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Common vision & commitments

Assessment of research, researchers, and research organisations **recognises the diverse outputs, practices and activities** that maximise the quality of research and resulting impacts.

This requires basing assessments primarily on **qualitative judgement**, supported by **responsible use of quantitative indicators**.

Signatories agree to:

- Base actions on common **Principles** (from scoping report)
- Implement **10 Commitments** for change, incl. **timeframe** for implementation
- Organise and operate a **Coalition**

487 Signatories from 41 countries (3 March 2023)

<https://coara.eu/agreement/signatories/>

Next steps

- **Implementation of changes** by signatories of the Agreement
 - ✓ Process started by the end of 2023
 - ✓ At least one cycle of changes by end of 2027
- **Start of CoARA operations**
 - ✓ Call for proposals of Working Groups by the members to support exchange of knowledge and the piloting of new criteria, tools and processes
 - ✓ Secure funding for the coalition operations
- **National activities** helping the identification of national barriers to reform and possible solutions
- **Further global alignment and cooperation**
 - ✓ Attract non-European research organisations to sign the Agreement and join CoARA
 - ✓ Stimulate dialogue to facilitate alignment of approaches in various regions
- **Development of synergies** with other initiatives
 - ✓ DORA, EOSC, European Universities Alliances, etc.

Commission's support

- The Commission **signed the Agreement** on 8 November 2022 (as well as the European Research Council in February 2023)
- The Commission remains committed to **support the CoARA notably by:**
 - ✓ Being an active **member of the Coalition**, mainly in its quality as a research funder, and participating in relevant working groups and activities
 - ✓ Providing **operational support** to the CoARA Secretariat, ad interim
 - ✓ Providing **financial support** to the CoARA activities through Horizon Europe
 - ✓ Providing **policy support** in liaising the Coalition with **Member States and Associated Countries** in the framework of the ERA Forum; this will facilitate the setting up of national/regional framework conditions conducive to reforms
 - ✓ **Fostering global alignment and cooperation** with other regions worldwide & **synergies with other European initiatives**

Thank you

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Panel Session: The European perspective on the reform of research assessment

STEPHANE BERGHMANS. Director of Research & Innovation, European University Association.

A Reform of Research Assessment
The Agreement & CoARA Coalition
a university perspective

Stephane Berghmans
Director for Research & Innovation

2nd TORCH Annual Forum
8 March 2023

Universities without walls
A vision for 2030

REFORM ACADEMIC CAREERS

This vision for Europe's universities in 2030 requires a reform of academic careers. This should be acknowledged and supported by all stakeholders.

2021

Figure 1 - Open Science elements included in academic assessment (2020-21 survey data).
Source: European University Association (EUA)

How often do you include institutions that endorse or host one element of Open Science as part of their academic assessments?

Element	Very important	Important	Modestly important	Not important	Don't know
Depositing of research articles in repositories	17	49	28	4	2
Open access publishing of research articles in open access journals	18	48	28	4	2
Open access books	18	48	28	4	2
Science outreach and communication	18	48	28	4	2
Depositing of data in repositories	19	47	29	4	2
Open education	19	47	29	4	2
Research data management plan	19	47	29	4	2
Data sharing	21	45	30	3	2
Open source research software and code	20	46	29	4	2
Preprints	20	46	29	4	2
Open access journals	19	47	29	4	2
Open access archival or special collections	17	49	28	4	2
Interdisciplinary research platforms	17	49	28	4	2
Co-design of research projects	14	52	25	7	2
Open educational materials	14	52	25	7	2
Open research protocols	14	52	25	7	2
Open evaluation	9	57	20	14	2
Co-creation platforms	8	58	19	15	2
Open access preprint servers	7	59	18	16	2
Open access journals	6	60	17	17	2

34% surveyed institutions reported not using any Open Science elements in their academic assessments.

Universities are needed to bring about change

- It is crucial that universities are actively involved in the reform of research assessment
- Universities should make an informed decision on this process
- Universities should be properly represented in the future coalition and its governing bodies
- Only a substantial number of universities joining the coalition will guarantee that the interests of the sector are taken into account in the reform process

UNIVERSITIES AND THEIR ASSOCIATIONS WHO HAVE SIGNED

64% of signatories (308 as of 3rd March)

3 members of the Steering Board

253 universities
9 NRCs
9 other university networks (271 in total)

CoARA

Country	Count
Poland	45
Spain	40
France	35
Italy	30
Germany	25
Sweden	20
Denmark	15
Finland	10
Belgium	8
Portugal	7
Utrecht University	6
University of Barcelona	5
ELTE University	4
Other countries	100

What about CoARA's future... What are the challenges ahead?

- Start CoARA operations
- Keep the momentum going
- Identify quick wins
- Develop synergies with other initiatives
- Expand the membership globally
- Expand the membership in Europe
- Set in motion nationally
- Be sustainable (funding)
- Think about (academic) career assessment

Signing the agreement... What does it mean for my institution?

What to expect and how will it affect us

Signing the agreement... What does it mean for my institution?

Is this Agreement legally binding?

- Not legally binding, but...
- It is an Agreement, with clear commitments.
- Signing the Agreement is a precondition for joining the Coalition.
- Participation on a voluntary basis.
- Full autonomy of organisations, full control on the steps towards the implementation of the Agreement and the speed of the reform journey.
- More of a morally binding signature, towards peer organisations and own community.
- Organisations and their staff can leave the Coalition at any time.

Signing the agreement...
What does it mean for my institution?

A word on coalition funding

- **No membership fee will be applied to CoARA members.**
- The preliminary work plan and budget of the CoARA were endorsed by the Constitutive Assembly.
- The document describes the tasks foreseen for the CoARA during the period 1st December 2022 to 31st December 2023, the corresponding budget necessary and available, and the fundraising strategy.
- The Secretariat has been tasked with **fundraising**. It will engage with public funding organisations, philanthropies, and other organisations within and outside the Coalition. It will also apply to relevant calls for proposals.

Signing the agreement...
What does it mean for my institution?

Resource allocation

Commitment 5: Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to

Purpose: "This commitment will ensure that organisations allocate the necessary resources, whether in the form of budget or staff capacity, to improve research assessment practices within their agreed timeframe."

"Resources should be allocated as is needed for each organisation to achieve the changes that will enable adherence to the Principles and to implement the Commitments."

Each institution will be autonomous in deciding the type and amount of resources they will commit to implement the Agreement. There is no minimum requirement.

Signing the agreement...
What does it mean for my institution?

- Concrete steps and activities to be developed in Year 1 and up to Year 5 will be decided by each institution.
- Each institution will develop its own path in the implementation of the Agreement.
- No benchmarking with other institutions.

Participants will keep full control on the steps they make to implement the Agreement and the speed of their reform journey, which can vary from one organisation to another depending on many factors (...)

Organisations commit to share information on the progress made and lessons learnt in their reform journey, according to the timeframe included in the agreement. Sharing of information shall be done on the basis of self-assessment and by no means the progress of individual organisations will be validated by the Coalition.

(cf. [FAQ](#))

EUA in CoARA for its members

EUA CoARA work plan
Establishing roles for EUA

Support EUA members

- Support through webinars, seminars, guidelines, etc.
- Platform for exchange and collaboration
 - EUA members in CoARA
 - Non-CoARA EUA members

Engagement in CoARA

- Working Groups
 - Manage/lead a Working Group linked to the core activities of universities
 - Ensure complementarities/synergies between CoARA activities and EUA's activities related to research/academic assessment
- Policy Advocacy in the new European Research Area (ERA)
 - Link CoARA's activities and outputs leading to policy development in the ERA Forum for dialogue with Member States
- Global outreach through sister organisations
- Support to the Steering Board
 - Experience from drafting of the Agreement and establishing the coalition
 - Represent and promote the voice and shared positions of universities from across Europe

Thank you for your attention

More questions?
stephane.berghmans@eua.eu

[in](#) [t](#) [f](#) [v](#)

Panel Session: The European perspective on the reform of research assessment

TERESA MAGUIRE. Director of Research Strategy & Funding, Irish Health Research Board.

Reform of Research Assessment
- research funder perspective

Dr Teresa Maguire
8 March 2023

HRB Mission

To support research that improves people's health, promotes evidence-informed care and creates solutions to societal challenges.

Research. Evidence. Action.

CONTEXT

- The research system is complex and multifaceted with many actors.
- More ambitious, more outward looking and more collaborative than ever (technological advances, digitalisation, open science, big data, demand for interdisciplinary and trans-disciplinary methods and skills).
- Research funding is often expected to provide solutions to problems facing society and governments, and perhaps even to take steps towards putting those solutions in action.

hrb.ie

CONTEXT

- The economic constraints on public funding have multiplied, leading to increased political demands to measure impact and demonstrate the value of investing in research.
- Assessment is one of the most significant processes in the global research arena, encompassing everything from policy goals and programme budgets to project selection, awards and career development

hrb.ie

RELEVANCE

- Focus on quality and excellence
- Incentivise diverse career progression
- Assess researchers based upon both individual and team contributions
- Bridge the evidence-to-practice gap
- Recognise and reward broad range of outputs
- Transparency and trust (including public trust)
- Promote a culture of diversity, openness and research integrity
- Promote and support open science agenda
- Embed a culture of innovation, experimentation and shared learning
- Reduce unnecessary burden across the funding lifecycle
- Ensure that systems and processes are sufficiently robust to safeguard public funds
- Demonstrate impact (and support the case for more funding in research)

hrb.ie

HRB Activities

- DORA funders forum- narrative based CVs
- Unconscious Bias training for staff and reviewers
- Behaviorally Anchored Rating Scale (qualitative and quantitative information)
- Alternatives and adaptations to peer review
- GEP and new EDI committee
- Promoting inclusion in research protocols (including clinical trials)
- Support for, and requirements for, PPI and knowledge users as part of team
- Recognise and fund diverse roles (technical support, administrative, project manager, coordinator, support services)
- FAIR Principles and support for data management plans
- Open Science policy, HRB Open Research platform and NORF Action plan signatory

hrb.ie

HRB Activities

- Investment in research networks to advance shared goals and agendas
- We do not promote/use RPO rankings or journal based metrics
- Research integrity training
- The Ensuring Value in Research Funders Forum (EVIR)- reduction of waste and research on research
- Recognise diversity of outputs (Buxton-Hanney Payback Framework)
- Developing Evaluation Implementation Plan
- Data audit and review of data systems
- Streamline reporting processes
- GrantRef, ORCID and persistent identifiers

hrb.ie

IMPACT

- Potential for and need for (sustained) improvements/change in the system
- There is no single solution that can be applied everywhere and by everyone
- Work together in the direction of a common goal with shared principles
- Work (and learn) together (funder-funder, funders and RPOs)
 - Simplification and harmonisation
 - Alignment and coordination
 - Pilots
 - Tools, frameworks, templates, systems
 - Fora for open dialogue and exchange
- National communities connecting in a global discussion

hrb.ie

Reflections

- **Informed, proportionate and transparent**
- **Evolution not revolution**
- **Will involve responsible use of metrics**
- **Risk appetite (compliance and accountability)**
- **Time, Skills and Systems- resourcing HEIs, HSE and Research funders**
 - **Governments need to acknowledge and invest in the people and systems for assessment, management, governance, coordination and evaluation of research**

Panel Session: The European perspective on the reform of research assessment

PAUL BOSELIE. Chair Recognition & Rewards in Open Science, Utrecht University.

The European perspective on the reform of research assessment

8 March 2023

Professor Paul Boselie, Utrecht University
School of Governance

Universiteit Utrecht

- TEAM
- RESEARCH
- IMPACT
- PROFESSIONAL PERFORMANCE
- LEADERSHIP
- EDUCATION

The Dutch Recognition & Rewards Transformation since position paper 2019

Room for everyone's talent
Focus on the interests of the recognition and rewards of education and research, professional performance, recognition & rewards

Support by Dutch national institutes
VSNU, KNAW, NWO, ZonMw

Key areas:
Education
Research
Impact
Leadership
Patient care (in UMCG)

Strategy Evaluation Protocol (SEP)

SEP 2021-2027 for institutional research assessment in the NL
 • 'standard' replaced by 'strategy'
 • Strategy: (1) context / discipline and (2) strategic choice

Stimulating open science

TOWARDS OPEN SCIENCE

The Utrecht University Recognition & Rewards Transformation

OPEN SCIENCE PROGRAMME

OPEN SCIENCE RECOGNITION AND REWARDS

Primary focus: Individual performance

Output: Quality, Quantity, Impact, Equity, Diversity, Inclusion

Outcome: Quality, Quantity, Impact, Equity, Diversity, Inclusion

The Utrecht University Recognition & Rewards TRIPLE model (2021)

- TRIPLE at UU consists of six parts
- Education;
- Research; and
- Professional Performance
- The Impact domain is an integral part of Education, Research and Professional Performance
- Leadership and Team Spirit are the foundations of the domains of Education, Research and Professional Performance.

UU Recognition & Rewards Transformation

Implementation

- Vision, Mission and Strategy
- Part of the UU Open Science Program
- Multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary
- Team Spirit: towards a collective approach
- Leadership at all levels, hands-on and value-driven
- Support and Academic Staff
- R&R is a culture change
- Career paths (differentiation)

Encouraging academic leadership

Encouraging academic leadership

You	You and your team	You and the organisation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Self-reflection Cultivating mutual trust, giving and taking responsibility Recognising and nurturing diversity of employees Clear communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaboration (interdisciplinary or otherwise) Reinforcing the culture of improvement Encouraging development Results-oriented 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Setting objectives for your own unit and connecting them to UU objectives Realising objectives in the UU Strategic Plan Taking responsibility for the bigger picture

Finding a balance between the individual and the collective

Career profiles:
researchers

Diversification and vitalisation of career paths

The Wilhelmina Children's Hospital

personal development tool

Diversification and vitalisation of career paths

Other career pathways will become more important
[Debbie Jaarsma, Dean of the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine](#)

Diversification and vitalisation of career paths

It is about team effort
[Marianna Tryfonidou, member of the Open Science Team of the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine](#)

Cluster 1: New approaches for diverse academic careers

NINA SHIEL, Trinity College Dublin (CHARM-EU/TORCH).

**Towards a CHARM-EU Inclusivity Plan:
An intersectional Approach to Attain Equality in R&I**

TORCH Second Annual Forum: 8 March 2023
Dr Nina Shiel (TCD)
nina.shiel@tcd.ie

Equality as a European Priority

- United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 5:** Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment
- European Union: Equality between women and men a core value**
 - LGBTIQ Equality Strategy 2020-2025 (including lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans, non-binary, intersex and queer persons)
- European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agenda 2022-2024:**
 - Action 4: Promote attractive and sustainable research careers, talent circulation and mobility
 - Action 5: Promote gender equality and foster inclusiveness
- Horizon Europe:** gender equality as a cross-cutting principle to eliminate gender inequality and intersecting socio-economic inequalities throughout R&I systems

TORCH Recommendations based on Gap Analysis

Ensure gender minority options in official records.	Increase visibility of mentoring schemes and evaluate.	Track funding applications and successes in terms of applicant gender, discipline, School/Faculty of origin
Encourage inclusive language	Increase intersectional elements in strategies, processes and structures	Develop opportunities and career paths for early career/part-time staff
Increase flexible working and focus on employee mental health	Active championing by senior management	Encourage formal and informal sharing of successes and experiences

Benefits of an Alliance Level Inclusivity Plan

One stop shop for EDI in research, teaching & learning	Clear statement to prospective students, researchers, collaborators and funders about values	Opportunity to share EDI expertise within Alliance as well as externally
Accountability for Alliance commitments and actions helps with evaluation	Demonstrates commitment with European Commission priorities at a high level	Guides Alliance level training and capacity building
Helps direct conversation about what the Alliance can do for its members (individuals & institutions)	Offers pathways for demonstratable impact	

TORCH
Transforming Open Responsible Research
and Innovation through CHARM

MOLTES GRÀCIES
MUCHAS GRACIAS
FÓRÇA GRÀCIAS
MANY THANKS
GO RAIBH MAITH ACAT
HEEL ERG BEDANKT
MERCİ BEAUCOUP
NAGYON KÖSZÖNÖM
DANKE SCHÖN!

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WWW.CHARM-EU.EU/TORCH

Cluster 1: New approaches for diverse academic careers

PIA VOIGT, Universität Leipzig. DANIELA PICHLER, Universität Graz (ARQUS R&I).

**Survey and Recommendations:
How to enhance Open Science?**

Workpackage 5 – Open Science Agenda

What is Arqus R.I. Workpackage 5?

Work Package 5 strives for enhancing Open Science within the Arqus Alliance

Implementation and Outcomes:

- ✓ Arqus-wide Survey among researchers regarding Open Science
- ✓ Recommendations to enhance Open Science within the Arqus Alliance
 - Open Science skills implications for alternative assessment approaches
 - Open Science Ambassador Network
 - Open Science training materials

2

Open Science Survey

3

Open Science Survey among Researchers

The aim of the survey of researchers in the Alliance was to gather experiences, hurdles, wishes and suggestions regarding practising Open Science activities. On this basis, and including respective scientific literature on the topic, recommendations were developed for the Alliance, the universities and the researchers in order to enhance Open Science.

- Sections of the questionnaire:
- Open Science knowledge and experience
 - Open Science obstacles
 - Open Science support
 - Open Science needs

Conduct of the survey

- Digital questionnaire via Limesurvey
- July and August 2022
- Researchers at PhD level and above
- Arqus R.I. Universities: Granada, Graz, Leipzig, Lyon 1, Padua, Vilnius

4

Survey Results: Open Science knowledge and experience

5

Survey Results: Open Science knowledge and experience

Survey Results: Open Science knowledge and experience

7

Survey Results: Open Science knowledge and experience

Recommendations on Open Science

Recommendations to enhance Open Science in Arqus

1 Develop and share policies, guidance and training offers among Arqus researchers, provide consulting and increase visibility of Open Science support services.

- Develop specific training offers on various Open Science activities based on researchers requirements and ensure visibility of the offers
- Share training materials and online workshops
- Map local support units, make Open Science institutions more visible
- Promote skill building for researchers and research staff
- Provide Open Science policies and guidance according to research assessment criteria

Recommendations to enhance Open Science in Arqus

2 Introduce rewards and incentives for Open Science practices in research(er) assessment respecting discipline and career stage specifications.

- Consider Open Science activities in research evaluation and as inherent part of research integrity
- Acknowledge Open Science practices as scientific contributions
- Monitor and display Open Science activities in local infrastructures (CRIS)
- Start pilots and discursive formats (e.g. panels, working groups) including researchers as well as academic support staff for the development of quality based criteria and for the recognition of open science activities
- Respect discipline specific differences and include researchers in developing quality based criteria for research assessment

Recommendations to enhance Open Science in Arqus

3 Provide resources, infrastructures and funding to enable Open Science activities regarding the discipline specific needs.

- Provide long-term financial support for quality-assured, preferably community-owned and open source infrastructures and tools
- Provide proper funding for Open Access publications and data sharing via publication funds
- Provide staff resources that support researchers in practising Open Science
- Establish and sustain open platforms for sharing research software and tools and infrastructures within the Arqus alliance
- Provide researchers with shared access to trustworthy Open Science infrastructures within the Arqus Alliance

How to enhance Open Science ?

1 Develop and share policies, guidance and training offers among Arqus researchers, provide consulting and increase visibility of Open Science support services.

2 Introduce rewards and incentives for Open Science practices in research(er) assessment respecting discipline and career stage specifications.

3 Provide resources, infrastructures and funding to enable Open Science activities regarding the discipline specific needs.

List of references

- All survey graphics generated and provided by Tommaso Canesso, Luigi Grossi, Nicoletta Parise, Maria Letizia Tanturri (University of Padua, 2022)
- Kaier, Christian, Walter, Hildrun et al. (2022). Arqus Openness Position Paper (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5881903>
- Recommendations and data will be published open access (tba)

STATEMENTS	0	1	2	3	4	5
1. The citizen science project I took part in was generally interesting to me.	0	1	2	3	4	5
2. I participated in defining the research topic in the project.	0	1	2	3	4	5
3. During the project I learned a method to gather data.	0	1	2	3	4	5
4. I learned how to analyze research results.	0	1	2	3	4	5
5. Taking part in the project I learned how to present the conclusion of my research.	0	1	2	3	4	5
6. There was enough time to complete the project.	0	1	2	3	4	5
7. I had the necessary resources to carry out the project (appropriate materials, help from others).	0	1	2	3	4	5
8. Teachers at school motivated me to participate in the project.	0	1	2	3	4	5
9. Thanks to the participation in the project, I have better school results.	0	1	2	3	4	5
10. My participation in the project was appreciated in my school.	0	1	2	3	4	5
11. Thanks to participating in the project I learned something that was not covered in school.	0	1	2	3	4	5
12. Participation in the project strengthened my interest in science.	0	1	2	3	4	5

Survey for pupils, taken after each cycle

MSCEDU in numbers

- 3 iterations (2020/21 – piloting, 2021/22, 2022-23 – in progress)
- 14 schools in 4 countries
- 20 teachers involved in CS supervision
- over 420 pupils involved in CS mini-projects
- 55 university students trained as CS facilitators
- 3 types of surveys administered
- 4 onsite events organized
- 12 videos in 5 languages developed for instruction and promotion of CS
- 23 academics involved in coordinating, training, modelling CS for schools

Prof. Katarzyna Volek-Kozłowska,
Unvers ty of Coole
mo.eb@uni.opole.pl

FORTHM: Multilingualism in School and Higher Education Lab

FIT FORTHM: MSCEDU Modelling Citizen Science for Education

Thank you!

FIT forthem.
Fostering International Transformation of RRI Practices in European Universities

Cluster 1: New approaches for diverse academic careers

MARIA PIETILÄ, JOUNI KEKÄLE, University of Eastern Finland (YUFERING).

YUFERING portfolio in researcher assessment

Dr. Jouni Kekäle and Dr. Maria Pietilä, University of Eastern Finland
2nd TORCH Annual Forum, 8 March, 2023

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017229

Young Universities for the Future of Europe – YUFE

Ten academic members in YUFE

- Maastricht University
- Nicolaus Copernicus University
- Sorbonne Nouvelle University
- Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
- University of Antwerp
- University of Bremen
- University of Cyprus
- University of Eastern Finland
- University of Essex
- University of Rijeka

YUFERING is a joint project of the YUFE alliance. Among other things, it aims at

- transforming recognition, reward and circulation of talents and teams across Europe, and
- making Open Science the "new normal" by creating a YUFE Open Science Strategy

Calls for reforming research assessment

Examples:

- DORA Declaration (2013): For the purposes of research assessment, consider the value and impact of **all research outputs**. Consider a **broad range of impact measures**, such as influence on policy and practice.
- Leiden Manifesto for research metrics (2015): **Quantitative evaluation should support qualitative, expert assessment**. Indicators must not substitute for informed judgement.
- UNESCO Recommendation on OS (2021): **Open Science allows new social actors to engage in scientific processes**, including through citizen and participatory science, thus contributing to democratization of knowledge.
- CoARA (2022): Recognise the **diversity of research activities and practices**, with a diversity of outputs, and **reward early sharing and open collaboration**.

Research- and evidence-based development of the YUFERING portfolio

Central declarations on responsible research assessment, policy papers, reports on metrics and career assessment, national initiatives on research assessment, narrative CVs

YUFE universities' central recognition and reward structures and examples of qualitative assessment (incl. Open Science) + holistic approaches

What we built:

- Narrative CV focused on researchers' individual capacities and skills supported by evidence (outputs/examples)
- Covers diverse aspects of academic work; holistic view of researchers' expertise and contributions
- In addition to research and teaching, societal interaction and transversal skills in the emphasis (e.g., leadership)
- Focus on the content of work rather than metrics (e.g., focus on a limited number of research outputs)
- Broadening the understanding of outputs (e.g., datasets, software)

YUFERING portfolio

Profile as researcher

- One's background, motivations, strengths and skills, vision for one's career, vision for promoting Open Science

Main merits, achievements and their significance

- Key merits or achievements in
 - 1) research;
 - 2) teaching and supervision;
 - 3) community engagement and societal outreach;
 - 4) teamwork, management, and/or leadership
- Description of 1–3 key outputs/examples/contributions to support the argument. Open science merits or achievements specified

Academic age

- Research experience in years

Conclusion and next steps

YUFERING Portfolio for the purposes of assessment and academic recruitment a result of joint developing within the YUFE alliance

Flexible approach that allows recruiters to emphasise their own priorities (taking into account also the academic field and career stage) and that is applicable to different national and institutional contexts

YUFE-wide piloting taking place in the selection of post-doctoral researchers to [YUFE4Postdocs Programme](#) in 2023

Implications of the portfolio depend largely on the academic gatekeepers' (incl. academic leaders, recruitment committee members) use of the gained information

Reporting in fall 2023

Thank you!
Questions or comments?
Ideas for collaboration?

Please contact:

jouni.kekale@uef.fi, maria.pietila@uef.fi

Cluster 1: New approaches for diverse academic careers

MIHNEA DOBRE, University of Bucharest. RAFAELLA LENOIR, Autonomous University of Madrid. FABIEN BORGET, Aix-Marseille Université (RIS4CIVIS).

Exploring a Path to Research Assessment Reform in a European University Alliance: RIS4CIVIS

CIVIS/ RIS4CIVIS: Fabien Borget (Aix-Marseille Université), Mihnea Dobre (University of Bucharest), Rafaella Lenor Improta (Universitat Autònoma de Madrid)
TORCH 2 conference | 8 March 2023

What is CIVIS?

CIVIS Alliance = part of the pilot programme of **European Alliances Initiative** launched by the European Commission in 2020.

- 1st call = 41 **pilot alliances** (today = 44 alliances)
- Funded both under **Erasmus+** and **Horizon 2020**
- CIVIS = partnership of **11 universities**

<https://civis.eu/en>

What is RIS4CIVIS?

A Swiss project of the CIVIS Alliance:

Research and Innovation Strategy for CIVIS

- 8 universities
- Duration: 3 years (Jan. 2021-Dec. 2023)

<https://civis.eu/en/ris4civis>

The Research component of CIVIS

Main objectives:

- ✓ **Promote collaborative inter-university research** that can impact on complex societal challenges of the 21st century.
- ✓ **Strengthen interactions and co-creation of knowledge** between academics, citizens, private and cultural sectors.
- ✓ **Reinforce the research links** existing between the alliance partners through **interdisciplinarity, shared research infrastructures** and **incentive funding for joint projects**.
- ✓ Being a **vector of change and innovation** and a **model for other University Alliances**.

➔ To achieve these goals, the Alliance is implementing **concrete actions** that will help to:

- develop innovative concrete **Infrastructures/tools**
- enable **exchanges** between scientists
- strengthen the **mobility** of researchers
- promote collaboration between the **research support units**

TRANSFORMATIONAL MODULES

3 STAGES over 3 YEARS
January 2021 - December 2023

MODULE 1 - DEVELOPING A COMMON RESEARCH & INNOVATION STRATEGY
What do we need for strategy, culture and focus on our work as a partnership?

MODULE 2 - SHARING INFRASTRUCTURES
How can we share our research and innovation infrastructure? How can we share our research and innovation infrastructure?

MODULE 3 - REINFORCING ACADEMIA - BUSINESS & SOCIETY COOPERATION
Cooperation of top quality researchers to help to the innovation ecosystem, the EU, the CS, SD, OI and the society.

MODULE 4 - STRENGTHENING HUMAN CAPITAL
How can we strengthen our human capital? How can we strengthen our human capital?

MODULE 5 - MAINSTREAMING OF OPEN SCIENCE
How can we mainstream open science? How can we mainstream open science?

MODULE 6 - EMBEDDING CITIZENS & SOCIETY
How can we embed citizens and society in the research process? How can we embed citizens and society in the research process?

1 - BENCHMARKING
Establishing an inventory of current activities and practices with a view to identifying best practices and to defining a research & innovation strategy.

2 - CONSENSUS BUILDING
Bringing the various partners together to build a common vision and strategy.

3 - VALIDATION THROUGH CASE STUDIES
Using case studies to validate the research & innovation strategy.

INSPIRING OUTPUT
CIVIS RAI STRATEGY AND INSTITUTIONAL TRANSFORMATIONAL MODEL

WP3. Case Studies in RIS4CIVIS

Module 4: "Strengthening Human Capital"

Module 5: "Mainstreaming of Open Science"

- The CIVIS OS Award
- Pilot case study on the Research Assessment Reform

Module 6: "Embedding Citizens and society"

- Set up an adequate common framework for the recognition of Science Dissemination (SD), Citizens Science (CS) and Open Innovation (OI) initiatives by universities: CS/ SD Award; Research Assessment Reform.

Research Assessment Reform in RIS4CIVIS

Challenges:

- **CoARA:** different approaches in the signatory universities (also, different national contexts).
- **Timeframe:** the need to limit the time for reaching a consensus in the pilot phase.
- **Strategy:** establish a long-time commitment for promoting the reform.
- **Scale:** the need to address to different stakeholder and not only to communicate, but also to convince them about the necessity of this change.

Research Assessment Reform in RIS4CIVIS – Global View

CoARA Signatories in the alliance

- Aix-Marseille University
- National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
- University of Bucharest
- Universidad Autónoma de Madrid
- Stockholms Universitet

RIS4CIVIS

CIVIS/ RIS4CIVIS

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Cluster 1: New approaches for diverse academic careers

ANDREAS RAGGAUTZ, Universität Graz (ARQUS R&I).

Activity Framework and Research Assessment Reform - University of Graz Pilot

Andreas Raggautz
Performance and Quality Management
Arqus Development

arQus
Research & Innovation

Where is ...

Where do we come from?

- Research evaluation
- Appointment procedures
- Research information system
- Open Science policy, Open Access initiatives
- Recommendations for research assessment (Quality Audit)

15. März 2022

arQus
Research & Innovation

Research Assessment – Alternative Approaches

- Activity Framework
- Research Fora

→

- focus on quality and impact
- consideration of a broad range of activities
- involvement of stakeholders
- strategic management tools
- in line with CoARA

Arqus Task Force to accompany the Graz' pilot

15. März 2022

arQus
Research & Innovation

Activity Framework

Transparency on the achievements expected at the respective career level and research culture

- activities in research and research funding
- promotion of early stage researchers
- teaching achievements and innovations
- societal engagement / outreach activities
- management performance
- transferable skills

Guidance and support in evaluation and appointment procedures, resource allocation, incentives
Monitoring the performance (dashboard)

15. März 2022

arQus
Research & Innovation

Research Fora

- Format for research units to internally discuss topics centered around
 - innovative research
 - impact within scientific community and the society
 - international visibility
- Outcome: strategy document on the development for the next 10 years
- Bottom-up, flexible, uses the creativity and innovation potential of the unit under evaluation

Traditional formal self-evaluation report can be replaced by the fora

15. März 2022

arQus
Research & Innovation

Further aspects of CoARA

- Assessment by (international) peers
- Bibliometric analysis: yes, but...
- Rankings not used in assessments and evaluation
- Funds for peers, workshops, site visits etc.
- Benchlearning within Arqus, CoARA, national networks

15. März 2022

arQus
Research & Innovation

Thank you!

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arQus
Research & Innovation

We work for tomorrow

UNI GRAZ

Cluster 1: New approaches for diverse academic careers

THRASYVOULOS TSIATSOS, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (EPICUR).

<p>EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP FOR AN INNOVATIVE CAMPUS UNIFYING REGIONS</p> <p>The deployment of a model researcher assessment framework (EPIQAssess) in the EPICCommunity platform</p> <p>Thrasyvoulos Tsiatsos, Associate Professor Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH), WP2-R Leader</p>	<h3>Flow of Presentation</h3> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> EPIQAssess Model Researcher Assessment Framework Towards EPICCommunity Platform
<h3>The context</h3> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Early career researchers on the epicenter! 	<h3>EPICUR Research – WP2</h3> <p>EPICCommunity as basis for strengthening human capital</p> <p>Main aim:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To deploy digitalisation and international collaboration as enablers in the delivery of the Research & Innovation formats: EPICCommunity <p>Main objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To enrich the current research and career evaluation systems with qualitative criteria (EPIQAssess) To create a gamification framework aimed at lowering the threshold for participation amongst underrepresented groups (by offering incentives, such as rules and rewards, e.g. micro-credentials and badges) on top of EPIQAssess to promote EPIMove (EPIGame). To design a non-commercial, open and inclusive registry of European researchers and the necessary platform for creating a European Social Network of researchers (EPICCommunity) to support academic match-making and collaboration.
<p>EPIQAssess Model Researcher Assessment Framework</p>	<h3>EPIQAssess: Problem statement & context</h3> <p>European Universities should create attractive, creative, safe and sustainable academic homes for their most valuable resource: their human capital</p> <p>However, current researcher and staff assessment models are not sufficiently catering for value performance or acknowledgement of competencies and skills</p> <p><i>There is a demand for practical models to help universities achieve these objectives</i></p> <div data-bbox="1240 1121 1419 1289" style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;"> <p>European Council Conclusions May 2021</p> <p>"Deepening the European Research Area: Providing Researchers with Attractive and Sustainable Research Careers and Working Conditions and Making Brain Circulation a Reality"</p> </div> <div data-bbox="1240 1310 1419 1352" style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;"> <p>A practical tool to test new practices fitting in each specific institutional context</p> </div>
<h3>EPIQAssess Description</h3> <p>Key characteristics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Key feature is the focus on actual deployment and implementation of the framework as a practical tool in university life EPIQAssess builds upon a context analysis of recent publications and adds value to the debate by offering an actionable approach to ignite change 	<h3>Structure of EPIQAssess</h3> <p>Two levels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Institutional level Researcher/group level <p>Four Dimensions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Innovation Teaching & Learning Service to Society <p>Categories of criteria</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Core Criteria Specific Criteria Personal Qualities

Implementing EPIQAssess in EPICommunity

Steps towards EPICommunity

Steps towards EPICommunity

EPICUR Researcher Assessment Framework

This framework offers a multi-dimensional set of assessment criteria that fit the needs of today's researchers, including skills related to Open Science, green transition, leadership, entrepreneurship, and interculturality. EPIQAssess marries together both quantitative criteria as well as qualitative assessment practices.

<https://epicomunity.auth.pr/deliverable/assessment>

Steps towards EPICommunity

EPICUR Researchers gamification framework

EPIGame gamification framework integrates inclusive gamification techniques and mechanics. In EPICommunity, through gamification and analytics, the members can monitor their own progress, identify their personal strengths and weaknesses, as well as acquire the acknowledgement they desire.

<https://epicomunity.auth.pr/deliverable/gamification>

EPICommunity Characteristics

- A **social network** for Researchers
 - Interoperable with **Europass**
 - Can be used as
 - basis for strengthening **human capital**
 - a tool for deploying EPIQAssess / **Peer assessment**
 - a tool for ECR/Professors **matchmaking**
 - as a tool for **collaboration** in groups
 - as a tool for finding experts/expose **profiles**
-

EPICommunity as basis for **strengthening human capital**

EPICommunity as a tool for deploying **EPIQAssess / Peer assessment**

EPICommunity as a tool for ECR/Professors **matchmaking**

EPICCommunity
as a tool for **collaboration** in groups

EPICCommunity
as a tool for **finding experts/expose profiles**

Demo!
<https://epicommunity.auth.gr>

EPICCommunity

Why to participate ?

Unique Features

• In the past, researchers had to find their own way to connect with peers, showcase their work, collaborate and create groups. EPICCommunity provides a platform for early career researchers.

Social Network of Researchers

• EPICCommunity provides a platform for early career researchers to connect with peers, showcase their work, collaborate and create groups.

Learn More

EPICUR Researcher Assessment Framework (EPICUR-RAF)
The EPICUR-RAF is a tool for assessing the research skills of early career researchers.

EPICUR Researcher qualification framework (EPICUR-RAF)
The EPICUR-RAF is a tool for assessing the research skills of early career researchers.

EPICCommunity platform design
The EPICCommunity platform is designed to support the needs of early career researchers.

Facebook, LinkedIn and EPICommunity google chrome audit

ResearchGate and EPICommunity google chrome audit

Conclusion & Invitation for participation

- EPICommunity is a solid platform implementing EPIQAssess
- EPICommunity is **open**
 - for every Researcher
 - for every Alliance

We are inviting you to participate and collaborate via EPICommunity!

Thank You!
Questions?

Cluster 1: New approaches for diverse academic careers

MARJANNEKE VIJGE, Utrecht University (CHARM-EU / TORCH).

Structure

- UU's Open Science programme
- UU's TRIPLE model
- UU's MERIT model
- Education track in UU
- Towards reforming assessments for CHARM-EU

Guide

Appointing and promoting Faculty of Geosciences academic staff

Version 2.0 Updated February 2022

Career track of an academic staff member
See the figure below.

UD = Universitair Docent - Assistant Professor
 UHD = Universitair Hoofddocent - Associate Professor
 BKQz = Basic Research Qualification
 BKQw = Basic Teaching Qualification
 SKQz = Senior Research Qualification
 SKQw = Senior Teaching Qualification

UD2: BKQz required
 UD1: BKQz required
 UHD2: SKQz or SKQw required
 UHD1: SKQz or SKQw required
 Prof.: SKQz or SKQw required

■ Teaching/research ratio within the bandwidth 30% or 70% and vice versa
 ■ Career principle
 ■ Formation principle: Strategic staffing plan

Education track in UU

In addition, professors with a special focus (e.g. public engagement, interdisciplinary education, regional education)

Towards reforming assessments for CHARM-EU

Challenge:
Education and societal impact not sufficiently recognised & awarded, still prime focus on research

Possible solutions:

- TORCH & beyond: institutional change through analyses & knowledge exchange, e.g. workshops/research visits for managers, support/scientific staff, HR
- CHARM-EU: alliance manifesto
- CHARM-EIGHT: testing research assessments, e.g. transdisciplinary joint PhD programs

Cluster 2: Intensifying R&I cooperation between universities

NICOLE BIRKLE, Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz (FORTHEM / FIT-FORTHEM).

GA No: 101017248

THE FORTHEM JOINT RESEARCH SERVICES AND POLICY OFFICE

A Common Structure for a Better Support for Experienced Researchers, Early-Stage Academics and External Partners in FORTHEM

Dr. Nicole Birkle
FIT FORTHEM Managing Coordinator & FORTHEM General Secretary

presentation based on input provided by Justine Biettron (prev. uB), Anca Serban and Delia Stefanel (ULBS)

2nd TORCH Annual Forum | March 2023

FORTHEM Alliance

- Jyväskylän yliopisto
- Université de Bourgogne
- Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz
- Università degli Studi di Palermo
- Latvijas Universitāte
- Universitetet i Agder
- Uniwersytet Opolski
- Uni. Lucian Blaga din Sibiu
- Universitat de València

Fortthem | Fortthem Alliance (fortthem-alliance.eu)

FORTHEM Alliance

- 1st funding period by Erasmus+ 2019 – 2022
 - 7 partner universities, 3 missions
- 2nd funding period by Erasmus+ 2022 – 2026
 - 9 partner universities, 5 missions

FIT FORTHEM Project

- Funded by H2020 2021 - 2023
 - 7 original partner universities,
 - >2 new partners signed a MoU in 2023

GA No: 101017248

The FORTHEM Joint Research Services and Policy Office

Major objectives to create this first trans-national and transversal support structure

- Reduce site-specific disadvantages in R&I support
- Collect FIT FORTHEM's results & exchanging best practices
- Develop FORTHEM's strategy for funding in R&I
- More joint applications (also with external partners)
- Up-to-date information related to ERA policies and lobbying

GA No: 101017248

What was done so far in FIT FORTHEM ? (coordinated by uB)

1. Establishing strong connections with the representations of the FORTHEM regions in Brussels including
 - organizing 3 joint events with regional representations of Rhineland-Palatinate and Burgundy (contributions of all partner universities)
 - collecting commitment letters of all regional representations to support and collaborate with (FIT) FORTHEM
2. Contributions to policy briefs and recommendations
3. Official Launch of the FORTHEM Research Services and Policy office in June 2022

[Fortthem | R&I Services \(fortthem-alliance.eu\)](http://fortthem-r-i-services.fortthem-alliance.eu)

GA No: 101017248

What are the Major Tasks of the Office at Present?

- central contact point for information related to R&I&T within the FORTHEM Alliance
- provide information and help to find the right contact person for R&I&T requests or related to partner search (pool of back-up experts identified at each partner university)
- collect FIT FORTHEM's results for further implementation (agenda's, strategies, recommendations)
- guarantee a smooth transition of the office from an experimental period in FIT FORTHEM to a long-term implementation of this office in FORTHEM (Research, Innovation and Transfer Mission)
- address the group of researchers not involved in FORTHEM Labs but willing to participate and cooperate
- promote the transfer and exchange of knowledge between academia and non-academic partners

What comes next ? (coordinated by ULBS)

- boost services of the joint virtual office
- strategic capacity building in R&I&T
- joint transfer strategy and training for researchers
- joining forces with other EUNs in R&I&T
- network with regional institutions and their representations in Brussels
- FORTHEM Annual Conference

GA No: 101017248

<https://www.fortthem-alliance.eu/fit-fortthem/>

Book of good practices: FIT-FORTHEM.indb (fortthem-alliance.eu)

Social Media

- FORTHEM Alliance - Facebook
- FORTHEM Alliance - Instagram
- FORTHEM Alliance - YouTube
- FIT FORTHEM - LinkedIn
- FIT FORTHEM (@FITForThem) - Twitter
- FIT FORTHEM - Spotify

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Cluster 2: Intensifying R&I cooperation between universities

ISABEL SALGUEIRO, Polytechnic University of Madrid. DAVID SCHKADE, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität (EELISA InnoCORE).

EELISA
European University

EELISA InnoCORE and EELISA Unfolds: opening up our innovation ecosystems, building joint initiatives for innovators and entrepreneurs

8 March 2023

EELISA InnoCORE is a 100% wide funding 100% European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017229

EELISA InnoCORE is a 100% wide funding 100% European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017229

what is EELISA?

- EELISA (**E**uropean **E**ngineering **L**earning **I**nnovation and **S**cience **A**lliance) is the first alliance of Higher Education Institutions from different countries in Europe meant to define and implement a **common model of European engineer** rooted in society.
- EELISA's acronym also pays tribute to women engineers through the memory of **Elisa Leonida Zamfirescu** (1887-1973), one of the very first women to obtain an engineering degree in the world.

EELISA Building Bridges, Bridging Boundaries

Co-funded by:

- European Union
- German Government

In Association with:

- PSL
- zhaw
- FAU
- SanAnna
- ITU

194,000 Students
18,500 Academics
12,000 Administrative staff

Entrepreneurship and Innovation under EELISA

EELISA is developing activities in innovation & entrepreneurship under two projects:

- EELISA InnoCORE**: INNOVation and COmmon REsearch Strategy (3 years)
- EELISA UNFOLDS**: UNlocking Full INNOVation capacity BUILDing and entrepreneurship (2 years)

EELISA InnoCORE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017229

EELISA Unfolds (Unlocking Full innovation capacity building and entrepreneurship)

Our main objective in EELISA Unfolds with regard to entrepreneurship is to bundle the existing entrepreneurship activities of the EELISA network and to build up joint structures by opening existing and offering new EELISA entrepreneurship activities.

Initiatives put in place during 2022:

- ✓ "Change-makers" and "Innovation & leadership" courses to provide practical challenge-based education to students, later consolidated in a credential.
- ✓ Joint repository of materials, videos and quizzes for members of the consortium to be used in their entrepreneurship and innovation education.
- ✓ "Boostee Program" in an online format to train the trainers and provide them with entrepreneurship skills.
- ✓ "InnoHack Event", a hackathon in person event gathering participants from different places of Europe.
- ✓ "Mentorship Program" to gather, share and provide additional tools to existing and startups' mentors-to-be.
- ✓ "European Championship Demo Day" in person event of startups to catch the eye of stakeholders and investors.

Entrepreneurship and Innovation in EELISA InnoCORE: Main Objective

Our main objective in EELISA InnoCORE with regard to innovation and entrepreneurship is to bundle the existing innovation and entrepreneurship activities of the EELISA network and to build up joint structures by:

- Opening existing and offering new EELISA innovation and co-creation activities
 - In EELISA InnoCORE, we accentuate the full innovation cycle in order to optimize the outcome of our research activities in cooperation with business and civil society. So we offer EELISA wide networking, trainings, and joint events on innovation processes, we exchange best practices for social prototyping, and we run test spaces for prototypes and projects that also include evaluation of user experiences. Furthermore, we set up the EELISA Innovation Talks as a public outreach format where research and innovation topics are discussed.
- The EELISA Entrepreneurship Action Plan
 - The EELISA Entrepreneurship Action Plan aims to create an EELISA landscape of startup support along all stages of the startup journey: to share key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses among alliance members wherever possible, to open existing and organize new joint events like startup contests, mentoring programs, and hackathons, and finally to open our innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystems for startups from EELISA partners through joint boot camps and an EELISA startup contest in Nuremberg, Germany.

Entrepreneurship and Innovation in EELISA InnoCORE: Main Initiatives put in place

- Opening existing and offering new EELISA innovation and co-creation activities: The example of the First EELISA Prototype Contest
 - So far, we have organized more than ten workshops and public events on innovation processes and on co-creation activities. Here, however, I would like to highlight only the First EELISA Prototype Contest.
 - The initial situation: We wanted to run test spaces for prototypes and projects that also include the evaluation of user experiences, but we had only one institution in our innovation ecosystem that professionally offers test spaces for prototypes: JOSEPHS – The Open Innovation Lab in Nuremberg, Germany that is part of FAU's innovation ecosystem.

Entrepreneurship and Innovation EELISA InnoCORE: Main Initiatives put in place

- Opening existing and offering new EELISA innovation and co-creation activities: The example of the First EELISA Prototype Contest
 - So we had to think about possibilities to open JOSEPHS to EELISA. The means of choice was to launch the First EELISA Prototype Contest in October 2022. The winning prototype got the first EELISA test space (worth 15,000 €) at JOSEPHS. Additionally, applicants with the best prototype from each EELISA partner could win a co-creation workshop with JOSEPHS' open innovation experts.

Entrepreneurship and Innovation EELISA InnoCORE: Main Initiatives put in place

- 1. Opening existing and offering new EELISA innovation and co-creation activities: The example of the First EELISA Prototype Contest**
- The EELISA test space at JOSEPHS did not only help the researcher and innovator from the startup with the winning prototype to get honest feedback from potential customers and access to a long-standing expertise in open innovation and co-creation, but also helped to disseminate successful open innovation practices in EELISA and bring about institutional transformation towards a more European innovation ecosystem.
 - The winning prototype, a nature-based air purifier developed by "The Green Factor", a startup from the EELISA partner university UPW in Madrid, addresses the serious problem of air pollution that is virulent in many European cities. The air purifier was tested by more than 100 potential customers and their user experiences were professionally evaluated in a co-creation process.
 - The evaluation of user experiences greatly helped the startup to get important information about the needs and wants of potential customers before the market launch of its product. Thus, the startup was able to integrate user feedback already into their product development and to create a product that people actually desire and are finally willing to pay a price for. This is a key element in any successful innovation process.

Entrepreneurship and Innovation EELISA InnoCORE: Main Initiatives put in place

- 1. Opening existing and offering new EELISA innovation and co-creation activities: The example of the First EELISA Prototype Contest**
- Some impressions from the first EELISA test space at JOSEPHS:

Entrepreneurship and Innovation EELISA InnoCORE: Main Initiatives put in place

2. The EELISA Entrepreneurship Action Plan rests on four pillars and aims...

- I. ... to create an EELISA landscape of startup support along all stages of the startup journey.
- In a mapping exercise, we are about to create a complete overview of the key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses at each EELISA partner with a particular focus on those that can be opened to all EELISA partners.
- II. ... to share key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses among alliance members wherever possible.
- As a minimum, we will interlink the key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses and promote them via EELISA media channels for innovation. Additionally, we might transform the mapping in the EELISA Entrepreneurship Action Plan into an overview on the EELISA website to make our resources better visible, accessible, and coordinated. Finally, we might organize networking events to better connect our key players and resources of startup support.

Entrepreneurship and Innovation EELISA InnoCORE: Main Initiatives put in place

2. The EELISA Entrepreneurship Action Plan rests on four pillars and aims...

- III. ... to open existing and organize new joint events like startup contests, mentoring programs, and hackathons.
- This can be easily done and increases the offer and networking opportunities for our startups and innovators. Moreover, this increases the effectiveness and outreach of single events.
- IV. ... and finally, to open our innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystems for startups from EELISA partners through joint boot camps and an EELISA startup contest in Nuremberg, Germany.
- To help startups scale on a European level (and EELISA covers many lucrative European markets), we will organize boot camps to inform participants about market access and to convey general basics like pitching or negotiation. Furthermore, we want to foster networking of existing founders and startups with each other, to promote this goal, we will also organize an EELISA startup contest that will give startups the opportunity to build an international network and possibly also to get access to venture capital.

Entrepreneurship and Innovation under EELISA: Strengths and good practices, challenges and barriers

Strengths and good practices:

- Contests seem to be a good means to open and share unique institutions in a European University innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystem and also to open the local innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystem of each EELISA partner.
- To open existing offers for other EELISA partners is easily manageable and quite effective.
- To interlink offers in a systematic way to avoid double structures and reallocate resources to build missing offers for startups and innovators seems to be promising in long-term alliances.
- Pilots are very helpful to learn from. Things have to be done, they can be imperfect the first time, and learnings can be made. In such a way EELISA Unifolds is also helpful as a pilot for EELISA InnoCORE entrepreneurship activities.
- It is a good practice to accompany startup contests with a prior mentorship program.

Entrepreneurship and Innovation under EELISA: Strengths and good practices, challenges and barriers

Challenges and barriers:

- Sometimes we have great offers, but few participants from other EELISA partners. Successful promotion is a key challenge.
- Most startups concentrate on their national markets or native language region and it is still to be seen if European Universities will be able to help their startups to scale on a European level.
- Oftentimes, activities seem to be promoted ad-hoc only a few weeks or days before an application deadline arises. It would be desirable to have a long-term calendar of key EELISA entrepreneurship and innovation activities that is interlinked and coordinated with the activities at each partner institution to improve long-term planning and to increase overall effectiveness.
- The pool of startups at each partner institution has a certain size and many activities have to rely on this pool. However, it would be desirable not just to have to rely on this pool, but also to increase it in the future through targeted activities.

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Cluster 2: Intensifying R&I cooperation between universities

GWENDOLINE TRAINSEL, Université de Bretagne Occidentale (SEA-EU / ReSEArch-EU).

Building a common strategy in a multidisciplinary alliance

Identifying and matching the research forces with societal challenges

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SEA-EU alliance

6 become 9: SEA-EU welcomes three new partners

- 01** The European university of the seas
- 02** 6 initial partners, 3 new ones since 2022
- 03** Two pillars: education & research
- 04** Project ReSEArch-EU: Explore possibilities & develop a common research agenda

SwafS project: ReSEArch-EU

- Resilience & anti-fragility**
Doing research differently:
- Anti-fragility think tank
- Digitalization
- Sustainable research
- Collaboration with non-academic stakeholders**
Going beyond fundamental research:
- Patent strategy
- Numerical platform for shared infra
- Co-design, co-creation et co-development**
Research & society:
- Report on stakeholder & citizen engagement
- Good practices guide for transdisciplinarity
- Open science within and beyond the alliance**
Working on common tools, common guides.
Goal: common framework for open science
- Common long-term research agenda**
Building on its own tasks and the previous activities:
- State of the art of research resources
- Research forces & societal challenges
- Research agenda

How to build a common strategy?

EC commitments

- Task 1: State of the art of research forces**
Knowing the research forces in place & identifying synergies across partners
- Task 2: Matching research forces & societal challenges**
Confront this in depth analysis to the major challenges facing Europe and the world.
- Task 3: The research agenda**
Provide a shared research long-term agenda

Decision makers: a Task Force of VR for research & researchers from various disciplines across the alliance

Challenges of such a task...

- Multidisciplinarity = visibility of a field**
Communication and therefore visibility differs across research fields (e.g. ecology vs history).
- Open Access tools**
Finding Open Access tools to ease reproducibility
- Databases**
Internal databases are incomplete or do not simply exist
Bias in international databases towards humanities
- Research classification**
Finding a classification (research fields) which matches the one used in each partner university

... their solutions

- Multidisciplinarity = visibility of a field**
Data collection across various ways of communication (publications, PhDs, conferences, projects)
- Open Access tools**
- R software
- VOSviewer
- Databases**
- International databases (WOS, CORDIS)
- National and internal databases (e.g. HAL - France, CROSBH - Croatia)
- Research classification**
Frascati classification with macro-disciplines & 42 micro-disciplines

- 01 Agricultural Sciences
- 02 Engineering & Tech.
- 03 Humanities
- 04 Medical & Health Sciences
- 05 Natural Sciences
- 06 Social sciences

An approach to identify research resources

2017-2021 Five year period

- 01** Bibliometric analysis: Thematic analysis based on research fields, Data exported from national and international (WOS) databases. **Over 58 000** of doc. extracted
- 02** Conferences & PhD theses: Thematic analysis, Data provided internally by the partners. **3 747** PhD theses, **1 263** conferences
- 03** Analysis of 53: Smart specialization strategy, Identification of synergies, Data provided by regional & national admin., 53 platform & partners
- 04** Projects funded: Analysis per research component, Data provided internally by the partners. **210** projects funded

ALL regional or national IS

The method

BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS

- Performance analysis**
Using the Frascati classification, two indices were created and analysed per research field:
- A specialisation index (based on the number of doc.)
- An impact index (based on citations)
- Science mapping**
The actual content of publications was examined. The top 100 authors' keywords were used to visualize the main topics within each partner university.

Bigger picture / Closer look

Cluster 2: Intensifying R&I cooperation between universities

JOHN BARIMO, University College Cork. BANU LIMAN, Koç University. ROBERTO SAN SALVADOR, University of Deusto (UNIC).

Towards a Strategy for 'Engaged' Research and a Collaborative Roadmap with Cities and City Stakeholders

John Barimo, Banu Liman and Roberto San Salvador

UNIC for Engaged Research (UNIC4ER)

- Co-Producing a Common Understanding of Engaged Research
- European Declaration on Engaged Research
- UNIC Engaged Research Strategy
- UNIC4ER Meets the City
- Engaged Research Seed Fund

The European Declaration of Engaged Research was signed by University and Municipal Leadership at the UNIC CityLab Festival in Oulu, Finland on the 15th of June 2022

"An overarching term that describes a wide range of comprehensive research approaches and methodologies that share a common interest in collaborative engagement 'with' and 'within' society."

A Cross-Institutional Engaged Research Strategy

- Based on virtual and in-person consultations and workshop
- Grounded by mapping and appraise the existing policies, practices, initiatives and structures at level of partner HEI's, funding arenas and nation states
- Explore the factors that promote or hinder engaged research approaches across the partner institutions (metaframework)
- Showcase good practice in engaged research across the UNIC consortia

UNIC Roadmap with Cities and City Stakeholders

- Objective: to strengthen the boundary spaces between our European University and our post-industrial cities, and by engaging their citizens in co-creating strategies to achieve a truly cross European collaboration space.
- The UNIC4ER Meets the City framework supports and encourage the cocreation of engaged research at a truly European level.
- ER roadmaps for encourage and assistant new collaborative initiatives focusing on post-industrial transitions. E.g., superdiversity, inclusion and mobility research challenges are contextualised for post-industrial transitions in cities.
- Research Roadmaps to be updated on a regular basis.

UNIC4ER Meets the City Framework Process is Continuous and Enables Transformative Engaged Research in UNIC Cities

UNIC Engaged Research Seed Fund

- Objective: to support the concrete work on actual challenges in collaboration with the city and the university partner.
- Promoting the development of research capacity amongst researchers (non-traditional backgrounds).
- Partners needed for the co-creation of the innovation in the approach to post-industrial transition and for the uptake (dissemination and exploitation) of the co-created innovative approaches -> beyond UNIC.
- Promotes the development of truly European collaborations where the initiatives can be made inclusive and representative for the superdiverse populations of the cities involved.
- Currently finalising the selection of award recipients.

Contact Details

UNIC European University Engaged Research

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Cluster 2: Intensifying R&I cooperation between universities

PÁDRAIG MURPHY, Dublin City University (ECIU SMART-ER).

research institute for smart European regions

ECIU SMART-ER
university

Organising alliance institutions to pilot bottom-up challenge-based research
Dr. Pádraig Murphy, SMART-ER PI and Associate Dean for External Engagement (Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, DCU)

TORCH 2nd Annual Forum
Trinity College Dublin – 8th March

ECIU SMART-ER
university

ABOUT the SMART-ER
Virtual Research Institute

- Members**
- University of Twente (Netherlands)
 - Aalborg University (Denmark)
 - Dublin City University (Ireland)
 - Hamburg University of Technology (Germany)
 - Kaunas University of Technology (Lithuania)
 - Linköping University (Sweden)
 - Tampere University (Finland)
 - Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (Spain)
 - University of Aveiro (Portugal)
 - University of Stavanger (Norway)
 - University of Trento (Italy)
 - Institut National des Sciences Appliquées (France)
 - TEC de Monterrey (Mexico)

ECIU SMART-ER
university

- The ECIU University
Research Institute for Smart European Regions:
- 1 New model of barrier-free research and innovation, based on a virtual collaboration environment
 - 2 Framework for joint research that delivers solutions to current and future UN SDG11 challenges
 - 3 Science- society cooperation and citizen science initiatives in practice, to help overcome the limitations of disciplines, sectors and countries.
- During the pilot phase, joint initiatives focus on SDG 11 'Sustainable cities & communities'

Opportunity to connect > 4500 researchers working on ECIU University SDG 11 priority topics across Europe

ECIU SMART-ER
university

More information: <https://www.eciu.org/smart-er-for-researchers>

CHALLENGE-BASED RESEARCH

Research with partners in society, using the grand challenges they face in reality, with the objective of arriving at solutions to these challenges.

- Societally relevant and urgent challenges
- Citizen science
- Team-based research
- Multi-stakeholder (Quadruple helix)
- Use-inspired research

SMART-ER RESEARCH COMMUNITIES

ECIU SMART-ER
university

- Energy and Sustainability
- Circular Economy
- Transport and Mobility
- Resilient Communities
- Citizen Science

Bottom-up communities of researchers and stakeholders across ECIU member institutions.

Communities developed by Research Field Coordinators, active researchers with strong expertise in each area

ECIU SMART-ER
university

Engagement in SMART-ER initiatives

Strong interest and need for more opportunities to support bottom-up approaches and joint initiatives in Horizon Europe

Building a Virtual Research Institute for a European University alliance

Needs include:

- Co-created agenda and mutual understanding across institutions and between all stakeholders
- Programme-based funding opportunities to address complex challenges, building long-term 4-helix partnerships & durable ecosystems
- Recognition of societal impact and flexible research outputs
- Sustainable & holistic approach to funding European University alliances across all their missions
- Clarification on legal issues incl. joint recruitment, affiliation, branding and other issues for a successful alliance

'Challenge-based research for a stronger and more sustainable Europe' ECIU Position paper May 2022

Thank you

Dr. Pdraig Murphy
Associate Professor, School of Communications
Associate Dean for External Engagement, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement #101016988. This result only reflects the author's view and the ECI is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Cluster 2: Intensifying R&I cooperation between universities

CIRO FRANCO, Sapienza University of Rome (RIS4CIVIS).

RIS4CIVIS: Sharing Research Infrastructures for the benefit of CIVIS Alliance community

Ciro Franco,
Head of Sapienza Research Office
8th March 2023

RIS4CIVIS Project overall aims

- To produce an integrated, long-term R&I Strategy enabling members of the CIVIS European University to **integrate their know-how, expertise and resources in the service of Research and Innovation**
- To transpose the CIVIS Alliance strategy into an **Institutional Transformation Model serving as inspiration for other European Alliances** and/or Universities wishing to engage in R&I cooperation as well as for the **European Commission** in designing its future programmes and policy, by **removing fragmentation, regulatory or legal barriers and by fostering optimisation of R&I resources**

European Commission - DG Research
H2020 funding – Science With And For Society sub-programme

The transformation modules

- Module 1: Common Research and Innovation Strategy**
 - Strategy for identification of joint R&I activities
 - Methodology for development of R&I Strategy
- Module 2: Sharing Infrastructures**
 - Common access point to infrastructure
 - Plan for a joint Storage and model for the sharing of infrastructure
- Module 3: Reinforcing Academic-Business R&I Cooperation**
 - Common support to innovation strategies and activities
 - Common approach to IP
 - Joint Innovation Training
- Module 4: Strengthening Human Capital**
 - CIVIS-wide HR&I grade standards on:
 - Open-Access, mobility, re-TRG, working conditions
 - Joint Transdisciplinary Skills Training
- Module 5: Mainstreaming of Open Science**
 - Common approach to Open Science and its transversal support, systems and procedures
 - JOINT OS Training
- Module 6: Embedding Citizens and Society**
 - Shared approach and pipeline to Open Innovation and Citizen Science
 - Support to Science Translational
 - Joint Science Communication training

Logos of partner institutions

Module 2: identified endpoints

- Definition of a long-term joint strategy for the creation of a CIVIS RI label.** The label will be used by the all 22 RIs identified in the Alliance member institutions as open also to external users and available to adopt the same general principles in terms of access and use regulation. In order to receive the label, the applying RI shall accept the principles and the requirements set in the CIVIS RI Charter (label awarding procedure)
- Establishment of one single information access point to CIVIS RIs** by the use of a joint *online Interactive Platform* including RIs available to an open use, even if only partially, by any user belonging to CIVIS institutions and eventually to external users, i.e. users not belonging to CIVIS Alliance, including CIVIS partner organizations and most of all businesses. Aim: enhancing the visibility of RIs not only internally throughout CIVIS community but also externally, towards external stakeholders

CIVIS Charter for RI access and use

TABLE OF CONTENTS

- INTRODUCTION
- PURPOSE AND DEFINITIONS
- EXPECTED BENEFITS
- NON-REGULATORY PRINCIPLES
- RULES AND GUIDELINES**
- RI MANAGEMENT

A set of reasonable and non-invasive principles, based on a soft approach

CIVIS Charter main Rules and Guidelines (1/2)

- The RI is able to offer its services to **international users, with a minimum machine time devoted to external users** coming from other host institutions
- The RI **has internal regulations** describing in particular the **access terms**
- The **conditions of access to the services of the RI are transparently known** to any user
- The RI management ensures that projects are carried out in **compliance with the rules of ethics and professional conduct**, as well as the legislation and regulations relating to safety of property, people and the environment
- CIVIS RI label is mentioned in any R&I output** (i.e. publications, patents, technical reports, etc.) resulting from the use of the RI

CIVIS Charter main Rules and Guidelines (2/2)

- Each labelled RI commits to have a **web page on its institutional website dedicated to the equipment**. The web page should show at least the following information:
 - Scientific Manager of the Instrumentation; Laboratory, location and building of the equipment; Model, type and characteristics of the equipment; Services available by the use of the equipment; Technical staff/Expertise devoted to the use of the equipment; Contacts for requiring the use and the reservation of the instrumentation; Rules of access, including any other relevant information as analysis requirements; Fee regulation for internal and external users
- The scientist in charge of the RI delivers a **yearly report on the use of the equipment by external users** as well as on training/networking activities eventually organized with the participation of external users

Main expected benefits from the Charter and from CIVIS RI label

- Enhanced awareness regarding RI availability throughout CIVIS community
- Fostered visibility of RIs also towards non-CIVIS users
- More efficient and effective use of RIs, also by facilitating RI access
- Transparent access within a common framework and shared principles ensuring quality of RI usage
- Benefits from different services supporting RI development
- Sharing of competencies and expertise
- Opportunity for fruitful networking among RIs
- Enhancement of international mobility of qualified HR
- Reduced fragmentation of the Research and Innovation ecosystem
- Making industry more aware of opportunities offered to improve their products

CIVIS Research Infrastructures IT database

- Creation of the **RI IT tool/database**, that includes all the 172 open Research Infrastructures interested in to be part of the RIS4CIVIS strategy. The database collects information about main characteristics of the RIs (i.e. name, location, description, ERC Panel, keywords, etc..) and how to access them (contact persons, services provided, access requirements, link to usage regulation)
- The database, in order to guarantee its sustainability and continuous updating in the future, will be easily updated by the same scientists in charge of the existing (or additional) RIs (see "[Document guide for scientists in charge of Research Infrastructures](#)")

CIVIS Research Infrastructure IT database

CIVIS Sharing Research Infrastructures Platform

- Release of the "Sharing Research Infrastructure Platform", an online interactive Platform, directly connected to the database, that aims to **enhance the visibility and to facilitate the access and the share of open Research Infrastructures (RIs)** not only throughout the Alliance scientific community but also towards third parties and external stakeholders, including businesses, with the aim of fostering public-private interactions and technology-transfer practices
- The Platform allows to **find, using search filters, information about the main features of each RI** (i.e. name, location, description, ERC panel, keywords, etc..) and how to access them (contact persons, services provided, access requirements, link to usage regulation)

CIVIS Sharing Research Infrastructures Platform

Thanks for your attention

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Cluster 2: Intensifying R&I cooperation between universities

ARNAUD FABRE, University of Montpellier (CHARM-EU / TORCH).

Creation of a virtual Technology Transfer Offices' network (TTOs)

THE PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT NO 101017229.

Why create this network ?

- « **PUI** » (University center of innovation) is a **local network** aiming to share experience with innovation specialists and pool some of our actions in terms of valorisation
- « **Réseau C.U.R.I.E** » is a **national network** with the purpose to stimulate and encourage exchanges between valorisation professionals and the socio-economic community such as CNRS, INSERM...

➔ **The next logical step : Creation of the TTOs network at european level** to encourage common actions about valorisation and innovation, exchange good practices, increase communication between all stakeholders, construction of a common model...

TORCH | TRANSFORMING OPEN RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION THROUGH CHARM

Objectives & actions

Actions to implement

- Creation of a Sharepoint to gather all information related to the network
- Arrange at least 2 online meetings to meet each other, discuss and share good practices and insights about various subjects (*success stories, social innovation...*)

Goal : Reinforce the cooperation between universities on R&I and improve our process thanks to experience-sharing.

TORCH | TRANSFORMING OPEN RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION THROUGH CHARM

Success criteria & risks

Success criteria	Risks
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 2 online meetings are arranged Resource needed : an online space such as Sharepoint to share documents and good practices Create and implement a common process (detection of inventions, strategy of protection, how these inventions/innovations are transferred to be valued, what relationship universities have with start-ups to diffuse innovation...) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of involvement from TTOs, especially if the structure is external to the university <p>➔ Mitigation action : Get a dedicated support in each university to foster the involvement of all TTOs and emphasis on the benefits of this pilot (possibility to translate documents, sharing good practices and advice...)</p>

TORCH | TRANSFORMING OPEN RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION THROUGH CHARM

Milestones

TORCH | TRANSFORMING OPEN RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION THROUGH CHARM

Expectations

Main objective ➔ **Experience sharing**

Our objectives & success indicators :

- ✓ During the first meeting : Discuss about a common document to standardize practices OR have a common process (detection and protection of innovation, transfer, spin-off...)
- ➔ Demonstrate the added value of each partner
- ✓ Regular implication of the network members (email exchange for instance)
- ✓ An open network : Discuss about the idea to solicit an external stakeholder if needed (e.g : EUKTS)
- ✓ Meet us in Montpellier at the end of the year
- ✓ Discuss what can happen after the end of the TORCH project

MOLTES GRÀCIES
MUCHAS GRACIAS
FORÇA GRACIAS
MANY THANKS
GO RAIBH MAITH AGAT
HEEL ERG BEDANKT
MERCÍ BEAUÇOUP
NAGYON KÖSZÖNÖM
DANKE SCHÖN!

Transforming Open Responsible Research and Innovation through CHARM

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017229

Cluster 3: Promoting inter/transdisciplinary research driven by societal challenges

ALBERT DIAZ, VICENTE ROYUELA, University of Barcelona (CHARM-EU / TORCH).

TORCH
Transforming Open Responsible Research and Innovation through CHARM

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017229.

Prof. Albert Diaz & Prof. Vicente Royuela (UB)
March 8, 2022 – TORCH 2nd Open Forum

Creating Multidisciplinary Teams to Conceive the TORCH Research Challenges
Prof. Albert Diaz (UB)

TORCH | TRANSFORMING OPEN RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION THROUGH CHARM

TORCH Transforming Open Responsible Research and Innovation through CHARM

TORCH MEMBERS

- University of Barcelona
- Trinity College Dublin
- Utrecht University
- Eötvös Loránd University
- University of Montpellier

Common RBi Agenda and Action Plan

- Cooperation with Non-Academic Actors
- Open Science
- Citizen Science & Public Engagement

TRANSFORMATIONAL MODULES

- Inter- & Trans-Disciplinary
- Gendered Innovation
- Ethics & Integrity

CROSS CUTTING PRINCIPLES

- Food, Water, Life & Health
- Biodiversity, Environment, Climate Change
- (In)Equality, Economic Growth, Governance, Migration

KNOWLEDGE THEMATIC AREAS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017229.

TORCH Common Science Agenda

GOAL

To develop the **list of challenges** the CHARM-EU alliance would tackle in each thematic area, from institutions strengths and complementarity, taking into consideration the state-of-the-art, the financing mechanisms, barriers and common infrastructure needed to implement them.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- Analysis of **research strengths and complementarities**.
- List of **challenges**: Focus on inter- and **transdisciplinary** cooperation, **SDG-driven** research (societal challenges), and **gender balance**.
- Study **funding instruments, barriers and infrastructures** to implement the common science agenda.

Innovative methodological approach: a multi-step bottom-up participatory process

1 DATA COLLECTION

RESEARCH AREAS QUESTIONNAIRE

- Researchers
- Fields of Science
- Thematic Lines
- SDGs
- Research Keywords

2 BIBLIOMETRICS

- 2 approaches: co-authorship + shared references in publications

INSTITUTIONAL ANALYSIS

Partners Results Breakdown

- Input: Form Results + Institutional Research Plans
- Output: 3 Priority SDGs + List of Potential Researchers

CHALLENGE PRODUCTION

SDG-Expert Focus Groups

- Preparation: Challenge Proposal Form (Researchers)
- 3 SDG Focus Groups
- Outcome: Challenges (at least one per SDG)

D4.2 REPORT

Methodology

- Questionnaire + Focus Groups
- Bibliometrics

Results

- Challenges + KCTs (According to SDGs)
- State of the art (Partners Strengths & Complementarities)

Deadline: January 2022*

Step 1 - Data Collection (results)

389 Researchers

Fields of Science (2022) (No. of Researchers)

SDG Research Areas (No. of Researchers)

TORCH Thematic Areas (No. of Researchers)

Step 2: Institutional Analysis (results)

TORCH Thematic Lines	UN SDGs
1. Food, Water, Life & Health	SDG2 - Zero Hunger SDG3 - Good health & Well-Being SDG6 - Clean Water & Sanitation
2. Biodiversity, Environment, Climate Change	SDG13 - Climate Action SDG14 - Life Below Water SDG15 - Life on Land
3. Inequality, Economic Growth, Governance, Migration	SDG1 - No Poverty SDG5 - Gender Equality SDG8 - Decent Work & Economic Growth SDG10 - Reduced Inequalities
4. Big Data, Artificial Intelligence	SDG16 - Peace, Justice & Strong Institutions Transversal

Step 3: Challenge Formulation (results)

TORCH Research Challenges

SDG3-C1	ACTIVE: Adult Child and Teenage participation In physical activity across Europe
SDG3-C2	Prevention and preparedness of negative effects of climate change on vector-borne infectious diseases
SDG10-C1	Coping with digitalization and the transformation of the world of work as a new source of inequalities
SDG10-C2	Designing better universities to fight against inequalities
SDG13-C1	Preventive Water Sustainable Management of Freshwater resources within a global change frameset (PWSM)
SDG13-C2	Mapping Risks, Joining Funds, Taking Actions – Fostering Nature-based Solutions to Mitigate Climate-related Hazards

Cluster 3: Promoting inter/transdisciplinary research driven by societal challenges

LUDOVIC THILLY, Université de Poitiers. (EC2U / RI4C2).

Co-funded by the Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union

The European Campus of City-Universities – EC2U

Interdisciplinary education & research promoted by the EC2U Virtual Institutes

Prof. Dr. Ludovic THILLY
EC2U Coordinator General

The European Campus of City-Universities - EC2U

7 Universities

- Coimbra (PT)
- Alexandru Ioan Cuza, Iași (RO)
- Friedrich Schiller, Jena (GE)
- Pavia (IT)
- Poitiers (FR, Coordinator)
- Salamanca (SP)
- Turku (FI)

30 Associated Partners

- Cities
- Regional Gvs & Agencies
- Students Associations
- Science parks & socio-economic actors

The European Campus of City-Universities (EC2U)

- 162 000 Students
- 9 500 Teachers and researchers
- 11 300 Staff
- +600 European projects
- 1 221 Joint research articles (2009-2018)
- 1 600 000 Citizens

The European Campus of City-Universities (EC2U)

Representation, for each university of the EC2U Alliance, of the wheel of Science providing the overview of the prominent topics each university has been active in over the period 2009-2018 (source: Scopus & SciVal, coll. Elsevier).

The European Campus of City-Universities (EC2U)

Representation of the 1221 Research articles (and their prominent topics) jointly published by researchers from at least two (and up to five) EC2U universities over the period 2009-2018 (source: Scopus & SciVal, coll. Elsevier).

- SSH
- Health & Biology
- Energy & Environmental Science
- Physics & Engineering

The European Campus of City-Universities (EC2U)

THE GLOBAL GOALS For Sustainable Development

The European Campus of City-Universities (EC2U)

Addressing all missions of the Knowledge Square

3 Virtual Institutes

- Education
- Research
- Innovation
- Service to society
- Interdisciplinarity

EC2U RI4C2

The European Campus of City-Universities (EC2U)

Addressing all missions of the Knowledge Square

3 Virtual Institutes

- Education
- Research
- Innovation
- Service to society
- Interdisciplinarity

3 EC2U Joint Master Programmes (open in Sept. 22)

- EC2U Joint Masters LIFESINE – Strong Well-being and Healthy Ageing
- EC2U Joint Masters of European Languages, Cultures and Societies in Contact
- EC2U Joint Masters Sustainable Cities and Communities

EC2U RI4C2

European Campus of City-Universities (EC2U)

Addressing all missions of the Knowledge Square

3 Virtual Institutes

- Education
- Research
- Innovation
- Service to society
- Interdisciplinarity

Ongoing:

- Summer schools & Joint PhD trainings
- Mobility programmes for researchers
- Joint PhD theses (cotutelles)
- Joint research programmes

The "Research & Innovation For Cities & Citizens – RI4C2" H2020 project

EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem (PEKE)

RI4C2
Research & Innovation
For Cities & Citizens

Thank you!

contact@ec2u.eu

www.ec2u.eu

Cluster 3: Promoting inter/transdisciplinary research driven by societal challenges

DAITHÍ MAC SÍTHIGH, Institute of Art, Design + Technology (FilmEU).

Dynamic research clusters in film and media arts

Daithí Mac Síthigh

8 March 2023
TORCH Open Forum, Trinity College Dublin

film_eu

FilmEU brings together four European Higher Education Institutions to collaborate around the common objective of jointly promoting high-level education, innovation and research activities in the multidisciplinary field of Film and Media Arts.

FilmEU_RIT designs strategies and action plans around research and innovation in film and media arts.

Research cluster on Cultural Heritage

Pilot 1
The European Archive of Short Animation

Research cluster on Stereoscopic Visions

Pilot 2
Decolonising the Panorama of Congo: A Virtual Heritage Artistic Research

Research cluster on Volumetric Cinema & Future Visions

Pilot 3
Expanded Memories: Artistic Experiments into Hybrid Analogue-Digital Film Production

Research cluster on Volumetric Cinema & Future Visions

Pilot 4
Machine Acts: Collaborative Screenplay Writing with GTP-3

Research cluster on Experimental Sound & Vision

Pilot 5
Artistic research and cognitive film studies: Towards a transdisciplinary understanding of cinema

Cluster 3: Promoting inter/transdisciplinary research driven by societal challenges

DAVID SITBON, Université Paris Cité (Circle U).

WHEN CIRCLE U. MEETS INTERDISCIPLINARITY

DAVID SITBON, CIRCLE U. COORDINATOR

CIRCLE U. ALLIANCE

Aarhus University (Denmark), Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin (Germany), King's College London (United Kingdom), Université Paris Cité (France), University of Belgrade (Serbia), University of Louvain (Belgium), University of Oslo (Norway), Università di Pisa (Italy) and Universität Wien (Austria) have agreed to combine our expertise and common interests to build a European University with the name Circle U.

- 9 partner universities
- 474 796 students (Ph.D. included)
- 64 314 academic and admin staff

<https://www.circle-u.eu/about/facts-figures/>

CIRCLE U. HISTORY

- Ongoing **Circle U. projects**
Erasmus+ "Circle U. project" (Nov 2020 – Oct 2023) with a budget of **5 Mio EUR**
Horizon 2020 "ERIA project" (Sep 2021 – Nov 2024) with a budget of **2 Mio EUR**
- **Circle U. application to Erasmus+ European Universities "roll-out" call 2023**
Application submitted by 31 January 2023
Results to be expected by end of June 2023
Project likely to be started by 1 November 2023

<https://www.circle-u.eu/news/2023/circle-u-2030-new-proposal-submitted.html>

CIRCLE U. ERIA PROJECT

The Circle U. ERIA project was developed in response to the SwafS (Science with and for Society) call for projects of the Horizon 2020 program to strengthen the Research and Innovation dimension of Circle U.

Coordinated by UP Cité, with 40 persons involved in Circle U. and 65 Deliverables and Milestones, it represents a funding of 2 million euros for 3 years with 4 Work Packages:

- Fostering interdisciplinarity to co-construct solutions with other sectors
- Involving citizens and society in research and innovation
- Strengthening human capital
- Structured collaboration at the European level, among pilot Alliances

<https://www.circle-u.eu/news/2023/eria-boost-research-and-innovation.html>

INTER CIRCLE U. PRIZE (ICUP)

To **showcase best examples** of inter- and transdisciplinary research at Circle U.
 • 3 laureates and production of promotional videos by professionals

- **Manon Bajard**, University of Oslo
VIKINGS: Volcanic Eruptions and Their Impacts on Climate, Environment, and Viking Society
- **Robert Arlinghaus**, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin
 Towards Sustainable Fisheries
- **Barbara McGillivray**, King's College London
 The Language of Mechanisation

<https://www.circle-u.eu/news/2023/icup-winners-report.html>

- ICUP Ceremony on November 25th, 2022
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=brur82B_ex8

<https://www.circle-u.eu/news/2022/icup-ceremony.html>

SANDPITS (OR SANDBOXES)

- A **innovative workshop** in UCLouvain, facilitated by a specialist in interdisciplinary research (Samantha Aspinall, University of Leeds), to connect researchers from our Circle U. universities and external stakeholders and kick start research projects.

- Funding applications and seedfunding to be followed

First session: September 12th-13th, 2023

Second session: November 23th-24th, 2023

Sunny days in UCLouvain for our participants

<https://www.circle-u.eu/news/2022/sandpits-second-session.html>

INTERDISCIPLINARY THEMATIC RESEARCH NETWORKS (ITRN)

Support interdisciplinary projects involving at least 3 universities

4 ITRN selected in 2022:

- Risk, Future Narratives and Sustainability : Students' Perspectives from 3 Circle U. Universities (**AU, HUB, UIO**)
- Syrian Refugees in Lebanon and Danemark (**AU, KCL, UCL**)
- Common Atmospheric Pollutants : first aggregation stages + water interactions + aerosol formation (**AU, KCL, UPCité**)
- Global Health, Sustainable Development and Individual Responsibility : contradictory or complementary concepts ? (**KCL, UB, UIO**)

<https://www.circle-u.eu/opportunities/calls/itrn.html>

AN ACADEMIC DIRECTORY TOOL

- To connect our researchers based on research interests and to allow smooth inter-university collaboration

SEARCH

Enter name of research area...

Rows per page: 20 | 21-40 of 183 | < >

University	Name	Research area
University of Oslo	Bjerk Libeth M.	Circle U.; classroom research; video research; online gaming; reading; higher education
Aarhus University	Bjøl Anemarie	Bone biology; Osteoporosis; CircleU

<https://www.circle-u.eu/opportunities/academics/>

TO BE CONTINUED

- Interdisciplinarity is at the core of the Alliance to promote research collaboration
- Several activities to occur every year and link to other interdisciplinary events
<https://www.circle-u.eu/opportunities/calls/call-for-applications-inter-circle-u-prize-2023.html>
<https://www.circle-u.eu/opportunities/calls/sandpits-2023.html>
- R&I integrated into the next roll-out phase

The Circle U. Newsletter: <https://www.circle-u.eu/newsletter/index.html>
 The Circle U. website: <https://www.circle-u.eu/>

Contact : david.sitbon@u-paris.fr

Cluster 3: Promoting inter/transdisciplinary research driven by societal challenges

SÉBASTIEN HUBER, European University Institute (CIVICA).

Bocconi University, Central European University, European University Institute, Hertie School, IE University, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration, Sciences Po, SGH Warsaw School of Economics, Stockholm School of Economics, The London School of Economics and Political Science

CIVICA members

A ten-member alliance founded in 2019 and reflecting the diversity of European higher education

CIVICA Research mission

“The CIVICA Research structure will create an academic network of excellence. Social sciences are imperative to tackling the world’s most pressing issues, and we aim for CIVICA to emerge as world champion of social sciences.”

CIVICA Research: focus areas

- Societies in Transition and Crises of Earth
- Challenges to Democracy in the 21st Century
- Europe Revisited
- Data Driven Technologies for the Social Sciences

Societies in Transition and Crises of Earth

- Societal dimensions of the Earth System & sustainability
- Global Sustainable Development Goals
- Knowledge and assessment systems regarding the environment and development
- Urban transformations

Challenges to Democracy in the 21st Century

- Democratic backsliding
- Reform of democracy; democratic innovation
- Polarisation
- Social embeddedness of democracy (inequality)

Europe Revisited

- Multilevel governance of migration
- Constitutional resilience in the EU
- EU and the world
- Green values and green economy in the EU
- Interdisciplinary approaches in EU-focused social science and humanities research

“The backdrop of the European Union has changed a lot so it’s good timing for the CIVICA initiative to address issues and come up with ideas that will bring forward the entire project of the EU.”

—Gianmarco Ottaviano, Professor of Economics at Bocconi University, member of CIVICA’s thematic group Europe Revisited

Data Driven Technologies for the Social Sciences

- Artificial intelligence and the society
- Societal changes triggered by digital technologies
- Using new technologies for the social good
- Innovative digital methods for social science research

CIVICA RESEARCH

CIVICA RESEARCH

"The process of debating and discussing research interests and finding common activities and interactions is an exciting and fruitful one - even more so in this complicated and isolated period."

—Bogdan Florian, Lecturer at SNSPA, member of CIVICA's thematic group Data-Driven Technologies for the Social Sciences

CIVICA RESEARCH

CIVICA Research milestones

Spring 2021	First call for collaborative research projects (11 selected for funding, a.y. 2021/2022) First two snowball seminars
Fall 2021	First research-oriented hackathon Launch of postdoctoral mobility scheme First international doctoral conference Open Science roundtable event
Spring 2022	Launch of Excellence Tours Launch of innovative research methods workshop Creation of Open Science network of academic and administrative staff Second research-oriented hackathon Second call for collaborative research projects (11 winning projects, a.y. 2022/2023)
Fall 2022	Launch of Open Science training and webinar series Second round of Excellence Tours Two research-oriented hackathons Third round of snowball seminars Second international doctoral conference
early 2023	Third round of Excellence Tours Fourth round of snowball seminars

CIVICA RESEARCH

Spotlight: First call for research proposals

- Open 1 Feb-23 March 2021
- 11 winning projects out of 27 applications
- c. € 400,000 from H2020 plus partners' own resources
- Most teams involve 3-4 universities (one involves 6)
- 59% of all projects submitted had at least one female PI

1 - Attitudes to Inequalities
2 - Contesting the Court
3 - Democracy and its Discontents
4 - Digital Trade Integration
5 - Mapping Emotions during COVID-19 Pandemics using Twitter data
6 - European Polarisation Observatory
7 - Migration, Terrorism, and Democracy
8 - When the Law is Silent
9 - Sustainable Energy and Food Transitions
10 - The Long Shadow of Educational, Skills, and Professional Inequalities in Time and in Space
11 - Welfare, Democracy, and Population under the COVID-19 Crisis

Focus areas:
Societies in Transition and Crises of Earth
Challenges to Democracy in the 21st Century
Europe Revisited
Data-Driven Technologies for the Social Sciences

CIVICA RESEARCH

"CIVICA Research support allowed me to put together a diverse, multi-disciplinary global network, with participants at every level of academia and practice. Coordinating such a massive research project has been a learning experience for me and the whole team."

—Martina Ferracane, Max Weber Fellow at the EUI, team leader of 2021 funded project "Digital Trade Integration - Dataset & Index"

CIVICA RESEARCH

Spotlight: Second call for research proposals

28 of which
Research projects funded by CIVICA

22 funded by CIVICA Research

11 winning projects in October 2022

€350,000 amount of funding for the 11 winning projects

3 average number of partners per winning project

Involvement in winning projects per partner

Bocconi	8
CEU	4
EUI	4
Hertie School	4
IE University	2
SNSPA	2
Sciences Po	4
SGH	2
SSE	2
LSE	2

*new member of the CIVICA alliance

CIVICA RESEARCH

"I very much look forward to starting the MERITA project because our team spans Law, Political Sciences, Economics, Sociology and Management. It is thought to be the seed of a much larger project that builds on the strength of our alliance for societal impact."

—Maria Kallinikou, Professor at the Stockholm School of Economics (SSE) and coordinator of the MERITA project

CIVICA RESEARCH

WINNERS OF RESEARCH CALL 2022

Focus areas:
Democracy in the 21st Century
Europe Revisited
Data-Driven Technologies for the Social Sciences
Societies in Transition, Crises of Earth

civica.eu

WP5

Synergies within and outside CIVICA

Objective: explore synergies and common actions within CIVICA and with other alliances

R&I management Lead: Bocconi	Doctoral training Lead: EUI	Doctoral community Lead: EUI	Roadmap for Interdisciplinary Laboratory Lead: Bocconi	Partnerships with other alliances & beyond Lead: Bocconi/EUI	Highlights 2022/23
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Comparative study of R&I policies Best practices along strategic dimensions Transformation inside and beyond CIVICA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrated advisory doctoral programme Improved contact between doctoral researchers and faculty Recommendations for best practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cross-border interaction of doctoral students Multidisciplinary doctoral conferences Contact with external structures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analysis of results from the snowball seminars Lab focus area Implementation roadmap 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Potential partners for CIVICA Evaluation of potential joint lobbying activities Common projects; dissemination activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International doctoral conference Doctoral training survey

CIVICA RESEARCH

www.civica.eu
justien.huber@eui.eu
[@CIVICA_Research](https://twitter.com/CIVICA_Research)
[@CIVICA_EU](https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC...)

Funded by the Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union.

The European Commission supports CIVICA through the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, under grant agreement No 101017229. This dissemination reflects the views only of the authoring and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Cluster 3: Promoting inter/transdisciplinary research driven by societal challenges

AINE MOORE, University College Dublin (Una Europa).

Una Europa's vision towards interdisciplinary hubs for research

Aine Moore, University College Dublin

Una Europa partner universities

- + Freie Universität Berlin
- + Università di Bologna
- + University College Dublin
- + University of Edinburgh
- + Helsingin Yliopisto
- + Universiteit Leiden
- + Uniwersytet Jagielloński w Krakowie
- + KU Leuven
- + Universidad Complutense de Madrid
- + Université Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne
- + Universität Zürich

Una Europa presentation

Towards a University of the Future: Our journey so far

Una Europa presentation

3

Una Europa in numbers

Una Europa presentation

4

Una Europa 2030 Strategy

Shaping our shared future for the better

Powering the Research of the Future

Enhancing collaboration in research and innovation

- Promotion of **high-quality and long-term research** collaborations to drive the excellence dimension of European research and contribute to the objectives of the ERA
- Advancing knowledge circulation and connecting complementary research strengths in key interdisciplinary research areas to tackle **global and societal challenges**
- Creation of a **trans-sectoral Una Europa ecosystem for research & innovation** through collaborations with other sectors and society
- Focus on **added-value**, going beyond what a single institution can achieve alone and pooling resources to prepare the **future leading researchers** of Europe and the globe

Una Europa presentation

7

Una Europa Focus Areas

Cultural Heritage | Data Science & AI | Europe and the World | One Health | Sustainability | Future Materials

8

Interdisciplinary hubs for research

- Evolution of academic Self-Steering Committees (SSCs) into truly **interdisciplinary hubs for education and research and innovation**
- **Development of strategies & action plans** to support this transformation with actions to boost cross-sectoral capacity, incl. plans for societal outreach projects
- **Focus on enhancing opportunities for early career researchers** incl. their well-being, development of sustainable and attractive research careers and professional skills training
- Development of targeted instruments to incentivize and reward **academic engagement and collaboration** in order to put academics (fellowships, sabbaticals, secondments,...)

Establishing a Roadmap for R&I

Una Europa's R&I Strategy sets out our path towards a common research and innovation ecosystem that supports the entire spectrum of multi-, inter-, and transdisciplinary research.

Supporting multidisciplinary research networks

Opening up research infrastructures and resources

Advancing early-career researchers

Developing an investment pathway to support the implementation of our R&I Strategy

Strengthening research collaboration with society and industry e.g. citizen science

Enhancing research capacities through professional and institutional development

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#Una_Europa

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Cluster 3: Promoting inter/transdisciplinary research driven by societal challenges

NICOLE BIRKLE, Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz (FORTHEM / FIT-FORTHEM).

The FORTHEM Research, Innovation and Transfer Mission

Background and Design

Dr. Nicole Birkle
FIT FORTHEM Managing Coordinator &
FORTHEM General Secretary

2nd TORCH Annual Forum | March 2023

FORTHEM Alliance

- Jyväskylän yliopisto (JYU)
- Université de Bourgogne (uB)
- Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz (JGU)
- Università degli Studi di Palermo (UNIPA)
- Latvijas Universitāte (LU)
- Universitetet i Agder (UIA)
- Uniwersytet Opolski (UO)
- Uni. Lucian Blaga din Sibiu (ULBS)
- Universitat de València (UVEG)

Forthem | Forthem Alliance (forthem-alliance.eu)

FORTHEM Alliance

- 1st funding period by Erasmus+ 2019 – 2022
 - 7 partner universities, 3 missions: 5 Million €
- 2nd funding period by Erasmus+ 2022 – 2026
 - 9 partner universities, 5 missions: 14,4 Million €

FIT FORTHEM Project

- Funded by H2020 2021 - 2023
 - 7 original partner universities
 - > 2 Millions €
 - > 2 new partners signed a MoU in 2023

FIT FORTHEM as the foundation of the FORTHEM R&I T Mission

- WP2: Intercultural and professionalization
- WP3: Common R&I agendas
- WP4: Connect, access, and share R&I resources
- WP5: Living Labs for societally embedded co-creation
- WP6: Joint Virtual Research Policy & Services Office

Thematic Areas of FORTHEM Labs

Two more to come:

- Cultural Heritage
- Arts and Aesthetics

The FORTHEM R&I T Mission based on results from the FIT FORTHEM project

The Main Topics in FIT FORTHEM

- Professionalization in R & I management
- Joint research agendas, and recommendations / protocols related to Open Science Policies, science communication, internationalization of research, co-creation, knowledge transfer, human resources
- Sharing infrastructures and resources, esp. digital resources and showcasing strongholds in research
- Fostering co-creation and an entrepreneurial mindset in FORTHEM Labs and beyond, matching with non-academic partners
- New forms of science communication and showcasing project results
- Establishing joint support structures including a Joint Virtual Support Office

Lessons Learned

- Workshops, boot-camps, and surveys identified Early-Stage Researchers as the most vulnerable group FORTHEM needs to address
- Agendas, policies, action plans, and recommendations will only show their impact after the lifetime of the project
- Strongholds are identified but need more incentives to be matched, especially in case of experienced researchers
- common understanding of co-creation needs to be further developed and trained
- Open Science as a core topic to be further developed and trained
- Office needs to be implemented permanently to guarantee results are exploited

Three core groups and three strategic goals

- Experienced Researchers
- Early Stage Researchers
- Non-academic partners, especially SME and the policy sector

↓

2 work packages in FORTHEM 2022 – 2026

- Joint Research-Innovation-Transfer Services and Policy Office (ULBS, uB)
- FORTHEM Academy for Early-Stage Researchers (JGU, UO)

MAIN STRATEGIC GOAL 1:

Make FORTHEM a breeding ground for excellent joint research projects developed by experienced researchers

MAIN STRATEGIC GOAL 2:

Make FORTHEM a role model for training Early-Stage Researchers (ESRs) prepared for multiple career pathways

MAIN STRATEGIC GOAL 3:

Make FORTHEM a strong partner in the value chain of innovation and transfer processes and in policy advice in the field of R&I T

Tasks of the Research Services and Policy Office (ULBS, uB)

Tasks of the FORTHEM Academy for Early-Stage-Researchers (JGU, UO)

Tasks of the FORTHEM Academy for Early-Stage-Researchers (JGU, UO)

- Co-tutelle programmes and co-supervision of students (UNIPA)
- FORTHEM MasterClass Programme for successful applications in the MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships Programme (JGU)
- Regular online training courses or workshops (UO)
- Doctoral students act as ambassadors for FORTHEM (uB)
- Secondments for Postdoctoral Students (UVEG)

Tasks of the FORTHEM Academy for Early-Stage-Researchers (JGU, UO)

- contributions of ESRs to FORTHEM annual conference (JGU)
- FORTHEM online-journal (UO)
- "My thesis in a nutshell" and Online Science Slams (UO)
- Doctoral students act as ambassadors for FORTHEM (UO)
- FORTHEM ESRs designing their own Open Science projects (LU)

GA No: 101017248

Conclusions

- Setting-up the FORTHEM Research, Innovation and Transfer Mission is a direct result of the FIT FORTHEM project and will also drive the alliance forward in the area of research and innovation;
 - Results from FIT FORTHEM are not lost after the end of the project, but are retained and further evaluated and exploited.
- But:
- There is still a need for better incentives for researchers to participate in the activities of the alliance, implementing structural measures alone is not in the core of their intrinsic motivation;
 - It needs attractive funding programmes for joint research, even in small formats, CSA and funding schemes especially in the WIDERA program are most appreciated, but it needs more attractive funding lines and better synergies between existing programmes.

GA No: 101017248

<https://www.forthem-alliance.eu/fit-forthem/>

Book of good practices: [FIT-FORTHEM.indb](#) [forthem-alliance.eu]

Social Media

- FORTHEM Alliance - Facebook
- FORTHEM Alliance - Instagram
- FORTHEM Alliance - YouTube
- FIT FORTHEM - LinkedIn
- FIT FORTHEM (@FitForThem) - Twitter
- FIT FORTHEM - Spotify

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Panel Session: University with and for Society: promoting Citizen Science within Open Science

MARKO JOAS, Vice Rector for Collaboration. MATS LINDFELT, Director of Research Services, Åbo Akademi University.

Piloting Citizen Science Support through Small Scale Projects – The Case of Åbo Akademi University

CHARM-EU
Åbo Akademi University
Trinity College Dublin

Pure Love. Pure Science

TORCH
Transforming Open Responsible Research and Innovation through CHARM

2nd TORCH Annual Forum 8 March 2023, Trinity College Dublin

About Åbo Akademi 1

1640	1100	5700	1300
1918	Employees in total, 650 working in teaching and research	Undergraduate students and 780 postgraduate students	Scientific publications per year
The Royal Academy in Åbo founded 1640	101	20%	16%
Åbo Akademi founded 1916	The overall annual budget (incl. year 2020) including about 60% government funding and 40% external public or private funding or competitive research funding	The percentage of Finnish speaking students	The percentage of international staff
An independent corporation under public law funded by the government			

13.3.2023

About Åbo Akademi 2

- Åbo Akademi University is a small multi-faculty/discipline university on two campuses (Åbo/Turku and Vaså) and with Swedish as working language
- ÅAU is committed to the **Declaration of open science and research 2020-2025** and associated national policies (edition.fi/tsv/catalog/book/79)
- Internally funded **Citizen Science pilot project 2022-2023** with purpose to develop and test forms of support for citizen science by
 - creating information materials for researchers
 - planning the process
 - supporting at least three research projects with citizen science elements

13.3.2023

About Citizen Science

- Citizen Science first found as a term in 1989 (in MIT Technology Review), but it is just a new name for old stuff or something completely new?
- Different traditions to work with and for society in different disciplines
- Two-way **collaboration with society** is a key element and goal for universities
- Citizen Science is about "developing concepts of scientific citizenship which foregrounds the necessity of opening up science and science policy processes to the public" (Kiesch & Potter 2014), but also about the "engagement of nonscientists in true decision-making about policy issues that have technical or scientific components", and the "engagement of research scientists in the democratic and policy process" (Lewenstein 2004).
- Definition: elements (that vary a lot depending on disciplinary background):
 - Scientific research conducted with participation from the public (in different phases of the research process)
 - Co-creation with the public in the research process
 - Two-way communication and education, both scientists and the public
- Citizen Science (or elements thereof) is also called for example community science, crowd science, crowd-sourced science, civic science, participatory monitoring etc

13.3.2023

About the Pilot at ÅAU 1

- The pilot project - How to engage researchers to include citizen science elements in their research practice?
 - What kind of support might researchers need when using citizen science in their research projects?
 - How to select projects that gain most from different kind of support?
 - What kind of service do we need to develop for researchers and citizens respectively?
 - Which collaborations and services within ÅAU do we need to develop to support citizen science?
- Involved in the project: **ÅAU Library, Centre for Lifelong Learning, ÅAU Communications Department** and representatives from the **Rectorate** (in the steering board)

13.3.2023

About the Pilot at ÅAU 2

- The ÅAU pilot will focus on
 - a) raising awareness amongst our researchers about CS and the general public by using a method for producing new knowledge and science impact – collaborative research
 - b) developing support structures for the researchers
 - c) Developing and training researchers in science communication
 - c) Leading to citizens being active participators rather than objects of science

13.3.2023

About the Pilot at ÅAU 3

- Implementation of the pilot project by:
- Arranging information sessions, workshops and webinars for researchers
- Selecting relevant research projects for the pilot:
 - different faculties and disciplines
 - previous experience and the need for support
 - different forms and levels of citizen engagement
- Developing information material on how to carry out citizen science together with the researchers in the pilot
- Offering researchers support with project coordination and communication to increase the possibilities of cooperation with citizens
- Evaluating the results of the pilot to further develop the support

13.3.2023

Tack! Thank You!

CHARM-EU
Åbo Akademi University
Trinity College Dublin

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Transforming Open Responsible Research and Innovation through CHARM

13.3.2023

Panel Session: University with and for Society: promoting Citizen Science within Open Science

LUKAS WORSCHCH. Head of Division Research and Technology Transfer, Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017229.

Citizen science as part of knowledge transfer actions with SMEs

Lukas Worschech, Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg
Service Centre Research and Technology Transfer (SFT)
Service Centre InterNational Transfer (SINT)
08.03.2023 – 2nd TORCH Annual Forum

Citizen science as part of knowledge transfer actions with SMEs/University with and for Society: promoting Citizen Science within Open Science

TORCH | TRANSFORMING OPEN RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION THROUGH CHARM

Science and knowledge transfer

With the Service Centre Research and Technology Transfer (SFT) the University of Würzburg aims to

- provide important impulses for the economy, society and the environment through research areas with high future potential
- build innovative transfer structures and dynamic innovation networks
- support the acquisition of collaborative projects between science and industry.
- promote start-ups and ensure the evaluation and exploitation of inventions.

The GOAL of knowledge transfer is to transfer knowledge generated at the university to economy and the public sector with a high degree of efficiency and for social and entrepreneurial benefit.
SFT supports networks between university with several hundred regional SMEs via ESF and EFRE projects

ESF-BuDanu: Using Business Data

Knowledge transfer for every employee from SMEs in Bavaria
Learning and further training in digital skills
Exploiting the potential of corporate data

Keyfacts:
3x theoretical concepts, 2x practical workshops - 90 minutes each.
Each measure is certified
Free participation - no obligations & contracts

Prof. Dr. Axel Winkelmann
Email: axel.winkelmann@uni-wuerzburg.de
contact: esf-budanu@uni-wuerzburg.de

Mainfranken Fair Würzburg: a place for citizen science

Exhibition area / number of halls: ~28.000 sqm exhibition space; 23 halls + outdoor area, ~100.000 visitors: general public, SMEs, trade visitors, ...
The university's booth and the ESF-FrischNET Lounge at the Mainfranken Fair attracted interested citizens via

- Development of participatory experiments together with SMEs or staff from didactics
- Accompaniment of the experiments by specialist staff
- e.g. ERP (Enterprise resource planning)-Systems – Business Informatics as test bed for interested citizen

EFRE BigData@Geo: BigData in Geography – Advanced environment technology using AI on the web

Example: Big Data to Application

- Interactive climate atlas conveys knowledge about climate change in Lower Franconia (Bavaria) in a low threshold and user-friendly way
- Citizens are particularly aware of extreme events and are thus primed for the climate change problem, at least in the short term
- The needs of decision-makers from society (here the agricultural sector) shape the scientific knowledge process and lead to products/information that science would not have produced without citizen participation
- Contact: Prof. Dr. Heiko Paeth, JMU, <https://www.bigdata-at-geo.eu/>

MOLTES GRÀCIES
MUCHAS GRACIAS
FÒRÇA GRÀCIAS
MANY THANKS
GO RAIBH MAITH AGAT
HEEL ERG BEDANKT
MERCİ BEAUCOUP
NAGYON KÖSZÖNÖM
DANKE SCHÖN!

FOLLOW US
www.charm.eu.eu/torch

Panel Session: University with and for Society: promoting Citizen Science within Open Science

ELLEN ROEMER. Hochschule Ruhr West.

Opportunities for Citizen Science Projects
Experiences at Ruhr West University of Applied Science

HRW HOCHSCHULE RUHR WEST
UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES

Prof. Dr. Ellen Roemer

CHARM-EU

Ruhr West is a small, young University
A little bit of our history

Year founded	2009
Campuses	Mülheim an der Ruhr / Bottrop
Faculties	4
Institutes	7
Degree programmes	32
Students	6,465

HRW 1

Mülheim an der Ruhr and its citizens
We are located in the Western part of the Ruhr in a diverse community

HRW 2

Opportunities for Ruhr West
Taxonomy of Citizen Social Science projects

Inspired by Sauermann et al. (2020).

HRW 3

Contributory projects
Citizens participating as research objects and discussants

HRW 4

Co-created projects
Institutions are co-creators in research projects

HRW 5

Key experiences
Important ingredients for successful Citizen Science projects are ...

- ... **Engagement** with and integration of researchers and their institutions into the activities of the local community
- ... **Networking** with key stakeholders and actors (citizens, politicians, NGOs, etc.) - digital (e.g., via social media) and non-digital (meetings, events)
- ... Non-scientific **communication** with key stakeholders and actors

HRW 6

Direct and indirect channels of involvement

HRW 7

Panel Session: University with and for Society: promoting Citizen Science within Open Science

JOSEP PERELLÓ. Director of OpenSystemsUB, University of Barcelona.

<p>CoAct Citizen Social Science</p> <h3>Co-designing citizen social science for collective action (CoAct)</h3> <h4>The case of CoAct for Mental Health</h4> <p>Josep Perelló OpenSystems, Universitat de Barcelona / UBICS</p> <p>Funded by the European Union Horizon 2020 Programme SwafS: Science with and for Society 5 years (01-01-2020/31-12-2024)</p> <p>coactproject.eu</p>	<p>CoAct Citizen Social Science</p> <h3>Co-designing citizen social science for collective action</h3> <p>Funded by the European Union Horizon 2020 Programme SwafS: Science with and for Society 5 years (01-01-2020/31-12-2024)</p> <p>coactproject.eu</p>
<p>Consortium of HEIs, RPOs, NGOs and global networks of open science and open data activism.</p> <p>UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA FH: P gig SMC FARN</p> <p>The CoAct project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 8125148</p>	<p>CoAct Citizen Social Science</p> <h3>Citizen Science - Epistemological viewpoint</h3> <p>[Citizen] science... " [...] assists the needs and concerns of citizens" " a form of science developed and enacted by citizens themselves" Irwin (1995)</p> <p>Irwin, A. (1995). Citizen science: A study of people, expertise and sustainable development. Routledge Press.</p> <p>The CoAct project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 8125148</p>
<p>CoAct Citizen Social Science</p> <p><i>"The social is not a part of reality that can be separated off in any meaningful way; instead, it is a principle of connection, association and relationship."</i></p> <p>At Grassroots talking about B, cars and the notion of collective agreements. See Ross (2019), The Social: Translating the art of Citizenship from labor to the marketplace. Columbia University. https://doi.org/10.1111/9781119987902.ch05</p> <p>The CoAct project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 8125148</p>	<p>CoAct Citizen Social Science</p> <h3>Citizen Social Science in CoAct</h3> <p>Participatory research co-designed and directly driven by citizen groups sharing a social concern.</p> <p>The CoAct project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 8125148</p>
<p>CoAct Citizen Social Science</p> <h3>Main Actors of CoAct</h3> <p>Co-Researchers: persons having a lived experience in relation to the social concerns and thus recognized as experts-in-the-field. They are co-owners of the research data and results.</p> <p>The CoAct project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 8125148</p>	<p>CoAct Citizen Social Science</p> <h3>SDG goals</h3> <p>R&I Actions: MENTAL HEALTH CARE, YOUTH EMPLOYMENT, ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE, GENDER EQUALITY</p> <p>The CoAct project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 8125148</p>

CoAct for Mental Health

Social support networks in mental health

What?
Peop's social environment, generated informally, not professionally

What for?
They facilitate the recovery process
They improve the quality of life
They are a preventive factor against isolation and social exclusion

Goals
Understand how they work
Propose actions to strengthen them

The CoAct project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101017229

CoAct for Mental Health

Call for Co-Researchers, Oct '20

Research design proposal call for Co-Researchers, April '21

Programme design and start of activities, June/July '21

Official launching of the chatbot, November '21

CoActeuem chatbot interpretation with Co-Researchers, June '22

Finalising chatbot, January-February '22

2020 2021 2022

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This morning at 8am... I have received a message in Telegram

@CoActeuem_bot
Hello! We are the CoActeuem chatbot, we are here to help you with your mental health. We are available 24/7 and we can help you with information, resources and support. We are here for you!

@CoActeuem_bot is then asking you...

@CoActeuem_bot
Hello! We are the CoActeuem chatbot, we are here to help you with your mental health. We are available 24/7 and we can help you with information, resources and support. We are here for you!

What about you? do you feel the same way?
 A) Yes, I feel the same way.
 B) No, I don't feel the same way.
 C) I don't know.
 D) No, I feel better than before.

And how would you like to be helped?
 A) Yes, I would like to be helped.
 B) No, I don't need help.
 C) I don't know.
 D) No, I don't want to be helped.

CoAct
EUROPEAN UNION

We want to improve mental health with citizen science!

CoActeuem chatbot interpretation: Sun, 13 Feb 2023 10:00:00 AM

How to join the chatbot?

1. Follow the link: [https://t.me/CoActeuem_bot](#)
2. Register on the Telegram channel: [https://t.me/CoActeuem_bot](#)
3. Click on the "Join" button in the Telegram channel: [https://t.me/CoActeuem_bot](#)
4. Click on the "Join" button in the Telegram channel: [https://t.me/CoActeuem_bot](#)

People-to-people chatbot

Photo: Francisco Borhegyi, Jacopo di Torella, Joseph (2022), CoAct D&I. Digital citizen science tools for supporting research. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.602957>

CoActeuem per la Salut Mental chatbot: [https://t.me/CoActeuem_bot](#)

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CoAct

Quadern de Recerca
CoActeuem per la Salut Mental

Recerca científica i innovació tecnològica per millorar la salut mental i el benestar dels ciutadans. Els projectes de recerca i innovació tecnològica són claus per aconseguir-ho.

[https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.602957](#)

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Participants' commitment and dynamics **C*Act**

●●●● The CoAct project. Best awarded funding from the Program. Forns, M. et al. 2020. Horizon and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101017229.

Sociodemographics and its interpretation by **C*Act** CoResearchers

●●●● The CoAct project. Best awarded funding from the Program. Forns, M. et al. 2020. Horizon and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101017229.

Microstories and its interpretation by CoResearchers. Identification of "most relevant" stories **C*Act**

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Aggregating data and the CoResearchers **C*Act** interpretation

Sharing an experiences means...

Have things in common
Be aware that we are not alone
See that we are not isolated
Observe the strength of a community, if a joint action needs to be taken
Awaken empathy
Highlight the differences

●●●● The CoAct project. Best awarded funding from the Program. Forns, M. et al. 2020. Horizon and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101017229.

Complex networks and the CoResearchers **C*Act** interpretation

●●●● The CoAct project. Best awarded funding from the Program. Forns, M. et al. 2020. Horizon and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101017229.

Co-designing citizen social science for **C*Act** collective action

Political fiction → Actions, demands and recommendations

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Joint work with OS team:
Anna Cigarini, Isobele Borhouro, Franziska Peler, Itziar González-Virós and Bàrbara Mitata
CoResearchers: Alba, Ana Maria, Amanda, Assumpta, Cristina, Emma, Josep, Quilona, Sebastia, Vicens and many others!

<https://coactuem.up.edu>

●●●● The CoAct project. Best awarded funding from the Program. Forns, M. et al. 2020. Horizon and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101017229.